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THE SOCIO-GENETICS OF MARRIAGE OF THE MEITEIS OF MANIPUR, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The Meiteis of Manipur have different rules of mate choice. The rules are based on kinship structure of different categories based on lineage, clan and above all, biological degree of marriage matrimony. The use of different terminologies of such rules and the latent meaning attached to these terminologies are self-evident and self-explained. These rules viz., yek tinnaba, shairuk tinnaba, pee tinnaba, pen tinnaba, leinung pen tinnaba, mungnaba and ee-omnaba are neither haphazardly named nor disorderly structured but named meaningfully and are arrayed in a sequential structure. Despite of the influence of hindunization in which many of them are converted into vaisnavism, the people still observe the ancient rules of marriage based on these seven above mentioned rules.

KEYWORDS: *Shagei, Shalai, Tinnaba, pa, pee, marriage, inbreeding.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Manipur which lies in the easternmost part of India bordering to Myanmar, was an independent sovereign country. She was occupied by the British Empire in 1891. She became a dominion part of India in 1949. According to the census report of 2001 (Govt. of Manipur, India), her total population is 23,88,634 of which approximately 50.64% are Meiteis.

Historical period of Manipur with written documents have started very late. However, through oral tradition, it is known that from 34 A.D. different communities have been living in this land as an independent kingdom (Ebungohal, Lairenmayum and Nithoukhongjam Khelchandra. 1967). From the remote past, the Meiteis of Manipur have been observing the

rules of marriage. The present paper attempts to portray the rules of avoidance of consanguineous marriage of the people and the possible reasons thereof.

2. THE YEK AND YUMNAK OF THE MEITEIS OF MANIPUR

The yek and shallai/shalai are the words that connote the entire rules of marriage alliance and kinship ties. The word, 'yek' is derived from the Meiteilon/Manipuri language, 'yekpa' which means 'to paint' and hence connotes 'colour'. There are seven yeks among the Meiteis of Manipur. The seven yeks of people of the Meiteis have different seven colours of cloth to be worn or associated with every yek of the people. The word 'shalai' might be derived from 'Shandokpa Lai', meaning 'the God of Expansion (of population)' which connotes the first ancestor from which descendants are descended. The two words are combined and formed a compound word 'yek-shalai'. The 'yek-shalai' of the Meiteis is similar with the Gotras of the Hindus and its nearest meaning is clan in English. However, majority of the Meiteis after embracing Hinduism in the 17th century used Gotras instead of Yek-Shalai. The seven yeks are:

1. Wangam/Poirei/Meitei/Ningthouja
2. Nungban/Luwang
3. Nongban/Selloi-Langmai/Angom
4. Nongyai/Khuman
5. Ewang/Moirang
6. Thangyi/Chenglei/Sharang-Leishangthem
7. Khaba-Nganba

From early period up to 1435 A.D., there were ten principalities who ruled the ten principalities of Manipur. In course of time these principalities were merged into one group, 'Meitei'. The ten principalities are-

1. Angom
2. Ningthouja
3. Khuman
4. Luwang
5. Moirang
6. Sarang-Leishangthem
7. Khaba-Nganba

8. Haorok-Konthou
9. Phantek
10. Heirem-Khunja

At first, in a yek, there was only one father. Through patrilineal system, his sons set up different families under the same lineage. The families sub-divided under a yek is known as 'shakay/shakai/shagei' (sha means 'body', kayba means 'to break down'). In course of time as population grew up, different families who professed different professions or who executed outstanding activities or after the peculiar activities carried out by the head of the families or the position he hold in the administration etc. were duly acknowledged and relevant title of shagei/yumnak (yum means 'home' i.e. lineage given to every household) was assigned to him. Each yumnak is sub-divided into 'yum/mayum' meaning, 'home/family'. Each family comprises of phunga(s). A phunga (which means 'hearth') is a unit consisting of a couple. If there are two or more phungas formed by the son and daughter-in-law (with or without grandchildren) of the couple, then the phunga is called yum/mayum. There cannot be two same yumnaks within a yek. However, within a same yumnak there can be families of phu kaynaba which are of more distant ancestors or phu kaynadaba which are more near ancestors. Some yeks have more than hundred yumnaks, some others above fifty yumnaks, and some others below fifty. However, there are some yumnaks that have no yeks.

3. THE MATRIX OF MARRIAGE OF THE MEITEIS

The rules of marriage among the Meiteis is traced back to the founder of Kangleipak/Manipur, 'Pakhangba' who is believed to reign from 34-154 A.D. (Kanglei Shanglen Puba Puya, MS). The rule of marital alliance is so instituted through omission and commission of events and experience of the past kings who reigned the kingdom. The strict rules of matrimonial alliance obeyed by the people before hindunization are taken into account. Still the rules are followed by the people though the grip of cord of the rules is not as stronger as before. The rules of avoidance of matrimonial alliance of the people are considered under the headings:

1. Yek Tinnaba
2. Shairuk/Shairup (Shallai Lup) Tinnaba
3. Pee Tinnaba
4. Pen Tinnaba
5. Leinung Pen Tinnaba
6. Mungnaba
7. Ee-Omnaba

8. Ngaknaba

YEK TINNABA

The descendants who are transcending from the same common ancestor are known as Yek Tinnaba descendants who are in the same phurups, shagei and yumnaks. They are under the same paint of colour ('yekpa' means 'to paint' in Meiteilon) and united through the colour symbol ('tinnaba' means 'to unite'). As per marriage rules of the Meiteis, those who are in the yek tinnaba phurups, shageis and yumnaks are proscribed for marriage while those group of people who are not under the same yek and who do not have blood ties are prescribed for marriage. This is because of the belief that children born to the marriage of same yeks are short lived and tend to suffer from diseases and deformities (Rajendra, B. 1993). Perhaps the people might have known it through time tested experiences.

SHAIRUK/SHAIRUP TINNABA

The descendants from a common ancestor who have been separated into different phurup by merging into different yeks are known as shairuk/shairup tinnaba meaning 'united through (the fold of) shairup. The word shairup is derived from shai and lup or rup which are the abbreviated form of shalai and phurup respectively. Shairup tinnaba is of two types, viz., shairuk achouba and shairuk macha. Descendants of children of the parents born to different mothers of a single father are classified under shairuk achouba. The different mothers, one's own and step mothers may or may not have same yek, shagei, yumnak or phunga. Descendants who are fall under such a shairuk achouba are prohibited for matrimonial alliance. This is so prohibited so as to check the hereditary line coming from a single 'pater'. Biologically, this may be because of the high probability of surfacing homozygous lethal genes if married among such descendants thereby causing harmful effects to the offspring.

Shairup macha tinnaba are those descendants who have been descended through mother's line. This is known as 'pee' tinnaba and 'pen tinnaba', which shall be discussed later.

The four shairuk tinnaba groups which are prohibited for matrimonial alliances among the Meiteis are, viz., moirang anouba and angom yek, khuman and luwang, khaba-nganba and chenglei yek, and moirang ariba and nganba yek.

PEE TINNABA AND PEN TINNABA

The word "pee" is derived from 'mapee' meaning 'mother' and hence 'pee tinnaba' means having united through the same mater. The word 'pen' is derived from 'mapen/maben' meaning 'grandmother'. Hence pen tinnaba means descendants having same grandmother. Children born to ego's father's sister's children and ego's father's brother's children are pee or pen tinnaba groups. Matrimonial alliances counting from ego's generation are not allowed up to the third generation. It can be said that if one examines minutely, pee tinnaba and pen tinnaba are forms of shairuk tinnaba.

LEINUNG PEN TINNABA

The descendants descending from the distant mapen (grandmother) but not from the direct mapen are called leinung pen tinnaba group. A woman if married to a man of a yek/shagei/yumnak or different yumnaks of the same yek or different yumnak/shagei of a different yek, then her son's descendants are leinung pen tinnaba group. For instance, in history, Pureiromba Angou's sister, Pureilemnusu first married to a man and she gave birth to Khamchingkon Haiheiba (Panditraj Atombapu Bidyaratna. 1965). Pureilmnusu again remarried to Khaba Yupuroi of Khaba phurup and she gave birth to Krumkoiba. Khamchingkon and his descendants became nganba yek shalai and Krumkoiba's descendants became khaba yek shalai. Therefore, nganba and khaba are in the fold of leinung pen tinnaba (Panditraj Atombapu Bidyaratna. 1965)

MUNGNABA

Mungnaba means something which cannot be done and if breach bad consequences are bound to be happened. Of the various forms of mungnaba, Ee-mungnaba (Ee means blood) is considered as the most important one. Two sibling sisters after marrying to two respective men who are in the same or different yek, shagei and yumnak and the children born to such sisters even though their husbands belong to different yek, yumnak and shagei are in the mungnaba fold and hence their descendants starting counting from the two sisters' generation cannot be marry up to fifth generations. The descendants can marry from the sixth generation (Panditraj Atombapu Bidyaratna, 1965). On the one hand, the rule of matrimonial alliances between descendants who are a little farther away in kinship bond have permission of less number of generation for marriage. For instance, children born to cousin sisters of two sibling brothers having same parents or of step brothers (having common mother but different fathers) are fall under the ee-mungnaba group. The descendants of the two cousin sisters are not allowed to marry up to third generation counting from them i.e. the two cousin sisters. The descendants can marry from the fourth generations (Sambandha Niranoy, Ms). However, the general rules of marriage cannot be ignored (for instance, if the descendants are in the same yek, they are not allowed to marry).

EE-OMNABA

There are few yumnaks descending from pee tinnaba and pen tinnaba groups. These yumnaks though fall beyond the restricted generations of marriage are considered not to allow matrimonial alliances. Such following of keeping exogamous relationship is known as ee-omnaba.

NGAKNABA

Two yumnaks who are not related through kinship, though can marry, do not marry by keeping words by considering themselves as having near kinship ties. For instance, teknonymous relationship maintains ngaknaba relationship.

SUMMARY, DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The Meiteis of Manipur have different rules of mate choice. The rules are based on kinship structure of different categories based on lineage, clan and above all, biological degree of marriage matrimony. The use of different terminologies of such rules and the latent meaning attached to these terminologies are self-evident and self-explained. These rules viz., yek tinnaba, shairuk tinnaba, pee tinnaba, pen tinnaba, leinung pen tinnaba, mungnaba and ee-omnaba are neither haphazardly named nor disorderly structured but named meaningfully and are arrayed in a sequential structure. In yek tinnaba, out of the seven yeks, same yeks are prohibited for marriage as the members of a yek have common ancestors. In shairuk tinnaba, the shalais i.e. the related groups are merged into seven groups basing on the nearness of the kinship ties of the ancestors. The next smaller dimension of shairuk tinnaba is pee tinnaba in which brothers and sisters of the same mother are not allowed to marry. The word “pee” means “mother”.

The next prohibition rule is based on the descendants coming from a grandmother “mapen” and hence the prohibition rule is known as pen tinnaba. This rule is followed by ‘leinung pen tinnaba’ in which the prohibition of marriage is among the descendants of remote ancestors. Mungnaba and Ee-omnaba are the rules of prohibition of marriage of descendants of different degree of generations.

Interestingly, if one tries to dig up the different inner layers of the social perception of the people and analysis of these terminologies, one can reveal and surface the structure of mind of the people behind these concepts. The terms used are feminine genders and the rules of social networks latent and attached to such words and phrases are not deliberate designs but the self-acting sub consciousness of the neural networks of the grey matter. The exclusive use of feminine genders for certain rules of marriage emphasizes the more responsible role of the mother and the mtDNA inherited from her and carrying through every individual irrespective of genders. Thus, pee (mother) not as pa (father) and pen (grandmother) not as pu (grandfather), are used. This gender based rule of social naming may be because of the role played by the mother, the feminine gender. A father’s biological role is almost ended up in 22 seconds by letting his X or Y sex chromosomes to fertilize with one of the X chromosomes of the mother. The embryo as a result of this fertilization is in the mother’s womb for ten months (25,9,20,000 seconds) nourishing through the placenta and separated at the end of the ten months by cutting this cord off the mother. The chance of probability of the mother’s death with no knowledge of modern medical science in the forgone preliterate periods was relatively high as compared to modern times. After the baby is given birth, the mother takes care of its overall physical survival and comforts through breast sucking which is also an exclusive natural capacity of women. Such higher and exclusive biological factors of being “motherhood quality” might have subconsciously creep in to the grey matters of male-centric, patriarchal and patrilineal social system.

If considering the sequence of rules like pee tinnaba, pen tinnaba and leinung pen tinnaba, the shift of terminology from pen to leinung pen is ought to be considered. The word leinung means ‘under the earth’. Hence leinung pen connotes pen under layers of earth symbolizing pen of past buried under the layers of earth far away from the present stage.

Lastly, an attempt to explain why mate choices among same descendants are allowed after 5th degree of generation is worth to discuss. Not allowing of marriage of same descendants up to this 5th degree may be an extensive exaggeration of observing incest taboo which is a universal phenomenon. The question of why then marriage is allowed after a fixed number of generations can be assigned to re-promote and enliven the social ties which otherwise, keep farther and forget forever. Another probable explanation is that the probabilities of surfacing homozygous lethal/dangerous genes through consanguineous marriage is free from such a fixed generation and the people might have perceived it through time tested traditions consciously or unconsciously. This prohibition of consanguineous marriage is found in many of the societies. About 40 per cent of incestuously produced children had serious abnormalities, compared with about 5 per cent of other children (Eva Seemanova, 1971a). William Durham's recent cross-cultural surveys suggest that inbreeding was biologically harmful. In his report, 50 per cent of the offspring were found to be biologically harmful (Eva Seemanova, 1971b). In some societies religious sanction is observed for prohibiting inbreeding the breach of which is believed to cause harm. For instance, the villagers in Yap in Micronesia referred to people who are related through women as "people of one belly" and if two people from the same kinship group married, they would not have any female children and the group would die out (reproduced from, Ember, C.R., Melvin Ember and Peter N. Peregrine, 2002, pp 354). However, coming to the present question of what may be called "the 5th degree generation exogamy" of the endogamous Meities, a very skeptical question arises. The doubtful premise is the deliberate designing of this 5th degree generation exogamous rule. For one thing, recording, examining and reinterpreting of harmful visible diseases and defective births to such consanguineous marriage within 5th degree is hard to believe and plus, one should not ignore the role of demographic factors. For instance, if the interbreeding Meitei population is very small, then the chance of mate choice is relatively less as compared to larger population. This is evident in many of the Meitei villages in which village endogamy because of geographical barrier or any other factors.

Thus, the Meiteis of Manipur still practice their traditional rules of matrimonial knot though there may be slight loose of the grip of knot. Still in matrimonial columns in newspaper or through websites, the rules of yek and shalai are vividly mentioned. These rules mentioned and discussed above have something to do with biological survival. The genetics of inbreeding and its consequences like infant mortality rate (IMR), still births, congenital defects and deformities, observed through socially accepted trial and biologically resulted errors, thus have shaped and come into such a socially accepted social stage. The social rule of marriage has genetical basis and hence may be labeled as socio-genetics of matrimonial alliance.

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BRIEF MYTHOLOGY OF LONGTE-YULLO FESTIVAL OF THE NYISHI TRIBE

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ABSTRACT

The Longte-Yullo, one of the oldest and agriculturally significant festivals of the Nyishis is a harbinger of new season after which begins sowing of seeds on cultivated fields. This festival also commemorates the separation of human being from evil forces by a barricade that took place from time immemorial. The unique feature of the Longte-Yullo festival is non existence of any priest for ritual chanting as there is no ritual sacrifice. However, an altar decorated with white feather of domestic fowl and bamboo decorated flowers etc on top is erected by the villagers to mark the occasion. This Longte-Yullo festival is celebrated by the Nyishis settled in upper belt- including Koloriang, Huri, Sarli, Damin, Parsiparlo circles of Kurung Kumey District of Arunachal Pradesh.

KEYWORDS: Nyishi; Tribe; Myth; Festival; Arunachal Pradesh; Tradition; Custom; God; Deity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nyishi tribe, which inhabits the five districts of Arunachal Pradesh and in some pockets of North Lakhimpur and Sonitpur districts of upper Assam, believe in the existence of some supra-physical beings and ancestor deities. Hence, their customs and traditions may rightly be described as conventional. They also propitiate a great variety of deities - benevolent and malevolent, beneficent and maleficent- which are credited with the power of influencing their lives and actions from womb to tomb. To avoid the anguish and displeasure of these unforeseen supra-physical beings and also to get their blessings, they are (Gods and Goddesses) worshipped

with performances of rituals and festivals individually and collectively by sacrificing domesticated animals and offering rice powder (attang), ginger (takki), fowls feathers (rugmh), paddy (amchuk) and other related items.

The tribe celebrates three main festivals on community basis- Nyokum, Boori-Yullo and Longte-Yullo. Amongst these festivals, Longte-Yullo is celebrated with traditional gaiety and fervour in all the Nyishi dominated districts, mainly in the upper reaches of Kurung Kumey district. It has been celebrated simultaneously across the entire length and breadth of Koloriang circle since time immemorial.

Literally, Longte-Yullo means a large wooden barricade/fence which is erected on community basis in the belief that this demarcates the domain of humans and spirits from ill-intended trespass. This festival is celebrated on the advent of spring season in the month of April (Lachar-Polu).

2. OBJECTIVES

The objective of the present paper is to understand the brief mythological background of Longte-Yullo festival of the Nyishis of Arunachal Pradesh.

3. METHODOLOGY

This paper is based mostly on the primary data collected through participant observation method from the field during the celebration of Longte-Yullo festival at Koloriang. However, some secondary data in the form of newspaper articles and clips has been used. The participant observation method was applied during the festival and the well known community elders were interviewed in connection with the mythological background of the festival.

4. UNIVERSE OF STUDY

The study on present paper was carried out in months of March and April, 2012 at Koloriang, the Headquarter of Kurung Kumey district and in the adjoining villages. The participant observation was, particularly, done on 15th April at Koloriang, which is the day for festival celebration.

5. MYTHOLOGY

As per the myths of the Nyishi community, the genesis of Longte-Yullo is contemporaneous with the marriages of Abu Tain/Abu Tain/Abotani with several wives in the heavenly abode and on earth. Myth had it that Abu Tain/Abotani, the mythical ancestor and progenitor of human race and also the hero of his time, married a number of wives including Nyudo-Noko, Nyudo-Negin, Nyudo-Lote Loder, Nyudo- Nonang, Nyudo-Nosho, etc, all of who were celestial wives. Finding no suitable lady as his life partner on earth, Abu Tain/Abotani decided to avenge his misfortune by creating havoc on earth. Empathizing with his plight, Doriang-ne (a divine and merciful lady) came to know the evil plan of Abu Tain/Abotani. She sent a messenger- Hintejarjo-Pu (a small bird) which in turn impressed upon Abu Tain/Abotani

against resorting to such extreme steps. Further, Hintejarjo-Pu informed that a divine lady named Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne (the most beautiful princess of the earth) was found weaving all the time in a beautiful place on earth.

The bird assured to offer his service to Abu Tain/Abotani. Resultantly, Abu Tain/Abotani with the aid of Hintejarjo-Pu impregnated Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne by applying an ingenious trick. Finally, Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne (the princess of the earth) conceived and gave birth to a baby boy, Atu-Niya.

The birth of a male baby heralded a series of extreme problems for Abu Tain/Abotani. All the malevolent contenders who wanted to marry Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne like Kiarg-Riargh (the prince of forest), Nyor (the prince of land), Sii (the creator of all living things), Pamdu (the prince of snow), began claiming the fatherhood of the child. In this regard, even Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne herself was confused because she could not understand how she could conceive and give birth to a baby without any physical contact with any male.

Finding no acceptable solution, Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne proposed that a series of tests be conducted to ascertain who the father was. Amongst the many tests, she handed over a piece of meat to the child and asked him to give it to his real father. The child crawled from person to person and finally gave the piece of meat to Abu Tain/Abotani, who was sitting at the end of the queue in a pitiable condition, and thereby provoking all other malevolent beings. As a result, the fatherhood was proved and Changa-Garyang-Loyang-Tamang-Ne accepted Abu Tain/Abotani as her legitimate spouse. Then and there, gruesome animosity and malice against Abu Tain/Abotani started emerging from corners in leaps and bounds. Finding it extremely difficult to live in harmony with those malevolent beings, Abu Tain/Abotani sought the advice of Doriang-ne, a divine lady who could foresee the future to suggest as Abu Tain/Abotani could separate and migrate to a safer place. Doriang-ne advised Abu Tain/Abotani to consult and seek the advice of Thugh-Changtung (a divine lady) and Tugung-Butey (a great malevolent spirit). Under such perplexing situation Thugh-Changtung (divine lady) and Tugung-Butey (a great malevolent spirit) felt pity for humankind and advised them to seek the help of Ana-Doriang-ne or Ane-Donyi (mother goddess resembling the sun).

Accordingly, Abu Tain/Abotani was advised to start migration before the dawn of spring season, the time when evils, diseases, epidemics, serpents, etc, are yet to become active on the earth's surface. The mouths of all the domesticated animals and birds to be taken along with them were tied up so as to restrict creation of any noise which could awaken the evil spirits, but some of the evil spirits manage to dig out the plan of Abu Tain/Abotani and his associates. At the same time, Abu Tain/Abotani also committed certain stupidities by not following all the instructions of Ane-Doriang-ne. Due to the follies committed by Abu Tain/Abotani; the malevolent spirits followed the human beings throughout their migration. Herein, the Nyishis believe that till today the malevolent spirits leave no opportunity to cause misfortune and harm to humankind. After having committed certain stupidities, Abu Tain/Abotani, without having any second option once again sought the advice of Ane-Donyi. Accordingly, she gave following advice to Abotani and his Associates:

1. That all unforeseen problems/miseries can be minimized by appeasing the evil/malevolent spirits by performing rituals, offertories and by sacrificing domesticated animals as and when the problem arises.
2. Tugh- Tariap was advised to erect two wooden posts (Lungriap) in upright position, at Narba-Gillang (a pass), one with left hand to restrict the entry of evil spirits or destructive forces in human domain (siikhi doligh-ham, deregh-yarangham, diidhar rachik-ham haghragh debe) and the other with right hand to signify multiplication of human race, his domesticated animals and crops (lapang piire ham, riich-kimu ham, dinte-subuham haghbukh debe).
3. Tugh-Tatup was advised to go to Kampung-Ryang, (where a plant with large leaves grow) to collect kukam (Large Leaves) and with these leaves he was asked to cover the tops and holes, so as to avoid injuries from objects like thorn, poisonous insects, sharp materials etc.
4. Tugh-Changtum was told to prepare attang (rice powder) for feasts of human and deities as sacred refreshment. She was also advised to offer rugmh-amchuk (White fowl feather & un-husked rice grain) to Gods and Goddesses of Namchang-Suku (Settlement areas and source of drinking water) as Nyishu Sujo-Gumlung Chakjo (token for upbringing, care and protection).

Abotani and his Associates followed above instructions religiously and won the love and affections of the deities, with this the era of Nikum-Tugh ended and the era of Niya-Tugung (Atu-Gungte) started. Atu-Gungte (a pious and divine man) and Ayu-Gamru (pious lady with divine nature) led the humans to a safer place and gifted the future generations following household articles, which symbolizes and signifies the domesticated animals or birds and food-grain to men and women folks:

After getting all these household articles, the humans started their own occupations for their survivals. First they started looking for their Gangdha deligh-Gangte deligh (settlements areas). Some of the others who stayed back in gangtung-rudung (their earlier settlement places) started occupying the lands while Gangta-Taba-bu succeeded in occupying new habitats before the others, Gangkar-yayar-ne became the caretaker of the new occupied lands and Gangping-Peming-bu became expert in giving names to land, forest, rivers, hills, streams, materials etc.

As seen above, the humans finally won the heart of the deities and able to defeat evils of malevolent nature, succeeded in capturing and converting the Taab-Taigh Namchang to Heme-Hu Namchang (dwelling places of snakes and bees to playground of joy full children); Sunyu-Tarmu-Abdak-Riitu Namchang to Hu-Namchang (Extinct and barren land to growing up land); Gumgo-Namchang to Ryunghiigh-Namchang (habitats of wild boar to pigs habitat); Dumpung (Deer) to Bingtung (Goat); Bigchugh (Wild Bos frontalis) to Subu (Mithun); Tade (Mountain bird) to Bobhiigh (Fowl) and lastly the humans started striving for their own future, their personal development and prospects. Thus originated the celebration of Longte by the Nyishis and is relevant even till date for the facts narrated in the foregoing paragraphs.

Before, during and after the course of the celebration of Longte Festival, the stakeholder's are expected to observe certain taboos or restrictions which are as follows:-

- a) Any kind of sacrifices which involve bloodshed of animals or birds are strictly prohibited just before, during and after the celebration of the festival.
- b) Dances/Circular movement around the fence is not done except placing or erecting their respective decorated bamboo poles in it and shouting/yelling of hymn called Gugrey with rhythmic.
- c) Giving of domesticated animals like mithun, pig, goats etc. to others are not done for some days after the celebration of the festival.
- d) After the closer of the path with Longte-Lungriap/barricade/fencing neither the stakeholders themselves nor other people are allowed to cross the fencing for at least seven days or less.
- e) Rice powder in paste form is not smeared to people as practiced in some communities. But rice powder is thrown on the sacred fencing and bamboo poles.
- f) There used to be heavy exchange of edible items like Oppo (Local brew) and adding (meat) and also male members used to visit each other's house while females remain in their respective house to receive the guests and to offer them meats & drinks.

The Nyishis believe that these formalities are observed to strengthen the demarcation of domain of humans and spirits and to free from the influences of ill intended trespasses of destructive or harmful forces. In brief, Longte is a customary practice to emphasize the efforts and endurance of humankind to block outside evils like epidemics, diseases and ill influences so that health, wealth and prosperity are maintained.

Thus, it was how the Longte became a traditional and customary practice of the Nyishi community since time immemorial. It was believed to have, first celebrated at Narba-Namchang (After erecting Longte-Lungbe or Longte-Lungriap at Narba-Gillang), a mythical place where the early Nyishis settled and the present day culture of the tribe evolved.

6. CONCLUSION

The Longte is a festival which does not distinguish any person on the basis of age, creed, sex etc. and it does not involve any kind of bloodshed ritual sacrifices during the course of its celebration. It has also close link with agricultural activities of the people. During Longte, the benevolent spirits are invoked for their blessings, so that there may be bumper production of food-grains and the occurrence of famines, damage by pests and rodents, drought, landslide, flood, etc does not hamper cultivation.

The festival also emphasizes on the fertility and multiplication of animal husbandry and human beings for centuries to come. On the whole, Longte is connected with the invocation of benevolent spirits for peace, prosperity and wellbeing of humankind. It was, and is, an organized,

conscious and deliberate attempt to uphold the pristine and age old custom and tradition. In the context of the rapid socio-cultural transitions, the celebration of the Longte festival is a much felt and conscious collective effort to preserve and promote the unique tradition of the Nyishi Community of the State of Arunachal Pradesh for the generations to come... thus popular chanting goes...

“SIILU-GE ATTU-GUNGTE-GE, AYU GAMRU-GE, GINDU ALUSO, ABU NYIA KU-NGAM RICHI-KIMU-AM, DINTE-SUBU-AM, TACHANG-TABIGH-AM HUGAR MUDUBE, SIIKYI-DOLYIG-YE PYANGMA DEBE, DIIRAGH YARRANG-NGE RANGMA DEBE, NU KYILLUNG KYIPPE JIPPI-KA, HAGLO HAGPE JIPPIKA...ATTU-GUNGTE NU, AYU GAMRU NU.....”

This means.....

On this auspicious occasion of Longte Festival (Migration day), May Atu-Gungte, Ayu-Gamru, shower blessings to each one of us with health, wealth, peace and prosperity. And also may they (Atu-Gungte and Ayu-Gamru) protect us from all evils like diseases, epidemics, droughts, famine, accidents, flood, landslide etc. in the years to come (Pingkap, 2012).

Longte-Yullo festival has close links with agricultural activities, too. During Longte-Yullo, the benevolent spirits are invoked for their blessings, so that there may be bumper production of foodgrains and the occurrence of famines, damage by pests and rodents, drought, landslides, floods, etc, does not hamper cultivation. The festival also emphasizes on the fertility and multiplication of animals and human beings for centuries to come. On the whole, Longte-Yullo is connected with the invocation of benevolent spirits for peace, prosperity and wellbeing of humankind.

With the impact of modernisation, cultural diffusion and advent of administration into the Nyishi society, a particular day is fixed for the celebration of Longte-Yullo; otherwise no particular day was fixed earlier. Rather, it was celebrated during the onset of spring season, clan wise or village wise, in the month of April. It was, and is, an organised, conscious and deliberate attempt to uphold the pristine and age-old custom, and tradition. In the context of the rapid socio-cultural transitions, the celebration of Longte-Yullo festival is a much felt and conscious effort to preserve and promote the unique tradition of the Nyishi community of Arunachal Pradesh for generations to come.

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TRADITIONAL RELIGIOUS BELIEFS, PRACTICES AND IMPACTS OF CHRISTIANITY AMONG THE NYISHIS

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ABSTRACT

Belief in the existence of supernatural powers and day-to-day unexplainable experiences has led the Nyishis into believing in other than the material visible world i.e. in the invisible spiritual world or supernatural power. Generally, the people are found to establish a close relationship with the spiritual world either by controlling or overpowering the spirit by enchanting or practicing some techniques and canalising the power or by offering ritual or worship to propitiate the supernatural power for acquisition of the thing or object desired. However, nowadays, there are clear indications that the Christian religious ideas have penetrated into the traditional religion of the people in the Nyishi villages. However, there are still many who retain their traditional religious beliefs and ritual practices which are altogether free from Christian influence. The Nyishis believes in the existence of a number of uyub, the spirits that there are in the jungles, on the lofty hills, on the top of huge or giant trees call Sangrik Sangney (Banyan tree), in rivers, and inside and outside the houses and these spirits often hurt human beings. Most of the Uyub are malevolent in character and cause harm to the human beings.

KEYWORDS: Nyishi, traditional, religion, Christianity, impact, change, belief, spirit, deity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Complex systems of beliefs in the spiritual qualities of nature and at the same time the conception of a Supreme Being are the two significant traits which characterises the traditional religion of Nyishi people. The spiritual worlds of the people are dominated by a number of Uyub

(spirits) either benevolent or malevolent. It is normally believed by the villagers that various diseases, miseries and misfortunes are caused by the evil spirits. These spirits have such great powers that they may exert influence on man in his earthly life and after life too. Almost every tribal people believed in a Supreme God, who is just, benevolent and good. Traditionally, the village people often considered Donyi-Pollo or the Sun and the Moon as one supreme God.

Belief in the existence of supernatural powers is almost universal. Day-to-day unexplainable experiences have led the villagers into believing in other than the material visible world i.e. in the invisible spiritual world or supernatural power. Generally the people are found to establish a close relationship with the spiritual world either by controlling or overpowering the spirit by enchanting or practicing some techniques and canalising the power, for good or bad or by offering ritual or worship to propitiate the supernatural power for acquisition of the thing or object desired.

However, nowadays, there are clear indications that the Christian religious ideas have penetrated into the traditional religion of the people in the Nyishi villages. They have taken up certain 'Christianised' rituals as well as participate in the worship of God in church. Apart from their relative physical isolation from the higher Christian personalities, with certain amount of avidity, the people as a group has definitely come within the Christian social fold. However, there are still many who retain their traditional religious beliefs and ritual practices which are altogether free from Christian influence.

The Nyishis believes in the existence of a number of spirits which are called Uyub. They believe that there are Uyub in the jungles, on the lofty hills, on the top of huge or giant trees call Sangrik Sangney¹ (Banyan tree), in rivers, and inside and outside the houses and these spirits often hurt human beings. Most of the Uyub are malevolent in character and cause harm to the human beings. The most dreaded Uyub are the Dojang and Yapam who resides in the jungles and take a toll of the human lives as they please by making people fall ill. Similarly, Jengee and Pamte, Nyori and Pamsi are known for causing various kinds of fever. A number of these Uyub (spirits) live in the forests that make people miserable by causing fevers and aches, swellings, dysentery and sores. Parte-Ringte Uyub is believed to be responsible for agriculture and, therefore, if a man is to have a good crop, these Uyub (spirits) should be pleased. Then, there are domestic Uyub like Ringtum Partum, Chirr Yorr, etc., who look after the welfare of the family and are given offerings of chicken and fowl. It is very difficult to mention the name of all the Uyub here since their number is very large.

2. OBJECTIVES

The current paper is focused on the following prime objectives:

- i. To understand the traditional beliefs and rituals practices among the Nyishis.
- ii. To understand the emergence of heterogeneous Christian beliefs and practices among the indigenous believers.

iii. And finally, to find out the impacts of Christianity which has brought social change among the Nyishis of the study village.

3. METHODOLOGY

For present paper I used both primary and secondary sources to collect data and to gained information on the given topic and its related aspects. The primary data were collected by undertaking fieldwork between December, 2009 and February, 2010. Secondary data were collected through consulting some relevant available books and articles on Nyishis. I have used conventional anthropological field methods for the collection of field data along with audiovisual tool for documentation. Participant observation method applied during the Christian ceremonial practices in Hiya Baptist Church and group interviews were conducted to find out key informants.

The priests and the well known village elders were interviewed in connection with the traditional religious beliefs and practices of Nyishi. On the other hand, eminent church leaders and members of different denominations were interviewed in connection with the origin and growth or penetration of Christianity in the village.

4. UNIVERSE OF STUDY

The study on present paper was carried out between December, 2009 and February, 2010 at Hiya village, which the name is taken from the hill slope of same name. Hiya, the largest village (in terms of area and population) of Kurung Kumey district is located in the extreme eastern part of the Nyapin circle, one of the oldest administrative circles of the state, with whom a status of small town was declared in the same name in 1953. The village has a population of more than 701 souls as per the recent electoral rolls of 2009. This excludes the population below 18 years of age. The population structure of the studied village is mentioned below:

TABLE NO.1: VARIOUS DENOMINATIONS OF CHRISTIANITY IN HIYA VILLAGE WITH THEIR POPULATIONS

Sl. No.	Denominations	Population		Baptised Members	
		Male	Female	Male	Female
1.	Baptist Church	228	203	115	112
2.	Catholic Church	49	47	41	43
3.	Christian Revival Church	52	60	23	31
4.	Indigenous Believers	34	28	-----	-----

Source: Churches records & Fieldwork (Feb., 2010)/ Hiya village.

In fact, the Hiya village is the blend of two villages i.e. Hiya-I and Hiya-II and one adjoining sub-village i.e. Lumtey. Hiya, once a single village was bifurcated into two villages in the year 2001 where the adjoining sub-village Lumtey shift under Hiya-I. The village has now one government aided newly upgraded secondary school, one centrally sponsored primary school under Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) and two pre-primary community schools. The administrations of the village are run under Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) with 2 Anchal Samiti Members (ASMs) and 8 Gram Panchayat Members (GPMs). Besides, the village too has 2 Head Gaon Burahs (HGBs) with few numbers of Gaon Burahs (GBs). The mosaic of these two combinations looks after the administrations of the village.

5. NYISHI TRADITIONAL RELIGIOUS BELIEF SYSTEMS

One of the major components of a society's culture consists of the systems of values and beliefs which are characteristic of that society. Nyishi traditional religious system has the following components:

5.1. INITIAL RELIGIOUS BELIEFS

There are four initial religious beliefs in the Nyishi traditional religion: (1) the belief in impersonal (mystical) power(s); (2) the belief in spiritual beings; (3) the belief in divinities/gods and (4) the belief in the Supreme Being. These initial religious beliefs are essential to our theological interpretation and analysis of the Nyishi traditional religion and belief systems. Any meaningful and effective Christian approach to the traditional religions must begin from here.

I. BELIEF IN IMPERSONAL (MYSTICAL) POWER(S)

The belief in the impersonal (mystical) power is dominant and pervasive in traditional Nyishi religious thought. The whole of creation, nature and all things and objects are consumed with this impersonal power.

In Nyishi beliefs, the source of this impersonal or (mystical) mysterious power is not always known, but it is usually attributed to the activities of higher "mysterious" powers, whether personal or impersonal that either generates or deposits such powers in things or objects. The potency, efficacy and the durability of such "inhabited" impersonal powers varies from object to object. Some objects are said to be inherently more power induced or "imputed" than others, that is, they are more naturally endowed with powers than others are.

The impersonal powers can be used for both good and evil. The life of a traditional Nyishi with this belief in the impersonal powers is at the mercy of the benevolent or wicked users of the mystical powers at their disposal. This belief is very much reflected in the traditional religious practices and behaviour.

II. BELIEF IN SPIRIT BEINGS

Traditional Nyishi concepts of reality and destiny are deeply rooted in the spirit world. The activities and the actions of the spirit beings govern all social and spiritual phenomena. The spirit world can be divided into two broad categories: (1) non-human spirits and (2) the spirits of the dead (Aram). Non-human spirits are regarded in hierarchical order in accordance with their kind and importance, depending upon their power and the role they play in the ontological order in the spirit world.

First in the hierarchy is the Creator, then the deities, object-embodied spirits, ancestors' spirits and other miscellaneous spirits that are non-human, comprising both good/harmless (benevolent) spirits and evil spirits (malevolent). Man stands between this array of spiritual hosts in the spirit world and the world of nature.

THE SPIRIT WORLD IN NYISHI SOCIETY

What constitutes the spirit world in Nyishi society is summarised below:

- 1) The whole world is full of spirits;
- 2) The abode of spirits is numerous, such as the banyan tree, burial grounds and other places;
- 3) The spirits are classified into two categories, the bad ones (malevolent) and the good ones (benevolent);
- 4) A belief in and practice of exorcism or spirit possession;
- 5) A belief in life after death, future reward and future punishment;
- 6) Spirit possession.

In defining the religious worldview of Nyishi society, we stresses the fact that the spirit world of the Nyishi people is very densely populated with spirit beings, spirits and the living-dead or the spirits of the. The spirit world is the most pervasive worldview. Contained within it are the spirits, the ancestors and the Supreme Being or God.

There is a very close relationship between the spirit beings and the mystical or impersonal powers and forces described earlier. This realm of the supernatural operates mystical power, magic, witchcraft, sorcery and many others. The spirit world or the realm of the supernatural is, in a sense, a battleground of spirits and powers that use their mystical powers to influence the course of human life. These mystical powers can be designated as positive or negative, good or evil, which may bring blessings or curses.

As we have already observed, in the Nyishi traditional religious thought, spirits are believed to dwell or inhabit certain trees like Sangrik Sangney (Banyan Tree), rocks or mountains, caves, rivers, lakes, forests, animals, human beings, the ground and other objects.

The spirit beings are usually divided into two categories: (1) the spirits of the Aram (dead elders or the ancestors) and (2) the non-human spirit beings. The ancestors are close to the humans and serve as their custodians. All spirit beings are endowed with certain powers and they apply these powers upon the humans for their good or for their harm. Because the spirit beings are malicious, capricious and sometimes benevolent, man must be wise in his dealings with the spirit beings. They can easily be angered, provoked or injured by the humans and so man requires tact and wisdom in dealing with them. In dealing with both the impersonal (mystical) powers and the spirit beings, man needs human specialists who have gained experience and access to these two types of mysteries to help them live a successful life and acquire good human well-being. These spirit beings can be “manipulated” to serve the humans or vice versa.

III. BELIEF IN NUMEROUS DIVINITIES

Nyishis for the past few decades have changed certain perspectives and even the definition of Nyishi divinities. Some no longer accept the term polytheism (worship of many gods). They prefer the term “divinities” or “deities” to “Gods”. The debate on whether Nyishi “divinities” were worshipped as “Gods” or whether they were only “intermediaries” or “mediators” is inconclusive. Some¹ argued that “Nyishis do not worship their divinities nor their ancestors, but God”. In this argument, a view is being held that sacrifices, offerings and prayers offered, are not directed to the divinities or the ancestors, as ends in themselves, but are directed ultimately to God. I have no intention of discussing this debate here, but simply to mention it in passing.

Nyishi divinities are many and each has its specific area of influence and control. Some of these divinities were originally mythological figures in some Nyishi legends and primordial histories and cosmologies, while some were tribal heroes or heroines. Divinities covering different aspects of life, society and community were usually established, such as divinities of the sea or the waters, rain, thunder, fertility, health or sickness, planting or harvest, tribal, clan or family deities. Nyishi divinities took the forms of mountains, rivers, forests, the mother earth, the sun, the moon, the stars, and ancestors. The plurality of the divinities with their varying powers, influence, hierarchy, territoriality, even within one ethnic group or community, says a lot about the Nyishi religions, worship, beliefs and practices. This leaves an open door for religious accommodation, tolerance, assimilation and adaptation within the traditional religious thought.

IV. BELIEF IN A SUPREME BEING (GOD)

The people believe in Ane-Donyi (Sun, the mother God) who is regarded as the Supreme Mother, kind and benevolent. She showers her kindness on the society and nothing can be

¹ The ‘some’ in the present context is referring to the converted Christians in the study village.

achieved without her will. She gives crops and keeps the Nassungⁱⁱ (granaries) filled; she gives children and keeps them well; without her mercy nothing could get.

5.2. INITIAL RELIGIOUS PRACTICES

Religious beliefs do beget corresponding religious practices and religious behaviour. The five inter-related and integrated religious beliefs examined in the previous sections have established the theological basis of the traditional religious system. These beliefs have in consequence influenced the development of the corresponding religious practices, which we are going to describe very briefly. The traditional religious system is informed and motivated by these religious beliefs and their corresponding practices, behaviour and feelings.

The people's indigenous religion practices is coherently and comprehensively expressed in their oral traditions in the form of myths, legends, folklore, folktales and performing arts that is passed on from generation to generation by word of mouth by priests and shamans. In the early days, cult of sacrifice was the dominant features of indigenous religious practices of the people in the village. They believed that human share the world with Uyub (spirits) of benevolence and malevolent, which take up residence in every animate and inanimate object, specific places and sometimes in human being. The Uyub is the nearest equivalent term for God used in Nyishi language (Showren, 2007), which literary meaning for both benevolent and malevolent Uyub (Gods).

The foundational religious practices in the traditional religions are: (1) the practices of establishing links, relationship and close ties with the cosmic mysterious, mystical and spirit powers and forces; (2) the practices involving various religious and social rites, rituals (sacrifices and offerings) and ceremonies; (3) the practices of establishing various spiritual and mystical communications with the spirit world and spirit beings and (4) the religious and social practices of relating to the various activities of the traditional Nyishi specialists. Thus, encompassing all these features the traditional ritual practices of people are categorised into following:

1. ROO-KUGNAM (CHICKEN LIVER EXAMINATION): This ritual practice is takes place to ascertain the type of Uyubs through Roo Kugnam or Ruksing Kanamⁱⁱⁱ (omen examination). It is usually perform by the Nyub (priest) and Nyajak (shamans) who are expert in such ritual. At the very beginning, the Nyub use to have a Roo (baby chicken) on his hand blows warm air from the mouth and start the ritual process. Besides this the chicken egg is also examined which coincides with the prediction and result. This examination of egg is called "Paap Chiinam"^{iv}. It is the chicken liver examination which tells everything for which the ritual chanting has been proposed. The chanting is done for specific case to trace out the main cause or vindicating the particular illness. Thus, the Nyub chant to find out the exact cause of the illness.

2. SANGRIK-TANGNAM (CUTTING OF BANYAN TREES): This ritual practice is perform when a man or woman or children is accidentally dead. The chicken liver is examined after chants by the priest whether the spirit or God (Gangda Uyub) has taken away life or not. If the chicken liver indicates positive then a ritual is performed. Until the ritual is complete the dead body remains in the house. In that very evening the people of the whole village are quietly

informed to get ready for an attack journey. In the next morning, a Ryatar^v is performed for an all-round protection and to gain power and strength to fight against the evil spirits. The villagers then attack that particular tree called Sangrik Sangney (Banyan Tree). The people arrived suddenly around the tree with a weapons accompanied by a Nyub (priest) and tied a rope around the tree. When the tree is felled down, its upper portion is well guarded. Whatever the animals like snakes, birds, lizards, squirrels, and many other comes out are killed. It is believe that they are the form of evil spirits who have taken the life of a human being. This ritual is kind of revenge to the evils. The priest chants and people follow him during the attack in the following manner. It is called Gamte Tanam^{vi}.

Sugh Gangtey Ge Atu nu, Ish Ge Ayu nu

Nu debe dapa nilo, tangbe tangpa nilo

Ho Gangtey Atu no, Anglik yama be

Uyub namtam namdar taju,

Sungkung namtam namdar taju

Poyub nyatey nu, Nyayub nyatey nu

Sanglum namtam namdar taju,

Sangrik namtam namdar taju.

The above phrase means: “Oh..! The owner of this land if you have taken the life of our man then you should not leave. We are going to destroy you and your dwelling place too.” Thus, it is a warning and challenge to the evil spirits called ‘Poyub’ and ‘Nyayub’. Lastly the tree is burnt down. After this, they retreat to their house with pronouncing a peculiar sound called Gugre Renam^{vii} while coming back. After reaching the village, the killed birds and animals are fixed on the Dapo^{viii} (pole) and are shooting with arrows by the villagers. After this, the people are dancing around the Dapo and by the same time the last rites of the deceased is perform and ultimately it is buried. The priest and the people who participated in the attack of Uyub used to sleep by placing their stomach facing the ground for up to five days. They are not enter the house for five days, and are only eat and drink on the ground. Any kinds of preparation including the animals sacrificed in this connection are restricted inside the house rather all preparations are done on the ground itself. It is because they believe that if such preparations are done inside the house, then the evil spirits will enter the same and will cause more miseries in the future.

3. JARBIK-BIGNAM: The Jarbik Bignam^{ix} is a prophecy of ritual through which the prediction is taken place. Here the sacrificed of animals does not take place. It is done through the special objects like Bopa (Head-gear), Alang (Stone), Uriuk (sword), Pate-Heegh (Tiger-teeth), Taab-Dumpo (Snake-head), Kyokam-Kheele (Claw of eagle), Kiidi (Soil) and through Ish (Water) etc. Usually, these objects are nearby the Nyub (Priest) during the ritual. This ritual is generally done to find out the cause of epidemics (diseases), theft cases and illicit relations etc. The Nyub

(Priest) through chanting enquire the matter using the above objects to make a positive signal through its movement in favour of Nyub's enquires. The silence atmosphere prevailed to maintain the secrecy during its night long chanting performance. The Nyub makes an enquiry through Jarbik Bignam chanting are as follows:

Lapang Atu nu,
 yaj yallu ham napey niri?
 Gangtey Atu nu kamju sucho paj bu nu,
 Yaj yallu ham napey niri?
 Hul nyetey nu ngam Nyijak-Nyub jaarj bu nu,
 Yaj yallu ham napey niri?
 Rillo- Pullo damj bu nu,
 Yaj yallu ham napey niri?
 Giir nyetey nu, sangkung mumii nu,
 Yaj yallu ham napey niri?
 Niid Atu nu, kamchang kamte nu, tungji bu nu,
 Yaj yallu ham napey niri?

The Nyub through his chanting enquires the almighty protector, whether he had taken the soul or not. The Nyub also asks the creator of art and architecture the same. The spirits of the forefathers and ancestors are also taken into account in this enquiry. The God of prosperity and development is also asked for the same. The evil spirits of man who met unnatural deaths through accidents are also made enquire. The God of orator and debate is also asked about the soul.

4. SUDUNG-IGNAM: The Sudung-Ignam^x is an extraordinary traditional ordeal way of examination or proving through which the wrong or guilty person is prosecuted in a general gathering. It is done only when there is claim and counter claim between two parties for their innocence. Before going for such examination, it is to be established that the accused is specified by the omen of the chicken liver for his or her involvement in the erroneous act. This ritual practice is takes place in a special place far away from the village or human settlement. The people from both the parties gather and examination of Sudung takes place at the witnesses of everybody. It is peculiar to note that sometime even if a man who has been blamed for wrong act is innocent and yet is involved in some other act wrongdoing, which is equivalent to the mentioned case, he, too will have the same effect during the Sudung examination. Therefore, if a man who has been blamed unreasonably and who is ready to go for such examination must be

free from committing any crime in his lifetime. If alleged person has committed any other such misdeeds, he is allowed to confess before the Nyub (Priest) by means of stick counting known as 'Kyotar Tarha Nam'.

Therefore, the Sudung-Ignam is meant for particular examination for a particular person. It must be well proved through the omen of chicken liver; otherwise, it will be a wrong punishment to an innocent man. In this practice, there are two types of examination. One is the boiling of water maximum boiling point level (100 degree Celsius) in an Udung^{xi}. Then a small stone put inside the Udung and the accused is asked to take it out from the boiling water. So, one has to inserts his/her hand to take out the stone. If the person is innocent, the stone will be taken out without any harm but if he/she is guilty, he/she will never be able to take it out and his/her hand will be badly burnt in the boiling water.

Another way of proving the same is by tying off a long thread to a small Udung. Inside the Udung few gravels of stone and piece of Sangrik-naney (Banyan leave) is put. It is done so that the mouth of Udung does not touch water when it is floating on the water. After this, the Udung (Bamboo-tube) is slowly released to lake or river. The thread is controlled by the left hand with a sword in the right hand by the Nyub. If the person has done wrong, the Udung will be drowned in the water and if he/she is innocent, it will never go under the water. The chanting of hymns is started simultaneously with the preparation of the thread and the Udung for the Sudung examination. Thus, at lasts the proof of the Sudung come into limelight. If the offence is proved, according to the magnitude of the case a heavy fine is imposed. However, in Nyishi society imposing of such fine depends upon the decision of the elders present in the meeting. The financial capacity or position of the concerned family is also taken into account. In most of the cases, the imposition is finalised before taking such extreme step. Sometime if a person is proved wrong, he/she is instantly killed in the spot. Therefore, during such occasion both the party gets ready to protect each other because in such situation anything can be happen. In this way, the process of Sudung-Ignam is complete only within a day with hundred of witnesses from the village.

5. SOTUNG-TUNGNAM (A BLACK-MAGIC): The Sotung^{xii} is a dangerous way of taking revenge between two individuals, families or the clans. Such ritual is done for a particular individual or family to fulfil the desired effect. Thus, Sotung is the most evil traditional practice of taking revenge causing a heavy loss to human lives just for a slight misunderstanding and mistake. While performing Sotung, the Nyub become very awesome as the spirit penetrate into his body for all the miraculous tasks. Sotung-Nyub^{xiii} invites all the different malevolent spirits at a place to convince and pursue them by offering gifts for the evil act of killing a particular man or a clan. It also includes the invitation of the particular Uyubs who are protecting the particular man or clan by the miraculous chanting power of the Nyub. Here, the "Cheney Butey-Radey Uyub", the spirit and protector of that clan is fully convinced to attack their own people whom they are protecting. The Sotung-Nyub will try to offer and sacrifice animals like goat, pig and fowls etc. in favour of Sotung-Uyub so that the evil spirit may take the soul of the concerned man or clan. The people generally sit together only in the Nyodang^{xiv} side of the house but never in the Koda^{xv} side during the Sotung ritual because the door of the house is half-closed. The ritual chanting with rapid walking takes place in the Koda. The Nyub digs a grave for the

concerned living man with the Changlang-Kiidi (Soil for graveyard) in his left hand side and starts chanting and directing the evil spirits to kill the person. The Sotung chanting takes place usually at night in a very secret manner without the knowledge of others. If it is not done for a special Sotung ritual, it takes about 2 to 3 days to complete the process. The Yugang^{xvi} is also constructed at a distance and secret site as per the direction of the Nyub. The Nyub is assisted by the Boo (Assistant Nyub). The Yugang is made of bamboo, dupp, etc. and its structure is approximately 1 metre in length and breadth respectively.

The cause of the Sotung-Tungnam may be due to a conflict involving woman, theft, land dispute and other personal enmities. During such Sotung performance, the Bujo^{xvii} charged by the Sotung-Nyub are as follows:-

1. One string of beads (Sangmi) or Rs. 5000/- to Rs. 10,000/-
2. Letum-Ijee (Clothes) or Rs. 700/- to Rs. 1000/-
3. Uriuk (Sword) or Rs. 500/- to Rs. 1000/-
4. Dumso (Nyalap) or Rs. 500/- to Rs. 1000/-

6. CHANGING PERSPECTIVES

The Nyishi traditional religious beliefs and practices are nowadays changed to many folds as compare to as it was in some decades back. The mass religious conversion of the people to Christianity has contributed a lot in the process. Nowadays the converted people do not performed any kind of rituals related to their tradition/indigenous social and cultural life. They considered that the performance of ritual practices imposes heavy expenditure of animal sacrifice and taboo, etc. which become unbearable for some people, particularly poor section of the people. This forced some people from avoiding the practice of indigenous belief systems and practices and later changes their faith to Christianity. The advanced and rationalised religion like Christianity took all advantages of this divertive force. They interpreted that belief on evil spirits was superstition, practice of animal sacrifice in worship was wastage, and performance of worship in traditional system was the practice of demon/devil. Here they pleaded that there is only one SAVIOUR i.e. Jesus Christ upon whom the people should establish their firm faith and belief. This doctrine of faith attracted the people to Christianity and accordingly many of the people gave up their traditional religious beliefs and ritual practices. In addition to this diversion of religious faith many of those neo-religious people gave up their festival celebration i.e. NYOKUM and secondly they began to challenge customary laws of the society.

However, in contrast to all those adversities, the Nyishi indigenous or religious movements are geared up in many parts of Nyishi areas, though it didn't yet reach many interior places. The Nyishi indigenous religion institution Nyedar-Namlo² is believed to be drawn out of the religious philosophical thought and considered as the highest end of spiritual existence (Showren, 2007). The God is worshipped in the form of a symbolic image of the Ane-Donyi

² Nyishi indigenous religious place (house).

(The Symbolic Sun), which is kept over the raised small platform in the Namlo (house). The devotees came to the Namlo either alone or in a family group, makes his/her offering or then departs. It would see that an underlying philosophy of the Nyedar-Namlo is to emphasise on abut action to preserve the Tani religion and culture with pristine ethos within the Nyishi community. Community also belief that all embodied souls is under the control of three Truths or Observances. They are Ane-Donyi (The Creator), Abo-Tani/Abu-Tain (Inheritor and Preserver) and the Sachang-Ane (Mother-Earth), the Supreme Abode of all human beings after their deaths. Sachang-Ane is a dwelling place for all living creatures including human, animal, and all living organisms.

People's culture still has its roots in the customs and practices of marriage, inheritance and land ownership. Yet with the process of globalisation, a significant shift is taking place in the perception of their culture. The younger generations' view that Christianity as superior has already shaken the foundation of the village society, both culturally and traditionally.

Modernity in the form of Christianity has brought in a new form of culture. People no longer sing traditional songs or traditional dances since they are considered to be primitive and belonging to an uncultured way of life. They have now been replaced with western music and dance in and outside the Churches. Hence a borrowed culture has become the guiding principle of the present younger generation in the village. The people are in danger of losing their own identity as Nyishi people with a distinct culture. Even though the people are in verge of facing a serious identity crisis in course of time due to the influence of Christianity, there still remains the possibility for maintaining their age old cultural identity. There needs to be the rediscovery and the giving of importance to their folk stories, folk songs, folk dances and festivals. That could only be possible when restrictions imposed by the Church leaders on any Church members especially youngsters to attending any ritual performances by the Priests are lifted.

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ENDNOTES

- i It is a name of tree which is believed to be the home of evil spirits who are cause illnesses and ultimately led to death of the people.
- ii It is a store house for preserving the all kinds of agricultural products, which popularly known as granary in English.
- iii It is a kind of prophecy where future predictions are made by examining the chicken liver.
- iv It is form of ritual chanting of an egg to predict the future.
- v It is a specific form of ritual performs by the Nyishis for peacefulness and coldness of mind during any kind of attack or test.
- vi It is a kind of phrase which is related with the warning to the evil spirits.
- vii It is a peculiar kind of sound produced by the people during ritual procession.
- viii It is a kind of pole stand erected on a ground for ritual purpose and on which ritual elements are fixed attached to it.
- ix It is a specific form of ritual through which the cause of diseases, theft cases and illicit relations etc. are find out.
- x It is a kind of ritual where the culprits are identified by asking the person to insert his/her hand inside the boiling water.
- xi It is often term as bamboo-tube where the people use to carry water and for drinks.
- xii It is a kind of black-magic which is use to destroy/devastate the others.
- xiii It is a priest who is expert in such ritual performances.
- xiv It is the back side of the hearth in the Nyishi house.
- xv It is the front side of the hearth in the Nyishi house.
- xvi It is an altar where all kinds' ritual related sacrifices are made.
- xvii It is an amount charged by the priest for her role in the ritual performance.

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KISAN CREDIT CARD SCHEME IN INDIA- ISSUES AND PROGRESS

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural credit is essential for the development of agriculture in India as most of the Indian farmers are marginal farmers and are not able to invest huge amount of money for the betterment of agriculture and thus remain marginal through out their life. In order to solve this problem, NABARD launches Kisan Credit Card Scheme 1998-99 with an objective to provide appropriate amount of credit to the farmers. This study is mainly concerned with the comparative performance evaluation of various bank groups in issuing KCCs and sanctioning credit through these KCCs for the period 2009 to 2011. For this purpose, co-operative banks, regional rural banks and commercial banks are taken for investigation. The study finds that commercial banks are most successful in fulfilling the objectives of NABARD followed by regional rural banks. Co-operative banks are not successful in achieving their objectives and thus are not serving the agriculture, the farmers and the nation.

KEYWORDS: *Kisan Credit Cards, NABARD.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the bread and butter for more than 60% of the people of our country means that more than 60% of our people depend upon agriculture for their livelihood even though contribution of agriculture to our GDP is less than 27%. Nonetheless, the importance of agriculture cannot be underestimated for years to come. Agriculture will continue to be central to all the strategies for socio-economic development of the country. Rapid growth of agriculture

will not only ensure continued food security to the people but also aid in growth in industry and the GDP which are the essential sign for the development of any economy and India is also not an exception in this case.

To sustain the growth in agriculture credit plays a crucial role. In order to address the problems in purveying credit for agriculture, the Reserve Bank of India had set up a one man High Level Committee of Shri R.V. Gupta in December 1997 to suggest measures for improving the delivery systems as well as simplification of procedures for agricultural credit. Against this background the Kisan Credit Card (KCC) scheme was introduced in pursuance to the announcement made by the hon'ble finance minister in his budget speech for the year 1998-99. It sought to address many of the issues concerning short-term credit needs of farmers.

The KCC came into existence in 1998-99 as a credit product that allowed farmers the required financial liquidity and avail credit when it was absolutely needed, providing in the process flexibility, timeliness, cost effectiveness and hassle free services to the farmers.

GENESIS

The Kisan Credit Card is a pioneering credit delivery innovation for providing adequate and timely credit to farmers under single window, with flexible and simplified procedure, adopting whole farm approach, including the short-term, medium term and long term credit needs of the borrowers for agriculture and allied activities and a reasonable component for consumption needs.

SALIENT FEATURES OF THE KISAN CREDIT CARD (KCC) SCHEME

- ❖ Eligible farmers to be provided with a Kisan Credit Card and a pass book or card-cum-pass book.
- ❖ Revolving cash credit facility involving any number of draws and repayments within the limit.
- ❖ Limit to be fixed on the basis of operational land holding, cropping pattern and scale of finance.
- ❖ Entire production credit needs for full year plus ancillary activities related to crop production to be considered while fixing limit.
- ❖ Sub-limits to cover short term, medium term as well as term credit are fixed at the discretion of banks.
- ❖ Card valid for 3 to 5 years subject to annual review. As incentive for good performance, credit limits could be enhanced to take care of increase in costs, change in cropping pattern, etc.
- ❖ Each draws to be repaid within a maximum period of 12 months.

- ❖ Conversion/reschedulement of loans also permissible in case of damage to crops due to natural calamities.
- ❖ Security, margin, rate of interest, etc. as per RBI norms.
- ❖ Operations may be through issuing branch (and also PACS in the case of Cooperative Banks) through other designated branches at the discretion of bank.
- ❖ Withdrawals through slips/cheques accompanied by card and passbook.
- ❖ Crop loans disbursed under KCC Scheme for notified crops are covered under Rashtriya Krishi Bima Yojna (National Crop Insurance Scheme), a crop insurance scheme introduced at the behest of Government of India to protect the interest of the farmer against loss of crop yield caused by natural calamities, pest attacks etc.

ADVANTAGES OF THE KISAN CREDIT CARD SCHEME TO THE FARMERS

- ❖ Access to adequate and timely credit to farmers.
- ❖ Full year's credit requirement of the borrower taken care of.
- ❖ Minimum paper work and simplification of documentation for drawl of funds from the bank.
- ❖ Flexibility to draw cash at any time and buy inputs as per the need of the farmer and also to repay as and when surplus fund is available.
- ❖ Assured availability of credit at any time enabling reduced interest burden for the farmer.
- ❖ Sanction of the facility for 3 years subject to annual review and satisfactory operations and provision for enhancement.
- ❖ Flexibility of drawls from a branch other than the issuing branch at the discretion of the bank.

BENEFITS OF THE SCHEME TO THE BANKS

- ❖ Reduction in work load for branch staff by avoidance of repeat appraisal and processing of loan papers under Kisan Credit Card Scheme.
- ❖ Minimum paper work and simplification of documentation for drawl of funds from the bank.
- ❖ Improvement in recycling of funds and better recovery of loans.
- ❖ Reduction in transaction cost to the banks.

- ❖ Better Banker - Client relationships.

MAJOR STEPS TAKEN BY NABARD

- ❖ Co-op Banks and RRBs were advised to enlarge the scope of the KCC Scheme to cover term loans for agriculture and allied activities, including a reasonable component to meet the consumption needs, besides the existing facility of providing crop loan limit.
- ❖ The coverage of KCC was extended to landless laborers, oral lessees, tenant farmers including defaulters.
- ❖ The concept of KCC has been extended to the borrowers of the long term cooperative structure.
- ❖ A Brochure on KCC Scheme highlighting the salient features, advantages and other relevant information about the Scheme was brought out by Head Office and ROs were asked to circulate the brochure to State govt. departments, Commercial Banks, Cooperative Banks, RRBs and other concerned agencies/officers so as to generate wider awareness about the Scheme.
- ❖ Minimum Floor limit of Rs.5000/- for issue of KCC stands withdrawn.
- ❖ Studies on KCC Scheme have been conducted by NABARD periodically to facilitate feedback on the ground level issues/problems so that changes, where necessary, could be considered.
- ❖ On the lines of instructions of RBI to Commercial Banks, Cooperative Banks and RRBs have been advised that they may, at their discretion, pay interest at a rate based on their perception and other relevant factors on the minimum credit balances in the cash credit accounts under the Kisan Credit Cards of farmers during the period from 10th to the last day of each calendar month.
- ❖ RRBs were advised to initiate innovative publicity campaign in each area of operation in order to cater all eligible farmers under KCC.

SCHEME OF THE PAPER

The plan of research report has been framed under six sections:-

Section-I gives the introduction of the problem taken for study.

Section -II deals with review of related literature.

Section -III objectives, data base, statistical techniques and research methodology.

Section -IV deals with the analysis and interpretation of data.

Section-V deals with conclusions and implications of the study.

Section-VI deals with future areas of research.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Samantara, S. (2010) found a number of encouraging results such as hassle free access to institutional loans through KCC effectively resulted in increasing productivity of paddy crop (13.3 per cent) compared to the corresponding yield of non-KCC holders. However, the whole of the yield increase was partly attributed to the credit access through KCC. The adequate application of comparatively higher doses of inputs like fertilizer, manure, pesticide, labour, irrigation waters, etc. by KCC farmers are contributing factors for improvement of yield level. However, there were quite a number of findings reflecting few areas of concern. The study revealed that 717.51 lakh KCC were issued at the end of March 2009, which constituted around 76.85 per cent of the total operational holdings of the 14 states. The study observed that there was something seriously wrong with the MIS of KCC. The study could detect four types of shortcomings in the MIS on KCC:

(a) More than one family member having the same operational holding have been issued the KCC,

(b) The same person has been issued multiple KCC by various banks,

(c) In certain cases, KCC lapsed after a period of three years, but were still counted as valid ones in the MIS and finally,

(d) In certain cases, KCC were renewed after a period of three years, but such cards were shown to be freshly issued.

- ❖ When these distortions are taken into account and the number of genuine KCC are re-estimated, it was found to be 472.68 lakh, which constituted around 50.63 per cent of the operational holding of the states.
- ❖ Among various states, the maximum coverage of KCCs (ratio of number of cards to operational holdings) was Punjab (77.53%), Haryana (74.21%), Andhra Pradesh (64.39%) and Karnataka (63.07%).
- ❖ Among the major banking institutions, commercial banks, cooperative banks and Regional Rural Banks accounted for about 43.7 per cent and 42.7 per cent and 13.6 per cent of the total number of cards issued respectively.
- ❖ In terms of total loan disbursed to cardholders, the share of commercial banks was 57.5%, followed by 29.5% for cooperative banks and 13% for RRBs.

- ❖ Coverage of marginal farmers and small farmers in the KCCs was in the range of 63-68 % (Coop banks), 58-61 % (RRBs) and 59-64 % (CBs). Share of tenant farmers was very negligible (<1%).

The study suggested that the add on features on KCC could be further improved in terms of extending other loan such as consumption loan, term loan in the ratio of 4:2:1 and evolve the KCC into a truly multipurpose card.

Kamble, B. (2009) in his study provides the following results

- ❖ Kisan credit cards is one of the most innovative, widely accepted, highly appreciated and non-discriminatory banking products.
- ❖ RRBs had issued 4.05 lakh cards and achieving 81.2 per cent of the annual target.
- ❖ Commercial banks and co-operatives target was very high compared to RRBs but these banks achieved 56.0 per cent and 46.1 per cent respectively.
- ❖ While considering state wise performance of RRBs, 12 states performance was excellent and these states achieved the target more than 80 per cent. The states are Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Orissa, Rajasthan, Tripura and Uttar Pradesh.
- ❖ In cooperative banks few states performed well. The states are Bihar, Haryana, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh.
- ❖ Southern states performance of RRBs and Co-operatives in issuing credit cards is very poor except Karnataka state.
- ❖ Commercial banks had issued 35.7 lakhs cards involving sanction of Rs. 9148.4 crores to different categories of farmers. Among the 27 commercial banks, Canara Bank, State Bank of India and Syndicate Bank performance is good and these banks issued more than 3.0 lakh Kisan credit cards.
- ❖ In southern states, Karnataka state performed well in terms of issuing Kisan credit cards.
- ❖ In zone wise performance in terms of coverage of holdings, west zone and south zone performance is excellent.
- ❖ The researcher observed that Kisan credit card within short span of time has established itself as a fairly popular credit among the farming community. It is expected that this would help the farmers in easy and timely access to much desired institutional credit and the KC card has been appreciated and accepted both by the bankers as well as farmers.

3. RESEARCH GAP

Kisan credit card scheme launched by NABARD has proved to be a boon to the poor and small farmers of India who need short term, medium term or long term credit for the fulfillment of their agricultural needs. For the achievement of this purpose, many institutions like Cooperative banks, regional rural banks and commercial banks are trying their level best, so that they can serve the farmers and basically the agriculture which is the backbone of Indian economy. But to know whether this scheme is successful in achieving its objectives or not or whether the farmers and the Indian agriculture is benefitted from this or which credit institution is doing better than others, a comparative study is must. So the researcher is tempted to the above study to analyze the trends and progress of Kisan credit card scheme in India.

4. OBJECTIVES

- i. To study the features of Kisan credit card scheme launched by RRBs, commercial banks and cooperative banks.
- ii. To study agency wise performance of Kisan credit cards.
- iii. To analyze state-wise performance of cooperative banks, Regional rural banks and commercial banks in terms of issuing of KCCs and amount sanctioned through KCCs.

5. DATA BASE

Secondary data had been used in the present study.

- i. Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India, RBI Publications, Mumbai 2009 to 2011.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

For the analysis of data arithmetic mean and percentage statistical techniques were used. Percentage increase was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Current Year}}{\text{Base Year}} \times 100$$

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

A descriptive conclusion research design was used for the present study. A comparative study has been conducted about the performance of various credit institutions during the study period to know up to what extent they are successful in providing appropriate credit facilities to the farmers and in achieving their objectives.

SAMPLE DESIGN

In the present study three types of bank groups has been taken for the study which are providing Kisan Credit Cards to the farmers and these bank groups are as follows:

- i. Co-operative Banks
- ii. Regional Rural Banks
- iii. Commercial Banks

TIME PERIOD

Time period for the present study will be taken from 2009 to 2011.

PARAMETERS OF THE STUDY

In the present study, the analysis and comparison of the performance of various credit institutions is done with reference to the following parameters:

- i. Number of Kisan Credit Card issued during the study period
- ii. Amount Sanctioned through Kisan Credit Cards during the study period.

6. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The major findings of this research and the analysis of data is shown the following tables:

**TABLE 1 SHOWS PERFORMANCE OF CO-OPERATIVE BANKS W.R.T. KCCS ISSUED:
STATE WISE PROGRESS (NUMBER OF CARDS ISSUED IN '000)**

Sr. No.	State/UT	Card Issued			% Growth
		2009	2010	2011	
1.	Andhra Pradesh	3594	3594	4143	0.15
2.	Assam	13	14	14	0.07
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	1	1	1	-
4.	Bihar	796	833	833	0.05
5.	Gujarat	1182	1206	1267	0.07
6.	Goa	4	4	5	0.25
7.	Haryana	1244	1259	1273	0.02
8.	Himachal Pradesh	66	192	203	2.08
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	52	53	53	0.02
10.	Karnataka	1677	1867	1991	0.19
11.	Kerala	1295	1482	1583	0.22
12.	Madhya Pradesh	3118	3389	3701	0.19
13.	Maharashtra	5217	5395	5513	0.06
14.	Meghalaya	10	11	11	0.10
15.	Mizoram	2	2	2	-
16.	Manipur	13	14	14	0.08
17.	Nagaland	2	3	4	1.00
18.	Orissa	3268	3592	3910	0.20
19.	Punjab	892	904	936	0.05
20.	Rajasthan	2851	2960	3410	0.20
21.	Sikkim	3	3	3	-
22.	Tamilnadu	1803	1638	1826	0.01
23.	Tripura	4	4	9	1.25
24.	Uttar Pradesh	6074	6280	6511	0.07
25.	West Bengal	1463	1535	1632	0.12
26.	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	3	4	4	0.33
27.	Chandigarh	-	-	-	-
28.	Daman & Diu(\$)	-	-	-	-
29.	New Delhi	2	2	2	-
30.	D&N Haveli (\$)	-	-	-	-
31.	Lakshadweep(\$)	-	-	-	-
32.	Puducherry	7	7	7	-
33.	Jharkhand	279	279	279	-
34.	Chhattisgarh	912	1046	1224	0.34
35.	Uttarakhand	298	314	335	0.12
Average Percentage Growth Rate					0.23

Source: Report on Trends and Progress of Banking in India: 2009-2011

(\$)- No Co-operative Banks in these states/ UTs

Table 1 shows performance of co-operative banks w.r.t. Kisan Credit Cards issued in different states/UTs during the study period. From the analysis of the table it is clear that co-operative bank's performance is quite well in states like Himachal Pradesh, Tripura and Nagaland, while in other states it is performing below standards. In three UTs namely Daman & Due, D & N Haveli and Lakshadweep, there is no co-operative bank. Overall average percentage growth rate of this bank group in issuing KCC is 0.23pc which is much below than the other bank groups i.e. RRBs and Commercial banks. The table shows less efficiency on the part of this bank group in issuing KCCs.

TABLE 2 SHOWS PERFORMANCE OF REGIONAL RURAL BANKS W.R.T. KCCS ISSUED: STATE WISE PROGRESS (NUMBER OF CARDS ISSUED IN '000)

Sr. No.	State/UT	Card Issued			% Growth
		2009	2010	2011	
1.	Andhra Pradesh	1853	2068	2354	0.27
2.	Assam	123	154	192	0.56
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	3	3	3	-
4.	Bihar	839	1110	1372	0.64
5.	Gujarat	242	248	259	0.07
6.	Goa(\$)	-	-	-	-
7.	Haryana	336	372	408	0.21
8.	Himachal Pradesh	40	55	70	0.75
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	15	24	34	1.27
10.	Karnataka	1097	1255	1411	0.29
11.	Kerala	424	473	494	0.17
12.	Madhya Pradesh	474	575	650	0.37
13.	Maharashtra	276	330	338	0.22
14.	Meghalaya	21	22	22	0.05
15.	Mizoram	9	9	9	-
16.	Manipur	2	2	2	-
17.	Nagaland	1	2	2	0.50
18.	Orissa	597	705	782	0.31
19.	Punjab	119	140	163	0.37
20.	Rajasthan	440	499	581	0.32
21.	Sikkim(\$)	-	-	-	-
22.	Tamilnadu	265	294	321	0.21
23.	Tripura	41	53	66	0.61
24.	Uttar Pradesh	3343	3916	4285	0.28
25.	West Bengal	311	375	531	0.71
26.	Andaman & Nicobar Islands(\$)	-	-	-	-
27.	Chandigarh(\$)	-	-	-	-

28.	Daman & Diu	-	-	-	-
29.	New Delhi(\$)	-	-	-	-
30.	D&N Haveli (\$)	-	-	-	-
31.	Lakshadweep(\$)	-	-	-	-
32.	Puducherry	-	-	-	-
33.	Jharkhand	300	387	438	0.46
34.	Chhattisgarh	256	301	354	0.38
35.	Uttarakhand	45	50	55	0.22
Average Percentage Growth Rate					0.36

Source: Same as Table 1, (\$) - No RRBs in these states/ UTs

Table 2 shows performance of RRBs w.r.t. Kisan Credit Cards issued in different States/UTs during the study period. From the analysis of the table it is clear that Regional rural bank's performance is quite good in states/UTs like J&K, Himachal Pradesh, W.B., Bihar, Assam and Nagaland, while in other states it is performing satisfactory. In states like Meghalaya and Kerala its performance is disappointing and in Mizoram and Manipur, it does not show any growth during the study period in issuing KCCs. In six states/UTs, like Goa, Sikkim, Andaman& Nicobar Islands, Chandigarh, New Delhi, D&N Haveli and Lakshadweep there is no RRB. Overall average percentage growth rate of this bank group in issuing KCC is 0.36pc which is satisfactory.

TABLE 3 SHOWS PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS W.R.T. KISAN CREDIT CARD ISSUED: STATE WISE PROGRESS (NUMBER OF CARDS ISSUED IN 'OOO)

Sr. No.	State/UT	Card Issued			% Growth
		2009	2010	2011	
1.	Andhra Pradesh	8985	9919	10982	0.22
2.	Assam	327	399	478	0.46
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	16	19	21	0.31
4.	Bihar	1493	1862	2167	0.45
5.	Gujarat	1377	1543	1714	0.24
6.	Goa	11	12	13	0.18
7.	Haryana	768	861	959	0.25
8.	Himachal Pradesh	219	256	286	0.31
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	12	15	21	0.75
10.	Karnataka	2266	2543	2914	0.29
11.	Kerala	1405	1512	1691	0.20
12.	Madhya Pradesh	1559	1813	2052	0.32
13.	Maharashtra	2426	2972	3572	0.47
14.	Meghalaya	37	46	50	0.35
15.	Mizoram	12	15	19	0.58
16.	Manipur	25	28	30	0.20
17.	Nagaland	18	23	26	0.44
18.	Orissa	1069	1257	1434	0.34

19.	Punjab	1219	1353	1512	0.24
20.	Rajasthan	1467	1762	2073	0.41
21.	Sikkim	7	8	9	0.29
22.	Tamilnadu	3741	4224	4838	0.29
23.	Tripura	52	64	77	0.48
24.	Uttar Pradesh	6005	6917	7665	0.28
25.	West Bengal	1334	1535	1731	0.30
26.	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	2	3	3	0.50
27.	Chandigarh	3	3	7	1.33
28.	Daman & Diu	2	2	2	-
29.	New Delhi	20	22	24	0.20
30.	D&N Haveli	3	3	3	-
31.	Lakshadweep	1	1	1	-
32.	Puducherry	48	60	69	0.44
33.	Jharkhand	414	503	607	0.47
34.	Chhattisgarh	262	317	359	0.37
35.	Uttarakhand	260	304	351	0.35
Average Percentage Growth Rate					0.38

Source: Same as Table 1

Table 3 shows performance of Commercial Banks w.r.t. Kisan Credit Cards issued in different States/UTs during the study period. From the analysis of the table it is clear that commercial banks are doing quite well on almost all the States/UTs except Daman & Diu, D&N Haveli and Lakshadweep because in these States/UTs, this bank group does not show any improvement as compared to the base year of the study. In States/ UTs like Chandigarh, J&K, Mizoram and Andaman & Nicobar Islands, this bank group performance is very good and in States/UTs like Goa, Kerala, Manipur and New Delhi, it need to work hard in issuing KCC. Overall average percentage growth rate of this bank group is 0.38pc which is more than the other two bank groups' namely co-operative banks and regional rural banks which shows superiority of this bank group over other bank groups in issuing KCCs.

TABLE 4 SHOWING COMPARISON BETWEEN PERFORMANCES OF VARIOUS BANK GROUPS W.R.T. KCCS ISSUED

Sr. No.	Bank Group	Average % Growth Rate	Rank
1.	Co-operative Banks	0.23	3
2.	Regional Rural Banks	0.36	2
3.	Commercial Banks	0.38	1
Overall Average % Growth of All Bank Groups in issuing KCCs		0.323	

Table 4 showing comparison between different bank groups w.r.t. KCCs issued during the study period. From the table it is clear that commercial banks surpass the other two bank groups in issuing of KCCs with an average percentage growth rate of 0.38pc. Regional Rural banks are at 2nd and Co-operative Banks are at 3rd place. Performance of co-operative banks is least as compared to the other two bank groups which shows their inefficiency in issuing KCCs. Overall average percentage growth rate of all the bank groups is 0.323pc which is satisfactory which shows that Indian Banking Industry is doing quite well in serving the most critical occupation of agriculture which is the backbone of Indian economy. But if co-operative banks are more strengthened than before this growth rate could be quite high.

TABLE 5 SHOWS PERFORMANCE OF CO-OPERATIVE BANKS W.R.T. AMOUNT SANCTIONED THROUGH KCCS: STATE WISE PROGRESS (AMOUNT IN CRORES)

Sr. No.	State/UT	Amount Sanctioned			% Growth
		2009	2010	2011	
1.	Andhra Pradesh	67510	6751	7129	0.06
2.	Assam	14.9	18	18	0.21
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	1.5	1	1	-0.5
4.	Bihar	944.8	1008	1008	0.07
5.	Gujarat	18377.6	18457	18846	0.03
6.	Goa	17.8	19	20	0.12
7.	Haryana	7732.1	7833	7924	0.02
8.	Himachal Pradesh	318.1	513	675	1.12
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	72.5	78	79	0.09
10.	Karnataka	6872.9	7197	7737	0.13
11.	Kerala	3470.7	4087	4654	0.34
12.	Madhya Pradesh	13352.2	14262	16976	0.27
13.	Maharashtra	30802.9	32157	33210	0.08
14.	Meghalaya	13.2	15	15	0.14
15.	Mizoram	1.3	1	1	-0.30
16.	Manipur	33.6	34	34	0.01
17.	Nagaland	0.8	2	3	2.75
18.	Orissa	9587.0	10323	10847	0.13
19.	Punjab	6199.5	6370	6683	0.08
20.	Rajasthan	8387.0	8915	10835	0.29
21.	Sikkim	6.3	8	8	0.27
22.	Tamilnadu	5228.9	5481	6215	0.19
23.	Tripura	5.6	6	14	1.50
24.	Uttar Pradesh	5910.0	7578	8002	0.35
25.	West Bengal	5494.9	5782	6118	0.11
26.	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	8.3	10	10	0.20
27.	Chandigarh	-	-	-	-
28.	Daman & Diu(\$)	-	-	-	-

29.	New Delhi	8.8	9	10	0.14
30.	D&N Haveli (\$)	-	-	-	-
31.	Lakshadweep(\$)	-	-	-	-
32.	Puducherry	34.3	34	35	0.02
33.	Jharkhand	544.3	544	544	-0.001
34.	Chhattisgarh	2195.0	2413	2899	0.32
35.	Uttarakhand	600.7	689	763	0.27
Average Percentage Growth Rate					0.27

Source: Same as Table 1

(\$)- No Co-operative Banks in these states/ UTs

Table 5 shows performance of co-operative banks w.r.t. amount sanctioned through Kisan Credit Cards in different states/UTs during the study period. From the analysis of the table it is clear that co-operative bank's performance is not at all satisfactory in sanctioning amount through KCCs. In most of the states/UTs its percentage growth rate from the base period of 2009 is almost negligible and in three states it is negative means the amount sanctioned through KCCs is decreased in these states during the study period which is not a good sign for the future of the farmers of the country. Only in Nagaland, Tripura and Himachal Pradesh this bank group is performing well, but performing well in 3 out of 35 states/UTs can't be considered a good performance. Overall average percentage growth rate of this bank group in all the states/UTs is 0.27pc which is very low.

TABLE 6 SHOWS PERFORMANCE OF REGIONAL RURAL BANKS W.R.T. AMOUNT SANCTIONED THROUGH KCCS: STATE WISE PROGRESS (AMOUNT IN CRORES)

Sr. No.	State/UT	Amount Sanctioned			% Growth
		2009	2010	2011	
1.	Andhra Pradesh	3739.2	4405	5156	0.38
2.	Assam	411.1	513	681	0.66
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	3.4	5	5	0.47
4.	Bihar	2936.0	4067	5494	0.87
5.	Gujarat	2590.2	2644	2744	0.06
6.	Goa(\$)	-	-	-	-
7.	Haryana	2907.5	3363	3853	0.33
8.	Himachal Pradesh	179.0	273	413	1.31
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	122.4	173	231	0.89
10.	Karnataka	5376.6	6135	7132	0.33
11.	Kerala	1475.1	1687	1987	0.35
12.	Madhya Pradesh	2415.5	3041	3759	0.56
13.	Maharashtra	1100.0	1180	1242	0.13
14.	Meghalaya	36.6	40	40	0.09
15.	Mizoram	43.9	56	58	0.32
16.	Manipur	2.7	3	3	0.11

17.	Nagaland	2.9	4	4	0.38
18.	Orissa	1299.5	1523	1732	0.33
19.	Punjab	1293.9	1719	2478	0.92
20.	Rajasthan	3595.6	4735	6721	0.86
21.	Sikkim(\$)	-	-	-	-
22.	Tamilnadu	588.9	675	739	0.25
23.	Tripura	62.5	94	119	0.90
24.	Uttar Pradesh	11167.9	14320	16499	0.48
25.	West Bengal	1357.5	1814	2489	0.83
26.	Andaman & Nicobar Islands(\$)	-	-	-	-
27.	Chandigarh(\$)	-	-	-	-
28.	Daman & Diu	-	-	-	-
29.	New Delhi(\$)	-	-	-	-
30.	D&N Haveli (\$)	-	-	-	-
31.	Lakshadweep(\$)	-	-	-	-
32.	Puducherry	-	-	-	-
33.	Jharkhand	340.5	496	602	0.77
34.	Chhattisgarh	613.4	779	984	0.60
35.	Uttarakhand	170.4	220	266	0.56
Average Percentage Growth Rate					0.53

Source: Same as Table 1

(\$)- No RRBs in these states/ UTs

Table 6 shows performance of regional rural banks w.r.t. amount sanctioned through Kisan Credit Cards in different states/UTs during the study period. From the analysis of the table it is clear that RRBs performance in most of the states/UTs is really remarkable and it is doing really well to serve the farmers with appropriate facility of credit for agriculture. In states/UTs like Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tripura and J&K, it is doing really good work and its percentage growth rate as compared to the base period is really good. In some states/UTs, like Meghalaya, Manipur, Maharashtra and Gujarat its performance is below standards. Overall, its average percentage growth rate is 0.53, which is quite good and satisfactory.

TABLE 7 SHOWS PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS W.R.T. AMOUNT SANCTIONED THROUGH KCCS: STATE WISE PROGRESS (AMOUNT IN CRORES)

Sr. No.	State/UT	Amount Sanctioned			% Growth
		2009	2010	2011	
1.	Andhra Pradesh	27986.6	32880	40436	0.44
2.	Assam	582.0	795	1077	0.85
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	29.1	42	52	0.79
4.	Bihar	6178.0	8181	10046	0.63
5.	Gujarat	20712.0	22622	24462	0.18

6.	Goa	130.4	139	149	0.14
7.	Haryana	7719.2	9319	11194	0.45
8.	Himachal Pradesh	1141.7	1461	1780	0.56
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	76.8	101	151	0.97
10.	Karnataka	13011.3	15476	19554	0.50
11.	Kerala	4885.5	5468	7248	0.48
12.	Madhya Pradesh	12002.2	14906	17213	0.43
13.	Maharashtra	10949.4	13859	17106	0.56
14.	Meghalaya	95.1	120	142	0.49
15.	Mizoram	23.7	34	47	0.98
16.	Manipur	61.3	76	87	0.42
17.	Nagaland	33.4	44	52	0.56
18.	Orissa	3124.6	3804	4569	0.46
19.	Punjab	13511.1	16979	21634	0.60
20.	Rajasthan	16573.5	20647	24917	0.50
21.	Sikkim	22.8	32	43	0.89
22.	Tamilnadu	11776.4	14592	20368	0.73
23.	Tripura	106.2	147	194	0.83
24.	Uttar Pradesh	33075.3	39731	46823	0.42
25.	West Bengal	3964.4	4756	5685	0.43
26.	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	8.0	10	12	0.50
27.	Chandigarh	15.3	20	42	1.75
28.	Daman & Diu	13.9	14	16	0.15
29.	New Delhi	173.0	295	322	0.86
30.	D&N Haveli	28.4	29	34	0.20
31.	Lakshadweep	2.6	3	3	0.15
32.	Puducherry	172.2	232	318	0.85
33.	Jharkhand	1067.8	1555	2070	0.94
34.	Chhattisgarh	1296.6	1718	2060	0.59
35.	Uttarakhand	2433.6	2835	3456	0.42
Average Percentage Growth Rate					0.59

Source: Same as Table 1

Table 7 shows performance of commercial banks w.r.t. amount sanctioned through KCCs in different states/UTS during the study period. From the analysis of the table it is clear that commercial banks are doing remarkable work in serving the farmers with credit facilities and their amount of credit to the farmers is increasing during the different years of the study period. Commercial banks are providing appropriate credit to the farmers in almost all the states/UTs. In states/UTs like Chandigarh, Mizoram, J&K and Jharkhand, its performance is really up to the mark and in other states also its percentage growth as compared to the base year is good. Overall, its average percentage growth rate is 0.59pc which is really good and shows its efficiency and success.

TABLE 8 SHOWING COMPARISON BETWEEN PERFORMANCES OF VARIOUS BANK GROUPS W.R.T. AMOUNT SANCTIONED THROUGH KCCS

Sr. No.	Bank Group	Average % Growth Rate	Rank
1.	Co-operative Banks	0.27	3
2.	Regional Rural Banks	0.53	2
3.	Commercial Banks	0.59	1
Overall Average % Growth of All Bank Groups		0.463	

Table 8 showing comparison between different bank groups w.r.t. amount sanctioned through KCCs during the study period. From the table it is clear that commercial banks surpass the other two bank groups in sanctioning amount through KCCs with an average percentage growth rate of 0.59pc. Regional Rural banks are at 2nd and Co-operative Banks are at 3rd place. Performance of co-operative banks is least as compared to the other two bank groups which show their inefficiency in providing appropriate credit facilities to the farmers. Overall average percentage growth rate of all the bank groups is 0.463pc which is satisfactory which shows the ever increasing efforts on the part of Indian Banks to fulfill the needs of the agricultural credit. But there is need to improve the services of co-operative banks, so that the farmers could be made more benefitted.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- i. As far as the performance of co-operative banks is concerned, it can be concluded that their efforts in fulfilling the demands of credit by the farmers are not at all satisfactory. Neither they are successful in increasing the rate of issuing their KCCs nor in sanctioning the appropriate amount of credit to the farmers. In some states/UTs the amount sanctioned has been decreased during the study period, which is not a good sign for this bank group. Their overall average percentage growth in issuing KCCs and sanctioning the amount is 0.23pc and 0.27pc respectively, which is very low as far as the contribution of credit in the development of agriculture, is concerned. So, if this bank group really wants to serve the farmers, it has to improve its functioning and operations.
- ii. As far as the performance of regional rural banks is concerned, it can be concluded that this bank group is doing quite well on both the aspects of the study i.e. in issuing KCCs and sanctioning appropriate amount of credit to the farmers. Its overall average percentage growth rate in issuing KCCs and in sanctioning the amount through KCCs is 0.36pc and 0.53pc, which is quite good. Its performance is quite close to the performance

of commercial banks which has a strong base and a large branch network. Making itself at par with commercial banks shows the efficiency of this bank group. But this bank group has to work hard in those states/UTs in which its performance is not so good, so that it can really serve the agriculture, the farmers and the nation in true sense.

- iii. As far as the performance of commercial banks is concerned, it can be concluded that this bank group is the pivot of agricultural development in India as it shows maximum growth in issuing KCCs and sanctioning appropriate amount of credit to the farmers in not only one or two states/UTs, but in all the states/UTs. This bank group's overall average percentage growth rate in issuing KCCs and sanctioning amount through KCCs is 0.38pc and 0.59pc respectively, which is much more than the other two bank groups. Commercial banks by their performance shows their supremacy over all the other bank groups and prove the fact that this bank group is the true heartbeat of Indian banking industry. So, this bank group needs to continue its efforts in serving the farmers with appropriate amount of credit, so that our country can become developed.

8. CONCLUSION

India is an agriculture based country and the development of other sectors of the economy also lies on the development of agriculture. But Indian farmers are poor and are not able to invest that much amount in agriculture which is necessary. So, Kisan Credit Card Scheme was launched by NABARD to solve this problem of Indian farmers. Various types of bank groups are issuing KCCs. In this study, after analyzing the relative performance of co-operative banks, regional rural banks and commercial banks in issuing KCCs and in sanctioning credit through these KCCs, it can be concluded that commercial banks and regional rural banks are doing their operations properly and shows maximum percentage growth in the study period on both the aspects, but co-operative banks are far lagging behind their objectives and are slow in their functioning and operations.

IMPLICATIONS

The current study is mainly concerned with the analysis of comparative performance of the specific bank groups during the period of 2009 to 2011 in issuing of KCCs and in sanctioning credit through these KCCs. As the study reflects the bank groups that have improved or declined their performance in respect of all the selected parameters, so provides important analysis to judge the banks with poor performance which further help to make some policy measures to improve their performance. The study will be more beneficial for the RBI & NABARD, for the bankers and policy makers to make some important decisions and to make policy measures to improve their performance. The study will be helpful to the academicians and researchers for further study in this respect.

II. FUTURE AREAS OF RESEARCH

- i. Comparative study of individual banks for all selected parameters

- ii. Performance evaluation of different bank groups w.r.t. of short term, medium term and long term loans.

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NEED, SCOPE AND EVOLUTION OF LABOUR WELFARE – A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The constitution of India guarantees complete freedom and protection to every individual for the fullest realisation of his individual personality. In the present age of technical development the problems of labourers are becoming more and more complex. In the light of this thinking a study of welfare programmes for labourers assumes great significance. The objective of the present study is to spell out the need, objective, evolution and to find out the measures for the effective implementation of various labour welfare schemes.

KEYWORDS: *Labour Welfare, Constitution.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of Indian Constitution is to set-up a welfare state. The distinguishing characteristics of the welfare state is the assumption by the community, acting through the state, of the responsibility for providing the means where by all its members can reach certain minimum standards of health, economic security and civilized living and can share according to their capacity in the social and cultural heritage.

The constitution of India guarantees complete freedom and protection to every individual for the fullest realisation of his individual personality. According to Directive Principles of State Policy as stipulated in the Indian constitution:-

1. The citizen, men and women, equally have the right to an adequate mean of livelihood:

2. The ownership and control of the material resources of the community are distributed so as best to subserve the common good.
3. The operation of the economic system does not result in the concentration of wealth and means of production to common detriment;
4. There is equal pay for men and women;
5. The health and strength of workers, men, women and children of tender age, are not abused and citizens are not forced by economic necessity to enter into avocations avocation unsuited to their age or strength; and
6. Child hood and youth are protected against exploitation and against moral and material abandonment.

In the present age of technical development the problems of labourers are becoming more and more complex. In the light of this thinking a study of welfare programmes for labourers assumes great significance. The objective of the present study is to spell out the need, objective, evolution and to find out the measures for the effective implementation of various labour welfare schemes. As a matter of fact, it is being increasingly realized the world over and in India, that with the advancement of technology and its advent in agricultural, Industrial and related spheres, the problems of working population are becoming increasingly complex. All this has major economic and equally, if not more, importantly, social and political implications.

The present study has been divided into two sections. Section - I deals with the need, objectives and scope of labour welfare, whereas section - II has been devoted to a critical analysis of the Labour welfare schemes.

SECTION- I

I (1) THE NEED OF LABOUR WELFARE

In this part of the study, we begin by discussing the thinking on the need for the labour welfare at the global level, moving to the Asian and National levels. Some of the broad steps taken in this direction at these levels are outlined.

Though only a small part of total population in India are employed in the organised sector, industrial workers today constitute functionally a very significant and vulnerable element, they also constitute a substantial part to the nation's economy. But if we make an over-all survey of the living and working conditions of workers, the need for labour welfare in India would immediately become apparent. These welfare services have become necessary to counteract the handicaps to which workers are exposed, both in their work-life and social life and to provide opportunities and facilities for the harmonious development of the workers' personalities.

In their work life, workers have many a time to work for long hours in unhealthy surroundings. Those who have migrated from rural areas, find themselves engulfed by and lost

in an uncongenial and strange environment. As a result, they fall prey to alcoholism, gambling and other vices, which demoralize and, sometimes, completely dehumanize them.

The higher rate of labour absenteeism in India industries is indicative of the lack of commitment on the part of workers, for they want to escape, whenever possible, from the environment of the work site. This absenteeism can be reduced by the provision of good housing, of health and family care, of canteens where healthy, balanced diet is made available in congenial surroundings.

Good educational and training facilities for workers are also very necessary in Indian industries because of the high rate of illiteracy among them. These facilities would also help in decreasing the number of industrial accidents, in increasing workers' efficiency and then sense of commitment. Other recreational facilities help workers to improve their health and develop their personality and make them feel that the state and employers are interested in their welfare. These also help in reducing the druggery of their work.

Family welfare, child welfare and maternity care facilities help workers in a variety of ways. They reduce infant mortality, improve the health of the spouse and keep the family size at the desirable minimum. They also tend to reduce these workers anxiety and absenteeism in so far as these were due to sickness in the family.

The provision of suitable facilities designed to meet the need of migrant workers can help them settle down more easily in their new working and living conditions. A proper organization and administration of welfare facilities can play a vital role in promoting better working conditions and living standards for industrial workers and also increase their productivity, especially in developing countries. It is obvious, however, that the scope of labour welfare depend on the kind of problems in existence and on the types of welfare which are needed in different situations.

Labour is an indispensable factor of production. Healthy and congenial Labour-management relations are the pre-requisite for efficient production. Labour welfare measures both on and off the job, are very crucial, since they are bearing on the workers' willingness to work and their productive capacity. In a very significant sense, it is the workers who really deliver the goods. Just as machine should be kept in good conditions for smooth operation, the operator too should be maintained in satisfactory physical, emotional mental and moral conditions for unbroken and increasing production. If workers are fed properly clothed adequately and treated kindly, and if the conditions of work are congenial, they will work efficiently. Welfare programmes are the means of securing, preserving and increasing the efficiency of Labourers.

The need and importance of Labour welfare has for long been appreciated through out the civilized world. It is being increasingly felt in the developing countries, like ours. The concept of welfare, however, varies from country to country depending upon social customs, degree of industrialisation and educational development of workers. The international Labour Organisation, in one of its publications, has defined the term 'Labour welfare' as services, facilities and amenities as may be established in, or vicinity of, undertakings with a view to

enabling persons employed therein to perform their work in healthy and congenial surroundings. The term 'welfare' includes:

- I. Feeding facilities;
- II. Rest and recreation facilities and work;
- III. Transportation to and from the work place where ordinary public transport is inadequate and Impracticable.

The National Commission of Labour appointed by the govt. of India in 1966, also observed that the concept of labour welfare is comprehensive and embraces a multiplicity of activities, such as working conditions, educational and recreational facilities, sanitation and health, housing etc. which help in increasing productive capacity of the workers.

The social concept of labour welfare implies the welfare of a man, his family and his country. There are interconnections among these three aspects, in the sense that all three work together as a three dimensional conglomerate, each serving the other two as an end and as means.

Welfare refers to, or signifies, a positive concept in as much as it stipulates the provision of certain minimum necessary and acceptable conditions of existence, biologically and socially. These conditions pertain to the provision and availability of certain minimum quanta of health, food, clothing, housing, medical assistance, insurance, education, recreation, job security, and so on. However, Labour welfare has a negative side too. While on the positive side, it signifies the provision of opportunities which enable the workers and his family to lead a better life socially and personally as well as help him in adjusting to the transition in work life, family life and social life, on the negative side, labour welfare functions with a view to neutralizing the effects large scale industrialization and provides a counter-balance to the undesirable social consequences and the labour problems which have evolved in the process of this transition.

The word 'labour' means any productive activity. Thus, in a broader sense, the phrase labour welfare means the adoption of measures to promote the physical, social, psychological and general well-being of working population. Labour welfare measures in any industry aim or should aim, at improving the working and living conditions of workers and their families.

The concept of labour welfare is, however, flexible and differs from time to time, region to region and country to country, depending upon the value system, level of education, social customs and degree of industrialization and the general standards of socio-economic development of the people.

Further it depends upon the kind of problems with which the society is confronted as well as the structure of the industry. It is moulded to age group, sex, socio-cultural background, marital status, economic status and educational level of employees in the various industries.

Broadly speaking, measures and activities taken by the state, employers and association

of workers for the improvement of workers, standards of living for the promotion of their social and economic well-being are labeled as welfare work. On this account, welfare work may be defined as, "work for improving the health, safety, general well-being and industrial efficiency of workers beyond the minimum standards laid down by the Factories Act and other labour legislations",¹ According to H.S. Kirkaldy, "the whole field of welfare is on in which much can be done to combat the sense of frustration of industrial workers, to relieve them of personal and family worries to improve their health, to afford them a means of self-expression, to offer them some share in which they can excel all others, to help them to widen their conception of life".²

According to Royal Commission on Labour in India, "It is a term which must necessarily be elastic', bearing a somewhat different interpretation in one country from another, according to different social customs, the degree of industrialization and educational development of the workers."³

According to the Encyclopedia of social sciences," the term is used to describe the voluntary efforts of an employer to establish within the existing industrial system, working and, sometimes, living and cultural conditions of his employees beyond what is required by law and customs of industry and the conditions of the market."⁴

I.2 OBJECTIVES OF LABOUR WELFARE

Initially, humanitarianism and social awareness motivated labour welfare activities. More generally, however, it is the desire to get greater efficiency and output from workers, and a motive to attract better workers, that make the employers offer extra-incentives in the form of labour welfare schemes. Such schemes also make it possible for employers to persuade workers to accept mechanisation. Sometimes, labour welfare is used by employers to combat the influence of outside agencies of their employees. Labour welfare measures are often undertaken with a view to avoiding payment of tax on surplus and simultaneously building up better relations with employees. The desire to show off and advertise their concern for labour are also factors which play their part in persuading employers to go in for labour welfare schemes. The bigger the organization the greater the expenditure incurred on such advertisement. Thus the motives that lie behind Labour welfare schemes are often complex, for human nature varies from person to person, certain characteristics, however, dominate in each successive period of the development of labour welfare movement and this is clearly seen in the broad historical perspective of industrial welfare. It often happens that if an organization adopts/introduces certain measures for the purpose, other organisations in the same industry may follow suit and thus in spreading of labour welfare movement in and around that particular industrial area.

¹ Industry and Society - A sociological appraisal of Modern Industrialism, pp - 250-251.

² Kirkaldy, H.S. The spirit of industrial Relations, pp. 77-78.

³ Report of the Royal commission on Labour in India, p. 281.

⁴ Encyclopedia of Social Sciences, Vol. XV, 1935, p. 315

I.3 THE SCOPE OF LABOUR WELFARE

The concept of labour welfare, by its nature "must necessarily be elastic, bearing a somewhat different interpretation in one country from another, according to different social customs degree of industrialization, educational development of workers." The scope of Labour welfare has to be elastic and flexible enough to suit the existing conditions of workers, and to include all the essential pre-requisites of life, and minimum basic amenities, our constitution, in its Directive Principles of State policy, refers generally to "the promotion of the people." In its specific applications to the working class, the necessity of, "securing just and human conditions of work" for them has been highlighted; but what these conditions actually imply cannot be specified in rigid terms for all times.

According to labour Investigation Committee, welfare work may be considered to include anything done for intellectual, physical and moral betterment of workers whether by employers, by government or by other agencies, over and above what is laid down by the law and what is normally expected as a part of contractual benefits for which the workers may have bargained. Thus, under this definition, we may include housing, medical and educational facilities, nutrition including provision of canteens, facilities for rest and recreation, co-operative societies, day nurseries and reaches provision of sanitary accommodation, holiday with pay, social insurance measures undertaken voluntarily by employees alone or jointly with workers including sickness and maternity benefits schemes, provident funds, gratuities and pensions, etc. The term welfare is thus very flexible as well as comprehensive.

The scope of labour welfare is fairly wide and is not specific to anyone country, one region, or one occupation or one industry.

The scope of labour welfare has been described by different authors differently. The line of demarcation can not be very precise, but we can say that in the final analysis, labour welfare services should:

1. "enable the workers to live a richer and more satisfactory life, contribute to the productivity of labour and efficiency of enterprises;
2. Raise the standards of living of workers by indirectly reducing the burden on their purse;
3. Be in tune and harmony with similar services obtaining in a neighbouring community where an enterprise is situated;
4. Be based on intelligent prediction of future needs in industrial work, and be so designed as to offer a cushion to absorb the shock of industrialization on workers; and

5. Be administratively viable and essentially developmental in out-look."⁵

The scope of labour welfare cannot be limited, however, the facilities with in or near the undertakings. Nor can it be so comprehensive as to, "embrace the whole range of social welfare activities or social services. It follows, therefore, that all extra- mutual and inter-mutual activities as well as statutory and non- statutory welfare measures undertaken by employees, government, tradeunions or voluntary organizations fall with in the scope of labour welfare. Thus it encompasses activities and amenities related to canteens, rest and recreation facilities, medical assistance, travel to and from work place, education, housing facilities and so on. It can also include social security measures which contribute to workers' welfare such as industrial health, insurance, provident fund, gratuity, maternity benefits, compensation, pension, retirement benefits, etc" which are the species of the larger family encompassed by the term "Labour welfare".

SECTION- II

EVOLUTION OF LABOUR WELFARE

Worker's welfare as a movement begin in early years in the western countries. Considerable in impetus was given to movement by the two world wars, as part of industry's effort to maximize production. Thus modern welfare may be said to have been the outcome of the movement for better and more efficient management in industries including the human angle. The all round acceptance of the concept of labour welfare was mainly due to:⁶

1. The need to provide a better life for the workers was dictated by the necessity to maintain the goodwill of the large and rather freshly requested war time labour force and to gear them to increase production:
2. The industrial expansion in the advanced countries of the world and the concomitant process of mass production and mass selling led to the emergence of the working classes as source of power. Steps to promote labour welfare were a direct recognition of the new situation.
3. There was also influence of the researches into scientific management and industrial psychology, which presented abundant evidence on importance of worker as human being and a total personality.
4. It has been a matter of public and government concern, especially in economically less developed countries for the amelioration of working living conditions of industrial workers and measures in this regard were being taken in many countries as an aspect of national policy.

In the conclusion we can say that the concept and percent of labour welfare as there are

⁵ Labour investigation Committee, Main Report, 1946, p. 345

⁶ I.L.O. Recent Developmetns in certain Aspects of Indian Economy , Vol. Iv, 1959, p.86.

prevalent and accepted in present time have been proceeded by the gradual evolution in different directions in different countries.

II.1 REPORT OF THE SURVEY TEAM ON LABOUR WELFARE

A survey team was appointed in December, 1859 at the instance of Labour minister with the purpose of recommending labour welfare schemes for the third five years plan, It was composed of the senior officers of the Labour ministry.

The committees observation were only based on the material already available with the office of the government. The committee sought to divide the Labour welfare facilities into tow categories as follows:-

1. Those that may be provided with in an undertaking, and
2. Those to be provided outside the undertakings.

Such faculties be provide either by the government, the employers, the workers' organistaion or welfare agencies such as welfare fund etc. Facilities inside the undertaking according to the committee were:-

1. Working conditions;
2. Health and sanitary arrangements;
3. Permeation of fatigue;
4. Washing facilities;
5. Canteens;
6. Creches;
7. Transport to and from the place of work;
8. Fair price shops, postal facilities and savings.

The committee recommended the followings-

1. Strict enforcement of the factories Act,. Mining and plantation Labour Act;
2. Training course in first aid;
3. Supply of cheap nutrition's food packets;
4. Improvement in the standards of crèches in factories;

5. Expansion of fair price shops;
6. Setting up a labour welfare fund by the state government at Bombay;
7. A system of in-plant training;
8. Health homes;
9. Travel concessions etc.

The committee did not think it possible to extend the benefits of social security to all the workers, but felt that the provident fund could be amalgamated into a pension scheme in due course of time.

II.2 LABOUR WELFARE WORK IN INDIA

The need of labour welfare, as stated earlier, is important because it creates a healthy atmosphere in the work place keeps the labour force stable and contented, helps in maintaining industrial peace, thereby by improving production efficiency of workers. It is in recognition of this need that the successive five year plans in India have envisaged additional welfare measures both at the centre and the state levels, for all the workers engaged in the various sectors of the economy.

In India, schemes of Labour welfare were introduced for the first time during the second world war in ordinance, ammunition and other factories engaged in war production, mainly to keep up the morale of workers and to increase productivity with the achievement of independence and emergence of the country as a republic wedded to the ideal of welfare state and socialistic pattern of society, efforts in this direction were intensified.

A discernible feature of government policy in this regard has been to bring matters connected with workers' welfare more and more within the purview of legislation setting appropriate standards. The Factories Act, 1948, the plantation labour Act, 1951 and The Mines Act, 1952, are basic enactments which contain elaborate provisions for safeguarding the health and safety of workers inside the working place and for eventuating their welfare. All those acts lay down the minimum standards for ensuring health and welfare of workers. The Employers are free to improve these minimum standards. Penal provision in these acts cannot be taken recourse to by the competent authorities in the event of contravention or lapses on the part of the employers. Besides these statutory provisions, the central government has constituted labour welfare funds for operation in certain mining activities like coal, mica, iron ore and lime stone and mines, these funds regulate welfare of workers employed in different mines. Separate welfare funds have also been formed for specified services - post & telegraph, parts, dockyards, railways etc. Some of the states also have enacted their own welfare legislation, e.g. ; The Asian Tea Plantation employees welfare Funds, 1959; The Bombay Labour welfare Fund, 1953, etc.

The provision of social security measures in the form of Provident fund, gratuity and pension under the various laws, and the industrial housing schemes undertaken by the central

government are meant to, and they do, promote welfare of the working class.

II. 3 WELFARE WORK BY EMPLOYERS

Many of the welfare facilities like canteens, pithead baths in mines have now been made statutory obligations. With the introduction of Employees State Insurance Schemes, medical aid is no more the responsibility of employers, their associations provide facilities for welfare of labour.

In the kolar gold mines, one main hospital with 240 beds, a dispensary, well equipped maternity clinic continued to function for the benefit of workers and their families. Under the Plantation Labour Act, 1951, the managements are provide certain welfare amenities like drinking water, conservancy, medical aid, housing, education and recreation facilities, etc. to plantation workers,. The Railways have a huge welfare organizations with a very wide range of activities.

II. 4 WELFARE WORK BY WORKERS ORGNISATIONS

A few workers' organizations are also engaged in welfare work for industrial employees. The most important among them is the Textile Labour Association, Ahmedabad, The Association spends a large' portion of its income on the social and educational upliftment of workers. The Association maintains a number of social and cultural centers for promotion of activities like literacy, group talks, adult education, seminars on important topics, imparting training to women in handicrafts like sewing, embroidery etc. A few nursery schools were maintained by the Association.

These were a large number of consumers co- operative stores, co- operative credit societies and housing societies for the working class. The Association maintained a workers co- operative Bank from where workers could get loans repayable in easy installments.

In this study, we have attempted to spell out in some details the various meaning and interrelations that have been put on the concept of Labour welfare , We have also tried to show how the concept evolved over time in different countries, regions and industries. The most noticeable features have been the flexibility and comprehensiveness of the idea and scope of labour welfare. It has been modified and moulded to suit the various time - specific and place-specific conditions. However, the core, the primary focus, has all the time and every where been the amelioration of the working and living conditions of the workers. Labour welfare has always and everywhere signified the ensuring of satisfactory and healthy working millieu for the workers, The actual context of the policy, the legislations, the measures implemented for the purpose has of necessity, varied from time to time and from region to region, to cope with, what we have termed above, the time- specific and place- specific constraints.

In final conclusion, we can sum up by saying while the government means well, but mere good intentions are not enough. It must also effectively implement the various programmes of Labour welfare already in existence and must make quantities and qualitative improvements and additions, A gramme measures is better- than a tonne of unimplemented proposals, however,

well- meaning the letter might be. This is as true of the policy and performance in the context of labour welfare as in most others.

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A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MORBIDITY PATTERN OF ICDS AND NON ICDS CHILDREN OF KATHUA DISTRICT, JAMMU, J&K

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out to compare the morbidity pattern of ICDS and Non-ICDS children in the age group of 0-3 years in Kathua district of J&K state. Multistage sampling technique and lottery method was used for sample selection. Observation, recall method for mothers, anganwadi records and interview with anganwadi workers were used for data collection. Significant difference was noted in the height of ICDS and Non-ICDS children. ICDS children were found to taller on an average as compared to the Non ICDS children. However, there was insignificant difference in the weight of children of the two groups. There was insignificant difference in the morbidity pattern of ICDS and Non-ICDS children during the last 4 weeks. However, there was significant difference in the two group's morbidity pattern in the last 6 months-1year. Commonly encountered illnesses/diseases were fever, cold -cough and diarrhea. More ICDS children (40%) remained disease free as compared to Non-ICDS children (25%). Major causes of illness/disease were seasonal variations and infections.

KEYWORDS: *Morbidity, ICDS Scheme, Non ICDS children.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the ever moving swirl of environmental and social change, there is now a millennial morbidity. The causes of poor physical and mental health are multi focal. The very process of rapid and continual change renders its own effects even on children. Hence, the health status of children under five is a major concern in developing countries. Most deaths among people under 50 years of age occur in the first 5 years of life. The health profile of a child has lasting effects

on adult health status also. Infants and young children are highly susceptible to infections and diseases. In fact, WHO estimates that acute infections account for more than 4 million death among children below 5 years of age (WHO , 2006).

The average Indian child has a poor start to life. Both infant and under-five morbidity for Indian children- at 67 and 93 respectively – are higher than the developing country average. One in four newborns is underweight. Only about one in three is exclusively breastfed for the first six months. Nearly one in two children less than five years of age suffers from moderate or severe malnutrition. One in three children does not get a full course of DPT immunization, and only one in three has the opportunity to be in an early learning program. Just about one in five is protected against vitamin A deficiency (Gupta, 1997).

ICDS scheme is India's attempt to deliver a package of services for children up to 6 years of age and pregnant and lactating mothers in a coordinated manner. ICDS program has components for de-worming, iron supplementation for children and home visits to improve childcare practices. Through its supplementary nutrition module it attempts to reduce the incidence of malnutrition among the country's poor children. Apart from this other services are also included to provide the young child opportunities for survival and optimal growth.

With this as background the present study is carried out with the following objectives:

- 1) Assess the morbidity pattern of children in the age group of 0-3 years in term of:
 - a) Prevalence/incidence.
 - b) Nature
 - c) Causes of various illness among children.

- 2) Compare morbidity pattern of ICDS and Non-ICDS children.

2. METHODOLOGY

I) SAMPLE: GROUP I: The core sample for the study comprised of 80 children in age group 0-3 years. Half of the sample children were enrolled at AWC's and rest were not enrolled at any preschool centers.

GROUP II: Mothers of children enrolled at AWC's formed this group.

II) SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: The sample was drawn by multistage random sampling procedure. Kathua is divided in 17 wards, out of these ward no.3 and 4 were selected by lottery method. From two selected areas 4 anganwadi's were selected randomly, 2 from each ward and then 10 children from each Anganwadi were selected randomly. A total of 40 ICDS children were hence covered for this study. A comparative group of 40 Non- ICDS children matched for SES, locality and age were also selected purposively.

III) TOOLS USED INCLUDED

A) OBSERVATION: Observations were carried out both on ICDS & Non- ICDS children to see the apparent signs in them like otitis media, polio mellitus, fever, allergy, cold, respiratory problem etc.

B) RECALL METHOD FOR MOTHERS: Recall method was used to know the type of diseases/ illness in the child in last 4 weeks, in last 6 months- 1 year and further identify the causes of illness/ diseases.

IV) DATA ANALYSIS

For the present study qualitative analysis was done After analyzing the results, the data was systematically coded and tabulated according to exhaustive categories. Statistically procedures such as chi-square (χ^2) were also used wherever applicable.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The results of study are presented as under:

1. AGE OF CHILDREN

TABLE 1
AGE OF CHILDREN

Age	ICDS		Non-ICDS		Overall total N	percentage
	N	%	N	%		
0-6 months	1	2.5	1	2.5	2	2.5
7months-1year	8	20	6	15	14	17.5
1year1month-1 ½	5	12.5	7	17.5	12	15
1year6months- 2year.	9	22.5	6	15	15	18.75
2year1month-2½year	10	25	12	30	22	27.5
2year6month-3year.	7	17.5	8	20	15	18.75
Total	40	100	40	100	80	100
Mean	2.507		3.6		2.09	

Table 1 reveals that majority (27.5%) of children both from ICDS & Non-ICDS fell in age group 2years 1month-2½years. The mean age of Non-ICDS children (mean=3.62) was slightly higher as compared to ICDS children (mean=2.50).

2. HEIGHT OF CHILDREN

TABLE 2
HEIGHT OF CHILDREN

Height (In feet)	ICDS		Non-ICDS		Overall total	Percentage
	N	%	N	%		
1½-2	4	(10)	8	(20)	12	(15)
2'1"-2'5"	7	(17.5)	19	(47.5)	26	(32.5)
2'6"-3'0"	15	(37.5)	11	(27.5)	26	(32.5)
3'1"-3'5"	13	(32.5)	2	(5)	15	(18.75)
3'6"-4'0"	1	(2.5)	-	-	1	(1.25)
Total	40	(100)	40	(100)	80	100
Mean	2.79		2.37		2.58	

Calculated $\chi^2=16.5$; * $\alpha=0.05$; $df=4$; Table value =9.49. *Significant difference

Table 2 reveals that majority (32.5% each) of children overall had the height of 2'1"-2'5" feet and 2'6"-3'0. Category wise it can be noted that most non ICDS children (47.5%) had a height of 2'1"-2'5" feet while most ICDS children (37.5%) had a height of 2'6"-3 feet. The mean height of ICDS children (mean=2.79) was higher as compared to Non-ICDS children (mean=2.37). Statically significant differences were observed in the height of children of both ICDS and Non-ICDS children, as ICDS children were taller as compared to Non-ICDS children. Bhandari et al (2004) had also noted that ICDS children are less likely to be underweight and undernourished.

3. WEIGHT OF CHILDREN

TABLE 3
WEIGHT OF CHILDREN

Weight (in kg)	ICDS		Non-ICDS		Overall	Percentage
	N	%	N	%		
5-6	2	5	3	7.5	5	6.25
6 ⁺ -7	7	17.5	5	12.5	12	15
7 ⁺ -8	6	15	10	25	16	20
8 ⁺ -9	6	15	6	15	12	15
9 ⁺ -10	5	12.5	6	15	11	13.75
10 ⁺ -11	3	7.5	5	12.5	8	10
11 ⁺ -12	7	17.5	3	7.5	10	12.5
12 ⁺ -13	2	5	1	2.5	3	3.75
13 ⁺ -14	2	5	1	2.5	3	3.75
14 ⁺ -15	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	40	100	40	100	80	100
Mean	9.1		8.62		8.86	

Calculated $\chi^2=4.37$; $\alpha=0.05$; $df=8$; Table value =15.5. Insignificant difference

Table 3 reveals that majority (20%) of children overall had the weight of 7⁺- 8kgs. Category wise, most ICDS children, (17.5% each) had a weight of 6⁺- 7kgs or 11⁺ -12kgs. As far as, Non-ICDS Children were concerned (25%) had a weight of 7kgs- 8kgs. Statistically no significant difference was noted in the weight of ICDS and Non-ICDS children. Calculation of mean values however, reveals that ICDS children (mean=9.1) on an average had more weight as compared to Non ICDS children (mean=8.625).

4. MORBIDITY PROFILE OF CHILDREN

Direct observations were carried out to note the apparent signs of illness in ICDS and Non-ICDS children. Majority of children had the problem of fever, cold and allergy at that time. Some had problem of otitis media, some had problem of diarrhoea and rest of them did not show any illness. However on the whole, at the time of observation 40% of the overall children were disease free. More ICDS children (15) were disease/ illness free as compared to Non-ICDS children (10). Also, data gathered from the mothers through recall method to indicate the nature, frequency and causes of illness/diseases encountered by their children.

4.1 ILLNESS PATTERN OF PAST 4 WEEKS

TABLE 4

ILLNESS PATTERN OF PAST 4WEEKS

Diseases	ICDS		Non ICDS		Overall total	Percentage
	N	(%)	N	(%)		
Measles	-	-	2	(5)	2	(5)
Fever	9	(22.5)	5	(12.5)	14	(17.5)
Combination- Measles & Fever	-	-	1	(2.5)	1	(1.25)
Cold cough	2	5	3	(7.5)	5	(6.25)
Fever-cold Cough	3	(7.5)	4	(10)	7	(8.75)
Otitis media	2	(5)	2	(5)	4	(5)
Otitis media +fever	-	-	-	-	-	-
Diarrhoea	-	-	-	-	-	-
Jaundice	3	(7.5)	4	(10)	7	(8.75)
Combination of Jaundice & Diarrhoea	1	(2.5)	1	(2.5)	2	(2.5)
Allergy	-	-	-	-	-	-

	2	(5)	3	(7.5)	5	(6.25)
Chest –infection	2	(5)	2	(5)	4	(5)
Combination of Chest- infection and allergy	-	-	1	(2.5)	1	(1.25)
Injury						
Anemia	-	-	2	(5)	2	(2.5)
No illness	-	-	-	-	-	-
	16	(40)	10	(25)	26	(32.5)
Total	40	100	40	100	80	100

Calculated= χ^2 =9.2 ; α =0.05 ;df=12 ;Table value=21.0, Insignificant difference

Table 4 reveals that as reported by the mothers majority (32.5%) of the overall sample children, had no illness in last 4 weeks. Category wise 40% of ICDS children as compared to 25% non-ICDS had no illness/diseases during the given period. Fever, cold and cough and diarrhoea were the common illnesses for ICDS children. While, besides these ailments allergies and measles were also commonly found in Non-ICDS children. Statistically no significant difference was observed between the illness pattern in last 4 weeks of ICDS and Non-ICDS children.

4.2 ILLNESS PATTERN OF PAST SIX MONTHS - ONE YEAR

Table 5 reveals that majority (20%) ICDS children had fever, 12.5% had anemia, 15% had problem of otitis media and 12.5% had no illness in the last 6 months to 1 year. In case of Non-ICDS group, most children had (22.5%) fever, jaundice (22.5%), chest infection (15%) and rest measles (10%). Significant differences were observed in the illness/disease pattern of past 6 months- 1 year of ICDS and Non-ICDS children. Though measles, fever and injuries were common for both the groups. However, ear infections (otitis media), allergy and anemia were more common among ICDS children. On the other hand, jaundice, chest infection and diarrhoea were more common among Non-ICDS children. Also, more Non-ICDS children (25%) had no illness as compared to ICDS children (12.5%).

TABLE 5

ILLNESS PATTERN OF PAST 6 MONTHS- 1 YEAR

Diseases	ICDS		Non ICDS		Overall total	Percentage
	N	(%)	N	(%)		
Measles	6	(15)	4	(10)	10	(12.5)
Fever	8	(20)	7	(22.5)	15	(18.75)
Combination- Measles & Fever	-	-	1	(2.5)	1	(1.25)
Cold cough	1	(2.5)	-	-	1	(1.25)
Fever-cold Cough	1	(2.5)	2	(5)	3	(3.75)
Otitis media	6	(15)	-	-	6	(7.5)
Otitis media +fever	-	-	-	-	-	-
Diarrhoea	2	(5)	1	(12.5)	3	(3.75)
Jaundice	2	(5)	6	(22.5)	8	10
Combination of Jaundice & Diarrhoea	-	-	-	-	-	-
Allergy	1	(2.5)	-	-	1	(1.25)
Chest –infection	2	(5)	6	(15)	8	(10)
Combination of Chest- infection and allergy	-	-	1	(2.5)	1	(1.25)
Injury						
Anemia	1	(2.5)	2	(5)	3	(3.75)
No illness	5	(12.5)	-	-	5	(6.25)
	5	(12.5)	10	(25)	15	(18.75)
Total	40	100	40	100	80	100

Calculated $\chi^2 = 31.87^*$; $\alpha = 0.05$;df=14 ;Table value=23.7.* Significant difference

4.3 CAUSES OF ILLNESS/ DISEASES

Table 6 reveals that majority of the (38.5%) children fell ill due to change of season. In both the categories it was mainly due to change in season (35% ICDS & 42.5% non-ICDS). Especially as the winter approached more children fell ill. Infections (30% ICDS & 20% Non-ICDS) and worm infestation and dust (7.5% ICDS & 10% Non-ICDS) were other common cause of illness. Siayed and Seshadri (1998) had also noted similar causative factors for illness among young children. No significant difference was observed in the causes of illnesses/disease of both ICDS and Non-ICDS children.

TABLE 6
CAUSES OF ILLNESS/DISEASES

Causes	ICDS		Non ICDS		Overall total	Percentage
	N	(%)	N	(%)		
Infection	12	(30)	8	(20)	20	(25)
Seasonal variation	14	(35)	17	(42.5)	31	(38.75)
Worm-infestation and dust	3	(7.5)	4	(10)	7	(8.75)
Birth problem	6	(15)	2	(5)	8	(10)
Change in milk & weaning food	2	(5)	5	(12.5)	7	(8.75)
Other Reasons	3	(7.5)	4	(10)	7	(8.75)
Total	40	100	40	100	80	100

Calculated $\chi^2 = 4.64$; $\alpha = 0.05$; $df=5$; Table value=11.1, Insignificant difference

4.4 FREQUENCY OF ILLNESS DURING PAST 4 WEEKS**TABLE 7****FREQUENCY OF ILLNESS DURING PAST 4 WEEKS**

Frequency	ICDS		Non ICDS		Overall Total	Percentage
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Once in 4 weeks	8	20	9	22.5	17	21.25
twice in 4 weeks	12	30	16	40	28	35
thrice in 4 weeks	4	10	5	12.5	9	11.25
Nil	16	40	10	25	26	32.5
Total	40	100	40	100	80	100

Calculated $\chi^2=2.08$; $\alpha=0.05$; $df=3$; Table value =7.81;Insignificant difference .

Table 7 reveals that majority (40%) ICDS children were healthy, (20 %) were ill once in 4 weeks; 30 % were ill twice in the 4 weeks and 10% were ill thrice in 4 weeks. As far as Non-ICDS children were concerned majority (40%) were ill twice in the period; 25% were healthy; 22.5% were ill once in 4 weeks and rest (12.5%) were ill thrice in 4 weeks. Calculation of χ^2 also reveals significant difference in frequency of illnesses of ICDS and Non-ICDS children. Overall ICDS children had lesser frequency of falling ill in last 4 weeks as compared to Non ICDS children.

4.5 IMMUNIZATION OF CHILDREN

TABLE 8
IMMUNIZATION SCHEDULE

Vaccines	ICDS		NON ICDS	
	N=40	Percentage	N=40	Percentage
D.P.T	36	90	35	87.5
Polio	37	92.5	35	87.5
B.C.G	40	100	40	100
Measles	33	82.5	39	97.5

Calculated $\chi^2=0.568$; $df=3$, $x=0.558$, table value =7.81. Insignificant difference.

Table 8 reveals that all ICDS and Non-ICDS children received B.C.G vaccination; 90% ICDS children and 87.5% Non-ICDS children received D.P.T; 92.5% ICDS children and 87.5% Non- ICDS children receive polio drops ; 82.5% ICDS children and 97.5% non-ICDS children received measles vaccines. The remaining children both from ICDS and Non- ICDS didn't received the D.P.T, polio and measles vaccination. No significant difference was observed in the immunization pattern of children belonging to ICDS and Non-ICDS group. Gupta and Walia (2001) had also noted that the immunization coverage is higher in areas where the ICDS scheme is functional.

5. SUMMARY

Children are the first call on agenda of human resource development not only because young children are the most vulnerable, but because the foundation for life long learning and human development is laid in these crucial early years. ICDS today represents one of the world's largest programmes for early childhood development. It is an intersectoral programme which seeks to directly reach out to children below 6 years especially from vulnerable and remote areas and give them a head start by providing an integrated programme of early childhood health and nutrition.

The results reveal that the ICDS children are taller than their Non ICDS counterparts, highlighting that the services received that the ICDS centers may be useful for the physical growth of these children. Though statistically no significant differences were found in the weight of the sample children yet, still the ICDS children were again found to be heavier than the other group children.

Analysis of the health record of the sample children further, reveals that more ICDS children were disease/illness free than the Non ICDS children. Though both the groups

encountered similar infections and diseases but again the incidence was lower for the ICDS group. This could probably be attributed to some supplementary nutrition received at ICDS centers along with other services available. The Non ICDS children were probably at a disadvantage of not being able to avail the services provided at such centers.

Overall, the findings of the study acknowledge the role of ICDS scheme in providing a better survival and development chance to the children especially those from the disadvantaged sections of the society. Even though there can be many intervening factors responsible for the health and wellbeing of children, yet the role of the scheme cannot be discounted. There is an urgent need to make the ICDS scheme a potent tool for addressing the various health issues of young children.

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HANDLOOM INDUSTRY ON THE WAY OF DISTRESS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OVER THE MAJOR PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

Handloom industry is the way of life for many more millions of people in India. Having a glorious past this industry's present is questionable and blurry future due to a lot of problems that are acting behind the scene. The main objective of this paper is to identify the various problems of handloom industry. For this purpose open ended questionnaire regarding major problems is used. The analysis is based on primary data sources as well as secondary data. Based on fieldwork and secondary data, this paper examines that Handloom industry is facing three major problems viz... Shortage of raw materials, lack of proper financing and marketing insufficiency of the finished products as well as competition with other sectors.

KEYWORDS: *Handloom Industry, Problems, Raw Material, Marketing, Finance.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Indian handloom industry plays a pivotal role for large employment potential next only to agriculture. This industry is a part of the culture and ethos of India and its glorious past. It has emotional bondage with nationalism and the champions of nationhood. creation of huge employment is best-suited under indian conditions, where capital is scarce and technology imports are not affordable by the nation; hence, the handloom sectors are also best suited to achieve planned objectives of "self-sufficiency" The industry is an age old source of livelihood for millions people in the country. Around 4.3 million people¹ are directly depending on the

¹ Handloom census of India 2009-10, NCAER, New Delhi.

industry to eke-out their livelihood while many more millions of people are depending upon the subsidiary occupation connected with the handloom industry. Despite having a glorious past this industry's present is questionable and blurry future due to a lot of problems that are acting behind the scene. This study attempts to identify those problems through response of selected sample units as well as secondary sources.

2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To identify the various problems of handloom industry faced by sample units and offer suggestions for solving such problems.

3 METHODOLOGY

The present study has been conducted in Varanasi city of Uttar Pradesh State because of major centre of handloom industry. This study is empirical in nature. The empirical data have been collected for analyzing major problems of handloom industry by conducting a market survey on handloom garments by using a schedule. The secondary data are also used to analyze major problems regarding Uttar Pradesh scenario. For this study 206 samples were collected through simple random sampling method and entire samples were segregated into 5 (five) stratum: Weavers (50), Master Weavers (50), Wholesalers (50), Retailers (50) and Government Showroom (6) (Because there are only four Government shops in Varanasi and two were selected from Head Office of Kanpur). Data collection technique was personal interview by using open ended questionnaire regarding major problems of handloom industry. For data analysis Stata 10 software was used.

4 ANALYSIS OF RESULT AND FINDINGS

4.1 PROBLEMS OF HANDLOOM INDUSTRY

This study tries to explore in to the operational problems of handloom industry. The problems that are being faced by the industry can be generally classified into three viz., Shortage of raw material, lack of proper financing and marketing insufficiency of the finished products. These factors play a crucial role in the survival of handloom industry.

4.2 PROBLEMS REGARDING RAW MATERIALS

Handloom industry is subject to many problems. Being an ancient industry, handloom could claim some technological advancement or refreshment. Again having counterpart in mechanised production, it is suffering from input constraints. Thus the study of input constraints and technological changes is important. A number of researches have been carried out on the input problems and technological advancement of handloom industry. A study of cotton handloom industry in Orissa by P.C. Mahapatra (1986)² shows that:

² Economics of Cotton Handloom Industry in Orissa – Ph.D. Thesis 1995, University of Bombay.

1. The yarn is the main problem to the weavers.
2. The weavers have a fascination towards their indigenous technique of production.
3. There is no commercial viability of handloom industry in long run.

Hence he suggested a few measures, which are follows:

1. Implementation of Shivraman Committee Report as to the control of yarn.
2. Absorption or adoption of new technology to increase productivity; and
3. Gradual conversion of handlooms into powerloom.

Yarn the basic raw material for the handloom sector is supplied by spinning mills and composite textile mills in the form of 'free yarn'. Handlooms use yarn picked in straight hand form³. The fact finding committee, also clearly indicated that the cost of raw material, namely that of yarn, varies from 50 to 80 percent of the total cost of production, depending upon the time of fabric to be woven⁴. It is therefore, clear that the availability of yarn of the required quality at a reasonable price, is a primary and necessary condition for the success of this industry.

The main raw materials for weavers are dyed yarn and hank yarn. A small proportion of households buy dyes and chemicals. They are of the kind that is into the use of special shades of coloured yarn for more expensive fabrics which are not easily available in the market. Most of the raw materials are sourced from the open market. However, in the case of 15 per cent to 20 per cent of weaver households, the master weaver is the source of dyed yarn, dyes and chemicals, as many of the colours and design elements are controlled at this level. Besides, these are not often openly available in the market⁵. This study tries to explore problems through major-sources distribution of households that procure hank yarn and Dyes and chemicals. These problems are discussed with Uttar Pradesh scenario.

TABLE 1 COMPARISON OF MAJOR SOURCES OF HANK YARN IN THE SECOND AND THIRD HANDLOOM CENSUS

Second Census (1995-96)		Third Census (2009-10)		Increase/Decrease
Source of Hank Yarn	Share (%)	Source of Hank Yarn	Share (%)	
Open Market	62.38	Open Market	74.63	▲

³ Report of High Power Study Team on the problems of the Handloom Industry, 1974, p.27.

⁴ Report of the fact-finding Committee (Handloom and Prices), Calcutta, Government of India, 1942, p.87.

⁵ Third National Census of handloom Weavers and allied workers, 2009-2010. Development commissioner (Handloom), Ministry of Textile GOI, NCAER.

Master Weaver	9.30	Master Weaver	19.89	
Co-operative Societies	9.45	Co-operative Societies	0.49	▼
NHDC/SHDC	6.22	NHDC/SHDC	0.06	▼
Others	12.65	Others	4.93	▼

Source: Second and Third Handloom Census Report, NCAER, New Delhi

An analysis of Table 1 represents that the open market is the major source of raw materials for handloom households. A major problem faced by handloom weavers is the fluctuation in the price of hank yarn. A greater role is to be played by organisations such as National Handloom Development Corporation (NHDC), State level Handloom Development Corporation (SHDC), Apex handloom societies and other organisations down to the level of handloom societies in villages, which could ensure supply of hand yarn and other inputs of handloom weavers at reasonable and stable prices. From the above Table, in 1995-96 the share of about 62 percent open market as against NHDC/SHDC about 6 percent and Co-operative societies' about 10 percent. However, the share of open market and Master Weaver jumped to over 75 percent and about 20 percent respectively in the third handloom census while the share of NHDC/SHDC and Co-operative Societies has reduced to 0.06 percent and 0.49 percent respectively. This analysis represents that procure Hank yarn problems are increasing due to increasing share of open market as well as share of Master Weaver. This trend can be easily understood by Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 CHANGE IN PROCURE OF HANK YARN**TABLE 1 COMPARISION OF MAJOR SOURCES OF DYES AND CHEMICALS IN THE SECOND AND THIRD HANDLOOM CENSUS**

Second Census (1995-96)		Third Census (2009-10)		Increase/Decrease
Source of Dyes and Chemicals	Share (%)	Source of Dyes and Chemicals	Share (%)	
Open Market	74.37	Open Market	89.83	▲
Master Weaver	0.61	Master Weaver	7.15	▲
Co-operative Societies	4.05	Co-operative Societies	0.6	▼
NHDC/SHDC	0.95	NHDC/SHDC	0.09	▼
Others	20.02	Others	2.33	▼

Source: Second and Third Handloom Census Report, NCAER, New Delhi

Table 2 reveals that the share of NHDC/SHDC and Co-operative societies has been decreasing significantly from 0.95 to 0.09 and from 4.05 to 0.6 respectively during the last 15 years. On the other hand the share of open market and Master Weaver has been increased during the last 15

years. Thus the result shows that there are procure Dyes and chemical problems are also increasing due to nil roles of NHDC/SHDC as well as Co-operative societies. These changes can be seen by Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 CHANGE IN PROCURE OF HANK YARN

The successive Textile policies of the Government of India are favourable to large scale sector. The Indian growing cotton is exported foreign countries, with cheaper rates and synthetic yarn is imported by paying higher prices. A percentage of yarn goes to powerlooms and other handloom related industries. As a result the industry is facing the problem of shortage in the supply of hank yarn required. the price of yarn is shooting up every year but sales of the handloom products are declined. It is necessary to know about the price of hank yarn in every year which indicates the scarcity of the yarn and the hike in the cost of the raw material. The problem of the supply of yarn is not new. It is in fact, a chronic one.

4.2.1 ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEMS REGARDING RAW MATERIAL – FINDINGS FROM THE SURVEY

TABLE 3

S. No.	Problems	Weavers	Master Weavers	Retailers	Wholesalers	Govt. Showroom	Total
1	Scarcity of Yarn inputs	13 (40.63)	25 (50.00)	10 (33.33)	16 (32.00)	3 (50.00)	67 (41.19)
2	Quality is not good	2 (45)	4 (8.00)	5 (16.67)	8 (16.00)	2 (33.33)	21 (16.05)
3	Wide fluctuation in inputs price	13 (40.63)	15 (30.00)	12 (40.00)	18 (36.00)	1 (16.67)	59 (32.66)
4	Chemicals & Dyes	3 (9.38)	4 (8.00)	3 (10.00)	7 (14.00)	0 (00.00)	17 (8.27)
5	Other if any	1 (3.13)	2 (4.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.00)	0 (00.00)	4 (1.83)
Total		32 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	6 (100.00)	168 (100.00)

Source: Field Survey (Out of 50 (Weaver) respondents, 18 respondents are rental weaver as well as co-operative societies member).

Table 3 reveals that out of 168 respondents about 41.19% of the respondents expressed their problems regarding scarcity of yarn input followed by 32.66% of the respondents expressed their concern regarding wide fluctuation of input price, about 16.05% of the respondents expressed their problem that they are not provided with qualitative raw material and about 8.27% of the respondents expressed their problem regarding chemicals and dyes whereas rest of the 1.83% of the respondents expressed that they are facing other problems like high price of looms, not available in time and poor quantity etc.

An analysis of the Table 3 represent that out of 32 respondents of weavers about 40.63% weavers expressed their problems regarding scarcity of yarn inputs as well as wide fluctuation in inputs price. About 9.38% weavers are expressed that they are facing problem of chemical and dyes whereas 45 % weavers are facing problems of inferior quality of raw material. Rest of the 3.13% weavers expressed that they are facing other problems like they do not get qualitative raw materials at right time and right price. It is also evident from the Table That out of 50 respondents (Master weavers), about 50% master weavers expressed their problems regarding

scarcity of yarn input followed by 30% master weavers expressed their problems regarding wide fluctuation input price, about 8% master weavers expressed that they are facing problem of dyes and chemicals as well as Inferior quality of raw materials and rest of the 4% master weavers are facing other problems.

Table 3 reveals that out of 50 respondents of retailers 20 respondents (40%) are not given any expression about raw materials problems. Out of 30 respondents about 40% retailers expressed their problem regarding wide fluctuation input price followed by 33.33% retailers expressed their problems regarding scarcity of yarn input, about 16.67% retailers expressed their problem regarding inferior quality and rest of 10% retailers are facing problem of dyes and chemical related. It is proof from the Table that out of 50 respondents (Wholesalers), about 36% wholesalers expressed their problem regarding wide fluctuation input price followed by 32% wholesalers expressed their problems regarding scarcity of yarn input, about 16% wholesalers expressed their problem regarding inferior quality, about 14% wholesalers expressed that they are facing chemicals and dyes related problems and rest of the 2% wholesalers are facing others problems. This table also reveals that out of 6 respondents (Govt. Showrooms), about 50% respondents expressed their problems regarding scarcity of yarn input followed by 33.33% respondents expressed that they are not getting qualitative raw materials and rest of the 16.67% respondents expressed their problem regarding wide fluctuation of input price.

4.3 MARKETING PROBLEMS

Production is possible with man, machine and material, but its viability or economic relevance exist only if it is profitably marketed. Thus marketing is the ultimatum. Unless there exist a market, there will be no venture. Indian handloom products were famous in home, as well as over the world till 19th century. Though most of the markets were captured by 'Mill-made' products and synthetic fibres, still Indian cotton products have the same prestige in the world market.

4.3.1 FINDINGS FROM THE SURVEY

TABLE 4 PROBLEMS RELATING TO MARKETING

S.No.	Problems	Weavers	Master Weavers	Retailers	Wholesalers	Govt. Showroom	Total
1	Seasonal Demand	9 (28.13)	10 (20.00)	6 (12.00)	8 (16.00)	1 (16.67)	34 (18.56)
2	Highly competitive market	3 (9.38)	27 (54.00)	39 (78.00)	28 (56.00)	4 (66.67)	101 (52.81)
3	High Transport cost	2 (45)	6 (12.00)	4 (8.00)	4 (8.00)	1 (16.67)	17 (10.18)
4	Delayed Payments	16 (50.00)	5 (10.00)	0 (00.00)	7 (14.00)	0 (00.00)	28 (14.80)
5	Other if any	2 (45)	2 (4.00)	1 (2.00)	3 (6.00)	0 (00.00)	8 (3.65)
Total		32 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	6 (100.00)	188 (100.00)

Source: Field Survey (Out of 50 (Weaver) respondents, 18 respondents are rental weaver as well as co-operative societies member)

Table 4 reveals that out of 188 respondents about 52.81% of the respondents expressed their problems regarding highly competitive market followed by 18.56% of the respondents expressed their concern regarding seasonal demand, about 14.80% of the respondents expressed their problem that they are facing problem of delayed payment and about 10.18% of the respondents expressed their problem regarding high transport cost whereas rest of the 3.65% of the respondents expressed that they are facing other problems like unskilled labour, high wage rate and marketing place problems etc.

An analysis of the Table 4 reveals that out of 32 respondents (Weavers) about 50% of the weavers expressed their problems regarding delayed payments followed by 28.13% weavers expressed their concern regarding seasonal demand, about 9.38% weavers expressed their problem that they are facing problem of delayed payment and about 45% weavers expressed their problem regarding high transport cost. Rest of the 45% weavers expressed that they are facing other problems. It is evident from the Table that out of 50 respondents (Master weavers), about 54% master weavers expressed their problems regarding highly competitive market, about 20% master weavers expressed their problems regarding seasonal demand followed by 12% master weavers expressed that they are facing problem of high transport cost and 10% master

weavers expressed their problems regarding delayed payments. Rest of the 4% master weavers are facing other problems.

Table 4 also reveals that out of 50 respondents (Retailers), about 78% retailers expressed their problems regarding competitive market, about 12% retailers are facing problem of seasonal demand followed by 8% retailers expressed their problem regarding high transport cost rest of the 2% retailers said that they face other problems. It is proof from the Table that out of 50 respondents (Wholesalers), 56% wholesalers said that they face competition with mill-made product as well as powerloom product. About 16% wholesalers expressed their problem regarding seasonal demand followed by 14% wholesalers expressed their concern regarding delayed payment and about 8% wholesalers face the problem regarding high transportation cost, rest of the 6% wholesalers expressed that they are facing other problems.

It is evident from Table that out of 6 respondents (Govt. Showroom), about 66.67% respondents expressed their problem regarding competitive market followed by 16.67% respondents expressed that they are facing problem of seasonal demand and rest of the 16.66% respondents expressed their problem regarding high transport cost.

4.4 FINANCIAL PROBLEMS

Finance constitutes an important factor of production. It is the livelihood of any industry. It is only through financial resources the industries can think of buying the needed inputs in their quantity of stock raw materials for use in production process at least for a period of three months. For this, industrialists need a sound financial background. Frankly speaking, the study of problems of any industry remains incomplete without the study of financial problems.

SOURCES OF FINANCE: sources of Finance are gradually expanding. Basically there are two types of sources.

- a. Institutional Sources: Commercial banks, regional bank, co-operative bank and the government.
- b. Non-Institutional Sources: Mahajan, Gaddidar, Money lender, Friends and Relatives.

In recent time financial institutional sources are expanding despite most of the weavers depend on the non-institutional sources like Mahajan, Gaddidar, Money lenders, Friends and relatives. They afraid for using financial institutional sources.

4.4.1 FINDING FROM THE SURVEY

TABLE 5 PROBLEMS RELATING TO FINANCE

S.No.	Problems	Weavers	Master Weavers	Retailers	Wholesalers	Govt. Showroom	Total
1	Security to be furnished	13 (26.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	13 (5.20)
2	High rate of interest	11 (22.00)	44 (88.00)	50 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	6 (100.00)	161 (82.00)
3	Influence required	6 (12.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	6 (2.40)
4	Too many formalities	17 (34.00)	6 (12.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	23 (9.20)
5	Other if any	3 (6.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (1.20)
Total		50 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	50 (100.00)	6 (100.00)	206 (100.00)

Source: Field Survey

Table 5 reveals that out of 206 respondents about 82% of the respondents expressed their problems regarding high rate of interest of banks followed by 9.2% of the respondents expressed their concern regarding too many formalities, about 5.20% of the respondents expressed their problem regarding security to be furnished and about 2.40% of the respondents expressed their problem regarding influence required whereas rest of the 1.20 % of the respondents expressed that they are facing other problems.

An analysis of the Table 5 reveals that handloom industry faces the problem of getting institutional finance. It is evident from the Table that out of 50 respondents about 34% weavers expressed that they are facing problem of too many formalities. Because most of the weavers are illiterate and they do not prepare for completing those formalities. They get financial support without completing any formalities to the non-institutional sources. About 26% weavers are expressed that they are facing problem of security to be furnished. The reason behind this they do not believe easily due to lack of knowledge, lack of communication gap etc. Because most of the weavers are passed their whole life within the weaving boundary. About 22% weavers are expressed their problem regarding to higher rate of interest of financing from the banks and other government institutions. About 12% weavers are expressed that they are facing problem of influence required. Rest of the 6% weavers are facing other problems like, bank agent, insecurity and time management. Out of 50 respondents about 88% master weavers expressed their

problems regarding to higher rate of interest. Whereas 12% master weavers are expressed that they are facing the problem of too many formalities. Rest of the other respondents like Retailers, Wholesalers and Govt. showrooms, they expressed their problems regarding to higher rate of interest from the banks.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS REGARDING PROBLEMS

It may be concluded that the Handloom Industry is a problematic industry and the producers are facing many problems in procurement of raw material. It is clear from above analysis that Handloom Industry in recent years is facing many problems regarding marketing as well as financial like marketers suffer from high competition of powerloom and other categories products. There is a great need to improve the marketing facilities of the handloom products.

6 REMEDIAL MEASURES

After analyzing all major and associated findings, we recommend the following steps which will provide a direction for further improvement of this sector.

- To solve the raw material problems the government should have a monitoring under Handloom Board of Uttar Pradesh to monitor activities of those wholesalers and retailers who are engaged in selling raw materials which will ensure with reasonable price.
- To improve the raw material facilities the government should allocate and adequate spend resources to the weavers welfare programmes.
- The Government should open more branches in States and give rebate on the Handloom cloth and improve the Handloom markets.
- For enhancing marketing of Handloom Garments, Government should afford promotional programme like trade fairs, public relations, sales promotion and advertising etc.
- The Government should follow price stabilization scheme like minimum support price regarding raw materials of handloom sectors'.

7 CONCLUSION

All recommendations are to boost up the sales and market share of handloom industry in Uttar Pradesh. Handloom marketers are facing a lot of problems that have been highlighted through above analysis and made necessary recommendations to bring the handloom industry at the blooming stage of development. We should extend our helping hand to the government and NGOs to pave the way of development for Handloom Industry.

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ABOVE THE CLOUDS: A VIEW OF CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Cloud Computing, the long-held dream of computing as a utility, has the potential to transform a large part of the IT industry, making software even more attractive as a service and shaping the way IT hardware is designed and purchased. Developers with innovative ideas for new Internet services no longer require the large capital outlays in hardware to deploy their service or the human expense to operate it. They need not be concerned about over provisioning for a service whose popularity does not meet their predictions, thus wasting costly resources, or under provisioning for one that becomes wildly popular, thus missing potential customers and revenue. Moreover, companies with large batch-oriented tasks can get results as quickly as their programs can scale, since using 1000 servers for one hour costs no more than using one server for 1000 hours. This elasticity of resources, without paying a premium for large scale, is unprecedented in the history of IT.

Cloud Computing refers to both the applications delivered as services over the Internet and the hardware and systems software in the datacenters that provide those services. The services themselves have long been referred to as Software as a Service (SaaS). The datacenter hardware and software is what we will call a Cloud. When a Cloud is made available in a pay-as-you-go manner to the general public, we call it a Public Cloud; the service being sold is Utility Computing. We use the term Private Cloud to refer to internal datacenters of a business or other organization, not made available to the general public. Thus, Cloud Computing is the sum of SaaS and Utility Computing, but does not include Private Clouds. People can be users or providers of SaaS, or users or providers of Utility Computing. We focus on SaaS Providers (Cloud Users) and Cloud Providers, which have received less attention than SaaS Users. From a hardware point of view, three aspects are new in Cloud Computing.

1. *The illusion of infinite computing resources available on demand, thereby eliminating the need for Cloud Computing users to plan far ahead for provisioning.*
2. *The elimination of an up-front commitment by Cloud users, thereby allowing companies to start small and increase hardware resources only when there is an increase in their needs.*
3. *The ability to pay for use of computing resources on a short-term basis as needed (e.g., processors by the hour and storage by the day) and release them as needed, thereby rewarding conservation by letting machines and storage go when they are no longer useful.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud Computing is a new term for a long-held dream of computing as a utility, which has recently emerged as a commercial reality. Cloud Computing is likely to have the same impact on software that foundries have had on the

TABLE 1: QUICK PREVIEW OF TOP 05 OBSTACLES TO AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR GROWTH OF CLOUD COMPUTING

	Obstacle	Opportunity
1	Availability of Service	Use Multiple Cloud Providers; Use Elasticity to Prevent DDOS
2	Availability of Service	Standardize APIs; Compatible SW to enable Surge Computing
3	Data Confidentiality and Audit ability	Deploy Encryption, VLANs, Firewalls; Geographical Data Storage
4	Scalable Storage	Invent Scalable Store
5	Bugs in Large Distributed Systems	Invent Debugger that relies on Distributed VMs

hardware industry. At one time, leading hardware companies required a captive semiconductor fabrication facility, and companies had to be large enough to afford to build and operate it economically. However, processing equipment doubled in price every technology generation. A semiconductor fabrication line costs over \$3B today, so only a handful of major “merchant” companies with very high chip volumes, such as Intel and Samsung, can still justify owning and operating their own fabrication lines. This motivated the rise of semiconductor foundries that build chips for others, such as Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company (TSMC). Foundries enable “fab-less” semiconductor chip companies whose value is in innovative chip design: A company such as nVidia can now be successful in the chip business without the capital, operational expenses, and risks associated with owning a state-of-the-art fabrication line. Conversely, companies with fabrication lines can time-multiplex their use among the products of many fab-less companies, to lower the risk of not having enough successful products to amortize operational costs. Similarly, the advantages of the economy of scale and statistical multiplexing may ultimately lead to a handful of Cloud Computing providers who can amortize the cost of their large datacenters over the products of many “datacenter-less” companies. Cloud Computing has been talked about, blogged about written about and been featured in the title of workshops, conferences, and even magazines. Nevertheless, confusion remains about exactly what it is and when it’s useful, causing Oracle’s CEO to vent his frustration:

Our goal in this paper to clarify terms, provide simple formulas to quantify comparisons between of cloud and conventional Computing, and identify the top technical and non-technical obstacles and opportunities of Cloud Computing. Our view is shaped in part by working since 2005 in the UC Berkeley RAD Lab and in part as users of Amazon Web Services since January 2008 in conducting our research and our teaching. The RAD Lab’s research agenda is to invent technology that leverages machine learning to help automate the operation of datacenters for scalable Internet services. We spent six months brainstorming about Cloud Computing, leading to this paper that tries to answer the following questions:

What is Cloud Computing, and how is it different from previous paradigm shifts such as Software as a Service (SaaS)? • Why is Cloud Computing poised to take off now, whereas previous attempts have foundered?

- What does it take to become a Cloud Computing provider, and why would a company consider becoming one?
- What new opportunities are either enabled by or potential drivers of Cloud Computing?
- How might we classify current Cloud Computing offerings across a spectrum, and how do the technical and business challenges differ depending on where in the spectrum a particular offering lies?
- What, if any, are the new economic models enabled by Cloud Computing, and how can a service operator decide whether to move to the cloud or stay in a private datacenter?
- What are the top 5 obstacles to the success of Cloud Computing—and the corresponding top 5 opportunities available for overcoming the obstacles?

- What changes should be made to the design of future applications software, infrastructure software, and hardware to match the needs and opportunities of Cloud Computing?

2 WHAT IS CLOUD COMPUTING?

Cloud Computing refers to both the applications delivered as services over the Internet and the hardware and systems software in the datacenters that provide those services. The services themselves have long been referred to as Software as a Service (SaaS), so we use that term. The datacenter hardware and software is what we will call a Cloud.

When a Cloud is made available in a pay-as-you-go manner to the public, we call it a Public Cloud; the service being sold is Utility Computing. Current examples of public Utility Computing include Amazon Web Services, Google AppEngine, and Microsoft Azure. We use the term Private Cloud to refer to internal datacenters of a business or other organization that are not made available to the public. Thus, Cloud Computing is the sum of SaaS and Utility Computing, but does not normally include Private Clouds. We'll generally use Cloud Computing, replacing it with one of the other terms only when clarity demands it. Figure 1 shows the roles of the people as users or providers of these layers of Cloud Computing, and we'll use those terms to help make our arguments clear.

The advantages of SaaS to both end users and service providers are well understood. Service providers enjoy greatly simplified software installation and maintenance and centralized control over versioning; end users can access the service “anytime, anywhere”, share data and collaborate more easily, and keep their data stored safely in the infrastructure. Cloud Computing does not change these arguments, but it does give more application providers the choice of deploying their product as SaaS without provisioning a datacenter: just as the emergence of semiconductor foundries gave chip companies the opportunity to design and sell chips without owning a fab, Cloud Computing allows deploying SaaS—and scaling on demand—without building or provisioning a datacenter. Analogously to how SaaS allows the user to offload some problems to the SaaS provider, the SaaS provider can now offload some of his problems to the Cloud Computing provider. From now on, we will focus on issues related to the potential SaaS Provider (Cloud User) and to the Cloud Providers, which have received less attention.

We will eschew terminology such as “X as a service (XaaS)”; values of X we have seen in print include Infrastructure, Hardware, and Platform, but we were unable to agree even among ourselves what the precise differences among them might be.¹ (We are using Endnotes instead of footnotes. Go to page 20 at the end of paper to read the notes, which have more details.) Instead, we present a simple classification of Utility Computing services in Section 5 that focuses on the tradeoffs among programmer convenience, flexibility, and portability, from both the cloud provider's and the cloud user's point of view

From a hardware point of view, three aspects are new in Cloud Computing:

1. The illusion of infinite computing resources available on demand, thereby eliminating the need for Cloud Computing users to plan far ahead for provisioning;

2. The elimination of an up-front commitment by Cloud users, thereby allowing companies to start small and increase hardware resources only when there is an increase in their needs; and
3. The ability to pay for use of computing resources on a short-term basis as needed (e.g., processors by the hour and storage by the day) and release them as needed, thereby rewarding conservation by letting machines and storage go when they are no longer useful.

FIGURE 1: USERS AND PROVIDERS OF CLOUD COMPUTING

The benefits of SaaS to both SaaS users and SaaS providers are well documented, so we focus on Cloud Computing effects on Cloud Providers and SaaS Providers/Cloud users. The top level can be recursive, in that SaaS providers can also be a SaaS users. For example, a mash up provider of rental maps might be a user of the Craigslist and Google maps services.

We will argue that all three are important to the technical and economic changes made possible by Cloud Computing. Indeed, past efforts at utility computing failed, and we note that in each case one or two of these three critical characteristics were missing. For example, Intel Computing Services in 2000-2001 required negotiating a contract and longer-term use than per hour.

As a successful example, Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) from Amazon Web Services (AWS) sells 1.0-GHz x86 ISA “slices” for 10 cents per hour, and a new “slice”, or instance, can be

added in 2 to 5 minutes. Amazon's Scalable Storage Service (S3) charges \$0.12 to \$0.15 per gigabyte-month, with additional bandwidth charges of \$0.10 to \$0.15 per gigabyte to move data in to and out of AWS over the Internet. Amazon's bet is that by statistically multiplexing multiple instances onto a single physical box, that box can be simultaneously rented to many customers who will not in general interfere with each others' usage.

While the attraction to Cloud Computing users (SaaS providers) is clear, who would become a Cloud computing provider, and why? To begin with, realizing the economies of scale afforded by statistical multiplexing and bulk purchasing requires the construction of extremely large datacenters.

Building, provisioning, and launching such a facility is a hundred-million-dollar undertaking. However, because of the phenomenal growth of Web services through the early 2000's, many large Internet companies, including Amazon, eBay, Google, Microsoft and others, were already doing so. Equally important, these companies also had to develop scalable software infrastructure (such as Map Reduce, the Google File System, Big Table, and Dynamo and the operational expertise to armor their datacenters against potential physical and electronic attacks.

Therefore, a necessary but not sufficient condition for a company to become a Cloud Computing provider is that it must have existing investments not only in very large datacenters, but also in large-scale software infrastructure and operational expertise required to run them. Given these conditions, a variety of factors might influence these companies to become Cloud Computing providers:

1. MAKE A LOT OF MONEY. Although 10 cents per server-hour seems low, Table 2 summarizes James Hamilton's estimates that very large datacenters (tens of thousands of computers) can purchase hardware, network bandwidth, and power for 1=5 to 1=7 the prices offered to a medium-sized (hundreds or thousands of computers) datacenter. Further, the fixed costs of software development and deployment can be amortized over many more machines. Others estimate the price advantage as a factor of 3 to 5. Thus, a sufficiently large company could leverage these economies of scale to offer a service well below the costs of a medium-sized company and still make a tidy profit.

2. LEVERAGE EXISTING INVESTMENT. Adding Cloud Computing services on top of existing infrastructure provides a new revenue stream at (ideally) low incremental cost, helping to amortize the large investments of datacenters. Indeed, according to Werner Vogels, Amazon's CTO, many Amazon Web Services technologies were initially developed for Amazon's internal operations.

3. DEFEND A FRANCHISE. As conventional server and enterprise applications embrace Cloud Computing, vendors with an established franchise in those applications would be motivated to provide a cloud option of their own. For example, Microsoft Azure provides an immediate path for migrating existing customers of Microsoft enterprise applications to a cloud environment.

TABLE 2: ECONOMIES OF SCALE IN 2006 FOR MEDIUM-SIZED DATACENTER (_1000 SERVERS) VS. VERY LARGE DATACENTER (_50,000 SERVERS).

Technology	Cost in Medium-sized DC	Cost in Very Large DC	Ratio
Network	95 per Mbit/sec/month	13 per Mbit/sec/month	7.1
Storage	2.20 per GByte / month	0.40 per GByte / month	5.7
Administration	140 Servers / Administrator	>1000 Servers / Administrator	7.1

TABLE 3: PRICE OF KILOWATT-HOURS OF ELECTRICITY BY REGION

Price per KWH	Where	Possible Reasons Why
3.6¢	Idaho	Hydroelectric power; not sent long distance
10.0¢	California	Electricity transmitted long distance over the grid; limited transmission lines in Bay Area; no coal fired electricity allowed in California.
18.0¢	Hawaii	Must ship fuel to generate electricity

4. ATTACK AN INCUMBENT. A company with the requisite datacenter and software resources might want to establish a beachhead in this space before a single “800 pound gorilla” emerges. Google AppEngine provides an alternative path to cloud deployment whose appeal lies in its automation of many of the scalability and load balancing features that developers might otherwise have to build for themselves.

5. LEVERAGE CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS. IT service organizations such as IBM Global Services have extensive customer relationships through their service offerings. Providing a branded Cloud Computing offering gives those customers an anxiety-free migration path that preserves both parties' investments in the customer relationship.

6. BECOME A PLATFORM. Facebook's initiative to enable plug-in applications is a great fit for cloud computing, as we will see, and indeed one infrastructure provider for Facebook plug-in applications is Joyent, a cloud provider. Yet Facebook's motivation was to make their social-networking application a new development platform.

Several Cloud Computing (and conventional computing) datacenters are being built in seemingly surprising locations, such as Quincy, Washington (Google, Microsoft, Yahoo!, and others) and San Antonio, Texas (Microsoft, US National Security Agency, others). The motivation behind choosing these locales is that the costs for electricity, cooling, labor, property purchase costs, and taxes are geographically variable, and of these costs, electricity and cooling alone can account for a third of the costs of the datacenter. Table 3 shows the cost of electricity in different locales. Physics tells us it's easier to ship photons than electrons; that is, it's cheaper to ship data over fiber optic cables than to ship electricity over high-voltage transmission lines.

3 .CLOUDS IN A PERFECT STORM: WHY NOW, NOT THEN?

Although we argue that the construction and operation of extremely large scale commodity-computer datacenters was the key necessary enabler of Cloud Computing, additional technology trends and new business models also played a key role in making it a reality this time around. Once Cloud Computing was "off the ground," new application opportunities and usage models were discovered that would not have made sense previously.

3.1 NEW TECHNOLOGY TRENDS AND BUSINESS MODELS

Accompanying the emergence of Web 2.0 was a shift from "high-touch, high-margin, high-commitment" provisioning of service "low-touch, low-margin, low-commitment" self-service. For example, in Web 1.0, accepting credit card payments from strangers required a contractual arrangement with a payment processing service such as VeriSign or Authorize.net; the arrangement was part of a larger business relationship, making it onerous for an individual or a very small business to accept credit cards online. With the emergence of PayPal, however, any individual can accept credit card payments with no contract, no long-term commitment, and only modest pay-as-you-go transaction fees. The level of "touch" (customer support and relationship management) provided by these services is minimal to nonexistent, but the fact that the services are now within reach of individuals seems to make this less important. Similarly, individuals' Web pages can now use Google AdSense to realize revenue from ads, rather than setting up a relationship with an ad placement company, such Double Click (now acquired by Google). Those ads can provide the business model for Web 2.0 apps as well. Individuals can distribute Web content using Amazon Cloud Front rather than establishing a relationship with a content distribution network such as Akamai.

Amazon Web Services capitalized on this insight in 2006 by providing pay-as-you-go computing with no contract: all customers need is a credit card. A second innovation was selling hardware-level virtual machines cycles, allowing customers to choose their own software stack without disrupting each other while sharing the same hardware and thereby lowering costs further.

3.2 NEW APPLICATION OPPORTUNITIES

While we have yet to see fundamentally new types of applications enabled by Cloud Computing, we believe that several important classes of existing applications will become even more compelling with Cloud Computing and contribute further to its momentum. When Jim Gray examined technological trends in 2003, he concluded that economic necessity mandates putting the data near the application, since the cost of wide-area networking has fallen more slowly (and remains relatively higher) than all other IT hardware costs. Although hardware costs have changed since Gray's analysis, his idea of this "breakeven point" has not. Although we defer a more thorough discussion of Cloud Computing economics to Section 6, we use Gray's insight in examining what kinds of applications represent particularly good opportunities and drivers for Cloud Computing.

MOBILE INTERACTIVE APPLICATIONS. Tim O'Reilly believes that "the future belongs to services that respond in real time to information provided either by their users or by nonhuman sensors." [38] Such services will be attracted to the cloud not only because they must be highly available, but also because these services generally rely on large data sets that are most conveniently hosted in large datacenters. This is especially the case for services that combine two or more data sources or other services, e.g., mash ups. While not all mobile devices enjoy connectivity to the cloud 100% of the time, the challenge of disconnected operation has been addressed successfully in specific application domains, 2 so we do not see this as a significant obstacle to the appeal of mobile applications.

PARALLEL BATCH PROCESSING. Although thus far we have concentrated on using Cloud Computing for interactive SaaS, Cloud Computing presents a unique opportunity for batch-processing and analytics jobs that analyze terabytes of data and can take hours to finish. If there is enough data parallelism in the application, users can take advantage of the cloud's new "cost associatively": using hundreds of computers for a short time costs the same as using a few computers for a long time. For example, Peter Harkins, a Senior Engineer at The Washington Post, used 200 EC2 instances (1,407 server hours) to convert 17,481 pages of Hillary Clinton's travel documents into a form more friendly to use on the WWW within nine hours after they were released [3]. Programming abstractions such as Google's Map Reduce [16] and its open-source counterpart Hadoop [11] allow programmers to express such tasks while hiding the operational complexity of choreographing parallel execution across hundreds of Cloud Computing servers. Indeed, Cloud era [1] is pursuing commercial opportunities in this space. Again, using Gray's insight, the cost/benefit analysis must weigh the cost of moving large datasets into the cloud against the benefit of potential speedup in the data analysis. When we return to economic models later, we speculate that part of Amazon's motivation to host large public datasets for free [8] may be to mitigate the cost side of this analysis and thereby attract users to purchase Cloud Computing

Cycles near this data.

THE RISE OF ANALYTICS. A special case of compute-intensive batch processing is business analytics. While the large database industry was originally dominated by transaction processing, that demand is leveling off. A growing share of computing resources is now spent on understanding customers, supply chains, buying habits, ranking, and so on. Hence, while online transaction volumes will continue to grow slowly, decision support is growing rapidly, shifting the resource balance in database processing from transactions to business analytics.

EXTENSION OF COMPUTE-INTENSIVE DESKTOP APPLICATIONS. The latest versions of the mathematics software packages Matlab and Mathematica are capable of using Cloud Computing to perform expensive evaluations. Other desktop applications might similarly benefit from seamless extension into the cloud. Again, a reasonable test is comparing the cost of computing in the Cloud plus the cost of moving data in and out of the Cloud to the time savings from using the Cloud. Symbolic mathematics involves a great deal of computing per unit of data, making it a domain worth investigating. An interesting alternative model might be to keep the data in the cloud and rely on having sufficient bandwidth to enable suitable visualization and a responsive GUI back to the human user. Offline image rendering or 3D animation might be a similar example: given a compact description of the objects in a 3D scene and the characteristics of the lighting sources, rendering the image is an embarrassingly parallel task with a high computation-to-bytes ratio.

“EARTHBOUND” APPLICATIONS. Some applications that would otherwise be good candidates for the cloud’s elasticity and parallelism may be thwarted by data movement costs, the fundamental latency limits of getting into and out of the cloud, or both. For example, while the analytics associated with making long-term financial decisions are appropriate for the Cloud, stock trading that requires microsecond precision is not. Until the cost (and possibly latency) of wide area data transfer decrease (see Section 7), such applications may be less obvious candidates for the cloud.

4 CLASSES OF UTILITY COMPUTING

Any application needs a model of computation, a model of storage and, assuming the application is even trivially distributed, a model of communication. The statistical multiplexing necessary to achieve elasticity and the illusion of infinite capacity requires resources to be virtualized, so that the implementation of how they are multiplexed and shared can be hidden from the programmer. Our view is that different utility computing offerings will be distinguished based on the level of abstraction presented to the programmer and the level of management of the resources.

Amazon EC2 is at one end of the spectrum. An EC2 instance looks much like physical hardware, and users can control nearly the entire software stack, from the kernel upwards. The API exposed is “thin”: a few dozen API calls to request and configure the virtualized hardware. There is no a priori limit on the kinds of applications that can be hosted; the low level of virtualization—raw CPU cycles, block-device storage, IP-level connectivity—allow developers to code whatever they want. On the other hand, this makes it inherently difficult for Amazon to

offer automatic scalability and failover, because the semantics associated with replication and other state management issues are highly application-dependent.

AWS does offer a number of higher-level managed services, including several different managed storage services for use in conjunction with EC2, such as Simple DB. However, these offerings have higher latency and nonstandard API's, and our understanding is that they are not as widely used as other parts of AWS.

Table 4 summarizes how these three classes virtualize computation, storage, and networking. The scattershot offerings of scalable storage suggest that scalable storage with an API comparable in richness to SQL remains an open research problem (see Section 7). Amazon has begun offering Oracle databases hosted on AWS, but the economics and licensing model of this product makes it a less natural fit for Cloud Computing. Table 4 summarizes how these three classes virtualize computation, storage, and networking. The scattershot offerings of scalable storage suggest that scalable storage with an API comparable in richness to SQL remains an open research problem (see Section 7). Amazon has begun offering Oracle databases hosted on AWS, but the economics and licensing model of this product makes it a less natural fit for Cloud Computing.

Will one model beat out the others in the Cloud Computing space? We can draw an analogy with programming languages and frameworks. Low-level languages such as C and assembly language allow fine control and close communication with the bare metal, but if the developer is writing a Web application, the mechanics of managing sockets, dispatching requests, and so on are cumbersome and tedious to code, even with good libraries. On the other hand, high-level frameworks such as Ruby on Rails make these mechanics invisible to the programmer, but are only useful if the application readily fits the request/reply structure and the abstractions provided by Rails; any deviation requires diving into the framework at best, and may be awkward to code. No reasonable Ruby developer would argue against the superiority of C for certain tasks, and vice versa. Correspondingly, we believe different tasks will result in demand for different classes of utility computing.

TABLE 4: EXAMPLES OF CLOUD COMPUTING VENDORS AND HOW EACH PROVIDES VIRTUALIZED RESOURCES (COMPUTATION, STORAGE, NETWORKING) AND ENSURES SCALABILITY AND HIGH AVAILABILITY OF THE RESOURCES

	Amazon Web Services	Microsoft Azure	Google AppEngine
Computation model (VM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ x86 Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) via Xen VM _ Computation elasticity allows scalability, but developer must build the machinery, or third party VAR such as Right Scale must provide it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ Microsoft Common Language Runtime (CLR) VM; common intermediate form executed in managed environment _ Machines are provisioned based on declarative descriptions (e.g. which “roles” can be replicated); automatic load balancing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ Predefined application structure and framework; programmer-provided “handlers” written in Python, all persistent state stored in Mega Store (outside Python code) _ Automatic scaling up and down of computation and storage; network and server failover; all consistent with 3-tier Web app structure
Storage model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ Range of models from block store (EBS) to augmented key/blob store (Simple DB) _ Automatic scaling varies from no scaling or sharing (EBS) to fully automatic (Simple DB, S3), depending on which model used _ Consistency guarantees vary widely depending on which model used _ APIs vary from standardized (EBS) to proprietary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ SQL Data Services (restricted view of SQL Server) _ Azure storage service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ Mega Store/Big Table

<p>Networking model</p>	<p>Declarative specification of IP level topology; internal placement details concealed _ Security Groups enable restricting which nodes may communicate _ Availability zones provide abstraction of independent network failure _ Elastic IP addresses provide persistently routable network name</p>	<p>Automatic based on programmer's declarative descriptions of app components (roles)</p>	<p>Fixed topology to accommodate 3-tier Web app structure _ Scaling up and down is automatic and programmer invisible</p>
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5 CLOUD COMPUTING ECONOMICS

In this section we make some observations about Cloud Computing economic models:

- In deciding whether hosting a service in the cloud makes sense over the long term, we argue that the finegrained economic models enabled by Cloud Computing make tradeoff decisions more fluid, and in particular the elasticity offered by clouds serves to transfer risk.
- As well, although hardware resource costs continue to decline, they do so at variable rates; for example, computing and storage costs are falling faster than WAN costs. Cloud Computing can track these changes—and potentially pass them through to the customer—more effectively than building one's own datacenter, resulting in a closer match of expenditure to actual resource usage.
- In making the decision about whether to move an existing service to the cloud, one must additionally examine the expected average and peak resource utilization, especially if the application may have highly variable spikes in resource demand; the practical limits on real-world utilization of purchased equipment; and various operational costs that vary depending on the type of cloud environment being considered.

5.1 ELASTICITY: SHIFTING THE RISK

Although the economic appeal of Cloud Computing is often described as “converting capital expenses to operating expenses” (CapEx to OpEx), we believe the phrase “pay as you go” more directly captures the economic benefit to the buyer. Hours purchased via Cloud Computing can be distributed non-uniformly in time (e.g., use 100 server-hours today and no server-hours tomorrow, and still pay only for what you use); in the networking community, this way of selling

bandwidth is already known as usage-based pricing. ³ In addition, the absence of up-front capital expense allows capital to be redirected to core business investment.

Therefore, even though Amazon's pay-as-you-go pricing (for example) could be more expensive than buying and depreciating a comparable server over the same period, we argue that the cost is outweighed by the extremely important Cloud Computing economic benefits of elasticity and transference of risk, especially the risks of over provisioning (underutilization) and under provisioning (saturation).

We start with elasticity. The key observation is that Cloud Computing ability to add or remove resources at a fine grain (one server at a time with EC2) and with a lead time of minutes rather than weeks allows matching resources to workload much more closely. Real world estimates of server utilization in datacenters range from 5% to 20% [37, 38]. This may sound shockingly low, but it is consistent with the observation that for many services the peak workload exceeds the average by factors of 2 to 10. Few users deliberately provision for less than the expected peak, and therefore they must provision for the peak and allow the resources to remain idle at nonpeak times. The more pronounced the variation, the more the waste. A simple example demonstrates how elasticity allows reducing this waste and can therefore more than compensate for the potentially higher cost per server-hour of paying-as-you-go vs. buying.

Example: Elasticity. Assume our service has a predictable daily demand where the peak requires 500 servers at noon but the trough requires only 100 servers at midnight, as shown in Figure 2(a). As long as the average utilization over a whole day is 300 servers, the actual utilization over the whole day (shaded area under the curve) is $300 \times 24 = 7200$ server-hours; but since we must provision to the peak of 500 servers, we pay for $500 \times 24 = 12000$ server-hours, a factor of 1.7 more than what is needed. Therefore, as long as the pay-as-you-go cost per server-hour over 3 years⁴ is less than 1.7 times the cost of buying the server, we can save money using utility computing.

They may also underestimate the spike (Figure 2(b)), however, accidentally turning away excess users. While the monetary effects of over provisioning are easily measured, those of under provisioning are harder to measure yet potentially equally serious: not only do rejected users generate zero revenue; they may never come back due to poor service. Figure 2(c) aims to capture this behavior: users will desert an under provisioned service until the peak user

(a) Provisioning for peak load

(b) Underprovisioning 1

Figure 2: (a) Even if peak load can be correctly anticipated, without elasticity we waste resources (shaded area) during nonpeak times. (b) Under provisioning case 1: potential revenue from users not served (shaded area) is sacrificed. (c) Under provisioning case 2: some users desert the site permanently after experiencing poor service; this attrition and possible negative press result in a permanent loss of a portion of the revenue stream.

load equals the datacenter's usable capacity, at which point users again receive acceptable service, but with fewer potential users.

Example: Transferring risks. Suppose but 10% of users who receive poor service due to under provisioning are "permanently lost" opportunities, i.e. users who would have remained regular visitors with a better experience. The site is initially provisioned to handle an expected peak of 400,000 users (1000 users per server _ 400 servers), but unexpected positive press drives 500,000 users in the first hour. Of the 100,000 who are turned away or receive bad service, by our assumption 10,000 of them are permanently lost, leaving an active user base of 390,000. The next hour sees 250,000 new unique users. The first 10,000 do fine, but the site is still over capacity by 240,000 users. This results in 24,000 additional defections, leaving 376,000 permanent users. If this pattern continues, after 1g 500000 or 19 hours, the number of new users will approach zero and the site will be at capacity in steady state. Clearly, the service operator has collected less than 400,000 users' worth of steady revenue during those 19 hours, however, again illustrating the underutilization argument —to say nothing of the bad reputation from the disgruntled users.

Do such scenarios really occur in practice? When Animoto made its service available via Facebook, it experienced a demand surge that resulted in growing from 50 servers to 3500 servers in three days. Even if the average utilization of each server was low, no one could have foreseen that resource needs would suddenly double every 12 hours for 3 days. After the peak subsided, traffic fell to a level that was well below the peak. So in this real world example, scale-up elasticity was not a cost optimization but an operational requirement, and scale-down elasticity allowed the steady-state expenditure to more closely match the steady-state workload.

Even less-dramatic cases suffice to illustrate this key benefit of Cloud Computing: the risk of mis-estimating workload is shifted from the service operator to the cloud vendor. The cloud vendor may charge a premium (reflected as a higher use cost per server-hour compared to the 3-year purchase cost) for assuming this risk. We propose the following simple equation that generalizes all of the above cases. We assume the Cloud Computing vendor employs 11 usage-

based pricing, in which customers pay proportionally to the amount of time and the amount of resources they use. While some argue for more sophisticated pricing models for infrastructure services [28, 6, 40], we believe usage based pricing will persist because it is simpler and more transparent, as demonstrated by its wide use by “real” utilities such as electricity and gas companies. Similarly, we assume that the customer’s revenue is directly proportional to the total number of user-hours. This assumption is consistent with the ad-supported revenue model in which the number of ads served is roughly proportional to the total visit time spent by end users on the service.

$$\text{UserHours}_{\text{cloud}} \times (\text{revenue} - \text{Cost}_{\text{cloud}}) \geq \text{UserHours}_{\text{datacenter}} \times \left(\text{revenue} - \frac{\text{Cost}_{\text{datacenter}}}{\text{Utilization}} \right)$$

The left-hand side multiplies the net revenue per user-hour (revenue realized per user-hour minus cost of paying Cloud Computing per user-hour) by the number of user-hours, giving the expected profit from using Cloud Computing. The right-hand side performs the same calculation for a fixed-capacity datacenter by factoring in the average utilization, including nonpeak workloads. Whichever side is greater represents the opportunity for higher profit.

Apparently, if Utilization = 1:0 (the datacenter equipment is 100% utilized), the two sides of the equation look the same. However, basic queuing theory tells us that as utilization approaches 1.0, system response time approaches infinity. In practice, the usable capacity of a datacenter (without compromising service) is typically 0.6 to 0.8.6 Whereas a datacenter must necessarily overprovision to account for this “overhead,” the cloud vendor can simply factor it into Cost cloud. (This overhead explains why we use the phrase “pay-as-you-go” rather than rent or lease for utility computing. The latter phrases include this unusable overhead, while the former doesn’t. Hence, even if you lease a 100 Mbits/second Internet link, you can likely use only 60 to 80 Mbits/second in practice.)

Finally, there are two additional benefits to the Cloud Computing user that result from being able to change their resource usage on the scale of hours rather than years. First, unexpectedly scaling down (disposing of temporarily underutilized equipment)—for example, due to a business slowdown, or ironically due to improved software efficiency— normally carries a financial penalty. With 3-year depreciation, a \$2,100 server decommissioned after 1 year of operation represents a “penalty” of \$1,400. Cloud Computing eliminates this penalty.

Second, technology trends suggest that over the useful lifetime of some purchased equipment, hardware costs will fall and new hardware and software technologies will become available. Cloud providers, who already enjoy economy-of-scale buying power as described in Section 3, can potentially pass on some of these savings to their customers. Indeed, heavy users of AWS saw storage costs fall 20% and networking costs fall 50% over the last 2.5 years, and the addition of nine new services or features to AWS over less than one year. 7 If new technologies or pricing plans become available to a cloud vendor, existing applications and customers can potentially benefit from them immediately, without incurring a capital expense. In less than two years, Amazon Web Services increased the number of different types of compute servers (“instances”)

from one to five, and in less than one year they added seven new infrastructure services and two new operational support options. 8

5.2 COMPARING COSTS: SHOULD I MOVE TO THE CLOUD?

Whereas the previous section tried to quantify the economic value of specific Cloud Computing benefits such as elasticity, this section tackles an equally important but larger question: Is it more economical to move my existing datacenter-hosted service to the cloud, or to keep it in a datacenter?

Table 5 updates Gray's 2003 cost data to 2008, allowing us to track the rate of change of key technologies for Cloud Computing for the last 5 years. Note that, as expected, wide-area networking costs have improved the least in 5 years, by less than a factor of 3. While computing costs have improved the most in 5 years, the ability to use the extra computing power is based on the assumption that programs can utilize all the cores on both sockets in the computer. This assumption is likely more true for Utility Computing, with many Virtual Machines serving thousands to millions of customers, than it is for programs inside the datacenter of a single company.

To facilitate calculations, Gray calculated what \$1 bought in 2003. Table 5 shows his numbers vs. 2008 and compares to EC2/S3 charges. At first glance, it appears that a given dollar will go further if used to purchase hardware in 2008 than to pay for use of that same hardware. However, this simple analysis glosses over several important factors.

Pay separately per resource. Most applications do not make equal use of computation, storage, and network bandwidth; some are CPU-bound, others network-bound, and so on, and may saturate one resource while underutilizing others. Pay-as-you-go Cloud Computing can charge the application separately for each type of resource, reducing the waste of underutilization. While the exact savings depends on the application, suppose the CPU is only 50% utilized while the network is at capacity; then in a datacenter you are effectively paying for double the number of CPU cycles actually being used. So rather than saying it costs \$2.56 to rent only \$1 worth of CPU, it would be more accurate to say it costs \$2.56 to rent \$2 worth of CPU. As a side note, AWS's prices for wide-area networking are actually more competitive than what a medium-sized company would pay for the same bandwidth.

Table 5: We update Gray's costs of computing resources from 2003 to 2008, normalize to what \$1 could buy in 2003 vs. 2008, and compare to the cost of paying per use of \$1 worth of resources on AWS at 2008 prices.

	WAN bandwidth/mo.	CPU hours (all cores)	disk storage
Item in 2003	1 Mbps WAN link	2 GHz CPU, 2 GB DRAM	200 GB disk, 50 Mb/s transfer rate
Cost in 2003	\$100/mo.	\$2000	\$200
\$1 buys in 2003	1 GB	8 CPU hours	1 GB
Item in 2008	100 Mbps WAN link	2 GHz, 2 sockets, 4 cores/socket, 4 GB DRAM	1 TB disk, 115 MB/s sustained transfer
Cost in 2008	\$3600/mo.	\$1000	\$100
\$1 buys in 2008	2.7 GB	128 CPU hours	10 GB
cost/performance improvement	2.7x	16x	10x
Cost to rent \$1 worth on AWS in 2008	\$0.27–\$0.40 ($\$0.10\text{--}\$0.15/\text{GB} \times 3 \text{ GB}$)	\$2.56 ($128 \times 2 \text{ VM's} @ \0.10 each)	\$1.20–\$1.50 ($\$0.12\text{--}\$0.15/\text{GB-month} \times 10 \text{ GB}$)

POWER, COOLING AND PHYSICAL PLANT COSTS. The costs of power, cooling, and the amortized cost of the building are missing from our simple analyses so far. Hamilton estimates that the costs of CPU, storage and bandwidth roughly double when those costs are amortized over the building's lifetime [23, 26]. Using this estimate, buying 128 hours of CPU in 2008 really costs \$2 rather than \$1, compared to \$2.56 on EC2. Similarly, 10 GB of disk space costs \$2 rather than \$1, compared to \$1.20–\$1.50 per month on S3. Lastly, S3 actually replicates the data at least 3 times for durability and performance, ensure durability, and will replicate it further for performance is there is high demand for the data. That means the costs are \$6.00 when purchasing vs. \$1.20 to \$1.50 per month on S3.

OPERATIONS COSTS. Today, hardware operations costs are very low—rebooting servers is easy (e.g., IP addressable power strips, separate out of band controllers, and so on) and minimally trained staff can replace broken components at the rack or server level. On one hand, since Utility Computing uses virtual machines instead of physical machines, from the cloud user's point of view these tasks are shifted to the cloud provider. On the other hand, depending on the level of virtualization, much of the software management costs may remain—upgrades, applying patches, and so on. Returning to the “managed vs. unmanaged” discussion of Section 5, we believe these costs will be lower for managed environments (e.g. Microsoft Azure, Google AppEngine, Force.com) than for hardware-level utility computing (e.g. Amazon EC2), but it seems hard to quantify these benefits in a way that many would agree with.

With the above caveats in mind, here is a simple example of deciding whether to move a service into the cloud.

Example: Moving to cloud. Suppose a biology lab creates 500 GB of new data for every wet lab experiment. A computer the speed of one EC2 instance takes 2 hours per GB to process the new data. The lab has the equivalent 20 instances locally, so the time to evaluate the experiment is $500 \times 2 = 20$ or 50 hours. They could process it in a single hour on 1000 instances at AWS. The cost to process one experiment would be just $1000 \times \$0:10$ or \$100 in computation and another $500 \times \$0:10$ or \$50 in network transfer fees. So far, so good. They measure the transfer rate from the lab to AWS at 20 Mbits/second. [19] The transfer time is $(500\text{GB} \times 1000\text{MB} = \text{GB} \times 8\text{bits} = \text{Byte}) = 20\text{Mbits} = \text{sec} = 4; 000; 000 = 20 = 200; 000$ seconds or more than 55 hours. Thus, it takes 50 hours locally vs. $55 + 1$ or 56 hours on AWS, so they don't move to the cloud. (The next section offers an opportunity on how to overcome the transfer delay obstacle.)

A related issue is the software complexity and costs of (partial or full) migrating data from a legacy enterprise application into the Cloud. While migration is a one-time task, the amount of effort can be significant and it needs to be considered as a factor in deciding to use Cloud Computing. This task is already spawning new business opportunities for companies that provide data integration across public and private Clouds.

Table 6: Top 10 Obstacles to and Opportunities for Adoption and Growth of Cloud Computing.

	Obstacle	Opportunity
1	Availability of Service	Use Multiple Cloud Providers to provide Business Continuity; Use Elasticity to Defend Against DDOS attacks
2	Data Lock-In	Standardize APIs; Make compatible software available to enable Surge Computing
3	Data Confidentiality and Auditability	Deploy Encryption, VLANs, and Firewalls; Accommodate National Laws via Geographical Data Storage
4	Data Transfer Bottlenecks	FedExing Disks; Data Backup/Archival; Lower WAN Router Costs; Higher Bandwidth LAN Switches
5	Performance Unpredictability	Improved Virtual Machine Support; Flash Memory; Gang Scheduling VMs for HPC apps
6	Scalable Storage	Invent Scalable Store
7	Bugs in Large-Scale Distributed Systems	Invent Debugger that relies on Distributed VMs
8	Scaling Quickly	Invent Auto-Scaler that relies on Machine Learning; Snapshots to encourage Cloud Computing Conservationism
9	Reputation Fate Sharing	Offer reputation-guarding services like those for email
10	Software Licensing	Pay-for-use licenses; Bulk use sales

TOP 05 OBSTACLES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR CLOUD COMPUTING

In this section, we offer a ranked list of obstacles to the growth of Cloud Computing. Each obstacle is paired with an opportunity—our thoughts on how to overcome the obstacle, ranging from straightforward product development to major research projects. Table 6 summarizes our top ten obstacles and opportunities. The first three are technical obstacles to the adoption of Cloud Computing, the next five are technical obstacles to the growth of Cloud Computing once it

has been adopted, and the last two are policy and business obstacles to the adoption of Cloud Computing.

NUMBER 1 OBSTACLE: AVAILABILITY OF A SERVICE

Organizations worry about whether Utility Computing services will have adequate availability, and this makes some wary of Cloud Computing. Ironically, existing SaaS products have set a high standard in this regard. Google Search is effectively the dial tone of the Internet: if people went to Google for search and it wasn't available, they would think the Internet was down. Users expect similar availability from new services, which is hard to do. Table 7 shows recorded outages for Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3), AppEngine and Gmail in 2008, and explanations for the outages. Note that despite the negative publicity due to these outages, few enterprise IT infrastructures are as good.

Table 7: Outages in AWS, AppEngine, and Gmail

Service and Outage	Duration	Date
S3 outage: authentication service overload leading to unavailability [39]	2 hours	2/15/08
S3 outage: Single bit error leading to gossip protocol blowup. [41]	6-8 hours	7/20/08
AppEngine partial outage: programming error [43]	5 hours	6/17/08
Gmail: site unavailable due to outage in contacts system [29]	1.5 hours	8/11/08

Just as large Internet service providers use multiple network providers so that failure by a single company will not take them off the air, we believe the only plausible solution to very high availability is multiple Cloud Computing providers. The high-availability computing community has long followed the mantra “no single source of failure,” yet the management of a Cloud Computing service by a single company is in fact a single point of failure. Even if the company has multiple datacenters in different geographic regions using different network providers, it may have common software infrastructure and accounting systems, or the company may even go out of business. Large customers will be reluctant to migrate to Cloud Computing without a business-continuity strategy for such situations. We believe the best chance for independent software stacks is for them to be provided by different companies, as it has been difficult for one company to justify creating and maintain two stacks in the name of software dependability.

NUMBER 2 OBSTACLE: DATA LOCK-IN

Software stacks have improved interoperability among platforms, but the APIs for Cloud Computing itself are still essentially proprietary, or at least have not been the subject of active standardization. Thus, customers cannot easily extract their data and programs from one site to run on another. Concern about the difficult of extracting data from the cloud is preventing some organizations from adopting Cloud Computing. Customer lock-in may be attractive to Cloud

Computing providers, but Cloud Computing users are vulnerable to price increases (as Stallman warned), to reliability problems, or even to providers going out of business. For example, an online storage service called The Linkup shut down on August 8, 2008 after losing access as much as 45% of customer data. The Linkup, in turn, had relied on the online storage service Nirvanix to store customer data, and now there is finger pointing between the two organizations as to why customer data was lost. Meanwhile, The Linkup's 20,000 users were told the service was no longer available and were urged to try out another storage site. The obvious solution is to standardize the APIs so that a SaaS developer could deploy services and data across multiple Cloud Computing providers so that the failure of a single company would not take all copies of customer data with it. The obvious fear is that this would lead to a "race-to-the-bottom" of cloud pricing and flatten the profits of Cloud Computing providers. We offer two arguments to allay this fear. First, the quality of a service matters as well as the price, so customers will not necessarily jump to the lowest cost service. Some Internet Service Providers today cost a factor of ten more than others because they are more dependable and offer extra services to improve usability. Second, in addition to mitigating data lock-in concerns, standardization of APIs enables a new usage model in which the same software infrastructure can be used in a Private Cloud and in a Public Cloud. 9 Such an option could enable "Surge Computing," in which the public Cloud is used to capture the extra tasks that cannot be easily run in the datacenter (or private cloud) due to temporarily heavy workloads. 10

NUMBER 3 OBSTACLE: DATA CONFIDENTIALITY AND AUDIT ABILITY

"My sensitive corporate data will never be in the cloud." Anecdotally we have heard this repeated multiple times. Current cloud offerings are essentially public (rather than private) networks, exposing the system to more attacks. There are also requirements for audit ability, in the sense of Sarbanes-Oxley and Health and Human Services Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) regulations that must be provided for corporate data to be moved to the cloud.

We believe that there are no fundamental obstacles to making a cloud-computing environment as secure as the vast majority of in-house IT environments, and that many of the obstacles can be overcome immediately with well understood technologies such as encrypted storage, Virtual Local Area Networks, and network middle boxes (e.g. firewalls, packet filters). For example, encrypting data before placing it in a Cloud may be even more secure than unencrypted data in a local data center; this approach was successfully used by TC3, a healthcare company with access to sensitive patient records and healthcare claims, when moving their HIPAA-compliant application to AWS

Cloud computing gives SaaS providers and SaaS users greater freedom to place their storage. For example, Amazon provides S3 services located physically in the United States and in Europe, allowing providers to keep data in whichever they choose. With AWS regions, a simple configuration change avoids the need to find and negotiate with a hosting provider overseas.

NUMBER 4 OBSTACLE: SCALABLE STORAGE

Early in this paper, we identified three properties whose combination gives Cloud Computing its appeal: short-term usage (which implies scaling down as well as up when resources are no longer needed), no up-front cost, and infinite capacity on-demand. While it's straightforward what this means when applied to computation, it's less obvious how to apply it to persistent storage.

As Table 4 shows, there have been many attempts to answer this question, varying in the richness of the query and storage API's, the performance guarantees offered, and the complexity of data structures that are directly supported by the storage system (e.g., schema-less blobs vs. column-oriented storage).¹⁴ The opportunity, which is still an open research problem, is to create a storage system would not only meet these needs but combine them with the cloud advantages of scaling arbitrarily up and down on-demand, as well as meeting programmer expectations in regard to resource management for scalability, data durability, and high availability.

NUMBER 5 OBSTACLE: BUGS IN LARGE-SCALE DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS

One of the difficult challenges in Cloud Computing is removing errors in these very large scale distributed systems. A common occurrence is that these bugs cannot be reproduced in smaller configurations, so the debugging must occur at scale in the production datacenters.

One opportunity may be the reliance on virtual machines in Cloud Computing. Many traditional SaaS providers developed their infrastructure without using VMs, either because they preceded the recent popularity of VMs or because they felt they could not afford the performance hit of VMs. Since VMs are de rigueur in Utility Computing,

that level of virtualization may make it possible to capture valuable information in ways that are implausible without VMs.

8 CONCLUSION AND QUESTIONS ABOUT THE CLOUDS OF TOMORROW

The long dreamed vision of computing as a utility is finally emerging. The elasticity of a utility matches the need of businesses providing services directly to customers over the Internet, as workloads can grow (and shrink) far faster than 20 years ago. It used to take years to grow a business to several million customers – now it can happen in months.

From the cloud provider's view, the construction of very large datacenters at low cost sites using commodity computing, storage, and networking uncovered the possibility of selling those resources on a pay-as-you-go model below the costs of many medium-sized datacenters, while making a profit by statistically multiplexing among a large group of customers. From the cloud user's view, it would be as startling for a new software startup to build its own datacenter as it would for a hardware startup to build its own fabrication line. In addition to startups, many other established organizations take advantage of the elasticity of Cloud Computing regularly, including newspapers like the Washington Post, movie companies like Pixar, and universities like ours. Our lab has benefited substantially from the ability to complete research by conference

deadlines and adjust resources over the semester to accommodate course deadlines. As Cloud Computing users, we were relieved of dealing with the twin dangers of over-provisioning and under-provisioning our internal datacenters.

Some question whether companies accustomed to high-margin businesses, such as ad revenue from search engines and traditional packaged software, can compete in Cloud Computing. First, the question presumes that Cloud Computing is a small margin business based on its low cost. Given the typical utilization of medium-sized datacenters, the potential factors of 5 to 7 in economies of scale, and the further savings in selection of cloud datacenter locations, the apparently low costs offered to cloud users may still be highly profitable to cloud providers. Second, these companies may already have the datacenter, networking, and software infrastructure in place for their mainline businesses, so Cloud Computing represents the opportunity for more income at little extra cost.

Although Cloud Computing providers may run afoul of the obstacles summarized in Table 6, we believe that over the long run providers will successfully navigate these challenges and set an example for others to follow, perhaps by successfully exploiting the opportunities that correspond to those obstacles.

Hence, developers would be wise to design their next generation of systems to be deployed into Cloud Computing. In general, the emphasis should be horizontal scalability to hundreds or thousands of virtual machines over the efficiency of the system on a single virtual machine. There are specific implications as well: •

Applications Software of the future will likely have a piece that runs on clients and a piece that runs in the Cloud. The cloud piece needs to both scale down rapidly as well as scale up, which is a new requirement for software systems. The client piece needs to be useful when disconnected from the Cloud, which is not the case for many Web 2.0 applications today. Such software also needs a pay-for-use licensing model to match needs of Cloud Computing. •

Infrastructure Software of the future needs to be cognizant that it is no longer running on bare metal but on virtual machines. Moreover, it needs to have billing built in from the beginning, as it is very difficult to retrofit an accounting system.

While we are optimistic about the future of Cloud Computing, we would love to look into a crystal ball to see how popular it is and what it will look like in five years:

Change In Technology and Prices Over Time: What will billing units be like for the higher-level virtualization clouds? What will Table 5, tracking the relative prices of different resources, look like? Clearly, the number of cores per chip will increase over time, doubling every two to four years. Flash memory has the potential of adding another relatively fast layer to the classic memory hierarchy; what will be its billing unit? Will technology or business innovations accelerate network bandwidth pricing, which is currently the most slowly-improving technology?

VIRTUALIZATION LEVEL: Will Cloud Computing be dominated by low-level hardware virtual machines like Amazon EC2, intermediate language offerings like Microsoft Azure, or high-level frameworks like Google AppEngine? Or will we have many virtualization levels that match different applications? Will value-added services by independent companies like Right Scale, Heroku, or Engine Yard survive in Utility Computing, or will the successful services be entirely co-opted by the Cloud providers? If they do consolidate to a single virtualization layer, will multiple companies embrace a common standard? Will this lead to a race to the bottom in pricing so that it's unattractive to become a Cloud Computing provider, or will they differentiate in services or quality to maintain margins?

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TRANSACTIONAL ANALYSIS DERIVATIVES AN APPROACH TO ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE AND DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

TA theory explains human behavior from the perspective of understanding transactions that take place based on the programmed experiences in the childhood. Transactional analysis theory and approach is given a fresh interpretation in the context of the organizational processes of change and development. The ego states of Parent, Adult and Child are further understood with its different components. Similarly analysis of transactions, script analysis, life positions and game analysis become the focal themes in the realm of organizational change and development. Finally a TA model of organizational change and development is suggested that can be effectively utilized to accelerate the process.

KEYWORDS: *Ego state Script Analysis Game Analysis Model of Organizational Change and Development Organizational Positions.*

I INTRODUCTION

Transactional Analysis (TA) that occupies a central position in the study, understanding, and interpretation of human behavior is embedded with lots of intricacies so far unexplored in the myriad situations of life. It is applied with vigor in the specific context of organizational behavior processes and more particularly in the area of organizational change and development. The present exploration and the consequent derivatives are drawn from the main body of TA theory and approach to transforming human behavior from unhealthy and negative programming to healthy and positive programming and living.

TA as applied today in the area of organizational change and development needs revision and a new interpretation which is supposed to be made here. The TA theory is applied to examining individual functioning with less focus on group/organizational contexts. The TA concepts of ego state analysis, analysis of communication transactions, script analysis, individual positions of okayness and not okayness and games people play get a new interpretation in the managerial and organizational contexts where individuals, groups and organizations are the units of analysis.

II EGO STATE ANALYSIS

Ego state as a psychological state of mind gets expressed in one's way of thinking, feeling and behavior at a point of transaction. It is the current state of the mind derived from the past events that refer to real situations of life. The ongoing transactions of the mind are based on the past programmed data that are reenacted in similar or apparently similar situations of interpersonal and intra personal processes. The present ego state is linked to stored data of emotional, cognitive, motivational and behavioral significance, all of which together give rise to the three identified ego states of parent, adult and child with subcomponents. Ego state as a differentiated system of interacting feelings, thoughts and potential behaviors represent the childhood experiences that take shape in the three states and that within each state different kinds of thoughts, feelings and acts can be identified (English, 2005). Over and above the traditional components of TA in each ego state, in this analysis of the relevance of TA in organizational change and development, six other components are brought forward in the ego states of parent, adult and child.

2.1. PARENT EGO STATE AND THE SUB-COMPONENTS

Generally known as the “taught” concept of life, parent ego state represents the ideas, attitudes, beliefs, opinions and behaviors of all parental figures like father, mother, teachers, elders, leaders and other authority figures who open a “file” in the memory structure of the individual that becomes a repository of their ideas, conversations, beliefs and opinions. Parent ego state is functional along the lines of right and wrong, do's, and don'ts, commands, orders, obedience, authority and unquestionable instructions. This file of parental memory gets activated in the current state of the mind as parental ego state that transacts with the world.

In the structural differentiation of the ego states, it is to be noted that each ego state can contain other ego states (Widdowson, 2010). This differentiation brings about further subdivisions in each ego state characterized by a specific system of thoughts, feelings and actions. As explained in the Figs.1(a) & 1 (b), the parental ego state is differentiated structurally and functionally which are specific to the organizational processes. And that a transaction process initiated and maintained in the parental state can contain “matters” which can be diagnosed as Adult and Child. In this way a parental ego state can be structurally and functionally differentiated into three positive and three negative ego states. Positive and negative ego states imply transaction conducted along productive and unproductive programmes.

The sub-components of the parental ego-state identified in the organizational context are the following:

2.1.1. THE AUTHORITY-MINDED PARENT (AM): In this ego state managers and top officials think, feel and act along strict authority channels, exercising the power in visible and invisible ways so as to influence the subordinates. Notions of authority dominate the state of the mind. The manager would say “you do this as suggested by me”.

FIG.1 (A).PARENT EGO STATE SUB-COMPONENTS

FIG.1 (B) PARENT EGO STATE SUB-COMPONENTS

2.1.2. COOPERATIVE AND CARING PARENT (CC): Similar to the nurturing parent ego-state, a cooperative and caring parent ego state expresses in terms of supporting and cooperating with the co-workers and subordinates in order to ensure smooth functioning of the organization. For example in the process of implementation of change and development programmes, the manager who is functioning in this ego state is prompted to say, “let us do it together”.

2.1.3. CONSERVATIVE PARENT (CP): In this ego state of conservatism, managers are sticking to traditions, conventions and the established procedures of managing instead of experimenting with the new and the modern. The conservative ego state, which is expressed as, for example, “I’m comfortable with this system of working” can be traced back to the conservative upbringing of the early life. As is evident, the conservative parental ego state opposes the introduction of modern change programmes.

2.1.4. LIBERAL PARENT (LP): Opposite to the conservative parent, the liberal parent actively promotes change and development. The ego state that is expressed verbally and non-verbally allows the manager to move forward with new development plans as he is prone to welcoming new plans. The desire to embrace modernity means that change is swift under this manager who may say, for example “I want to proceed with the programme at any cost”.

2.1.5. SUSPICIOUS AND DOUBTFUL PARENT (SD): The ego state characterized by wavering and frequent change prevents the manager from effectively executing change projects or even conceiving change plans. As the mind is overcrowded with the thoughts and the feelings of suspicion and hesitation to act, a doubtful and indecisive ego state never transacts in a way to make progress. “We can’t do this as it has lots of limitations and it is going to invite lots of opposition” is reflective of this ego state.

2.1.6. A RESILIENT AND CONFIDENT EGO STATE (RC): In this parental ego state of tolerance, patience, resilience and executive confidence, the manager transacts in a way pointing to the characteristics of an effective and efficient executive who is determined to make success a daily mantra. This parental component of personality always expresses perseverance and realistic belief in one’s own capabilities and resources. “Let us try to overcome the obstacles using our resources and plans” is the form of communication that the manager resorts to in interactional situations.

It has been observed that Parent Ego state take different structural and functional forms from the introjected system of feelings, attitudes and behavioral patterns and it can also be based on a fantasy of a parental figure that leads to the development of what is called a self-generated parent ego state or an internal saboteur (Zaletel, et.al, 2009; Erskine and Moursund, 1998).

It can be assumed that introjections, self-generations and/or fantasy figures produce same and/or different system of feelings, attitudes and behavioral patterns resulting in further differentiation at the structural and functional levels. Feelings, attitudes and behavior patterns of the same nature form a particular subdivision and different feelings, attitudes and behavior patterns make a different cleavage in the parental ego state.

It can be stated that in the dynamic functioning of the parent ego state, that is in response to multiple and a wide range of transactional stimuli and responses, the ego states get differentiated. A sort of structural and functional specialization comes into play when the individual starts confronting newer and newer stimuli and responses. The processing of new stimuli and the demands for a new set of responses result in the combination and the recombination of the parental data leading to the formation of the different sub-components that makes it possible for the parent ego state to function in the new situation. Specifically in response to the organizational stimuli and responses, the managers come to develop the sub-components.

2.2. ADULT EGO STATE AND THE SUB-COMPONENTS

Adult ego state is marked by the information processing activity that processes information received from different sources. This “thought” concept of life either functions in the resourceful way or it fails to function leading the person to think intelligently or unintelligently in his transactions with the world. The childhood experiences shape the way an adult comes to use his intelligence and cognitive activities.

Following the pattern of parental ego states, the structural and functional differentiation of the adult ego states fall into three productives and three unproductives Figs. 2(a) & 2 (b).

In the adult ego-state functioning, the subcomponents relevant and manifested in work behavior are the following:

2.2.1. ANALYTICAL EGO STATE (AE): In this ego state of functioning, the individual shows high amount of reasoning and componential analysis in his transactions that demand high information processing. In the analytical ego state of functioning, the mind is in a mode to receive a good amount of information from the organizational environment and transforms the same into productive channels of organizational functioning. “I will go through it in a detailed manner”, the manager would say when the organization receives a new proposal.

2.2.2. COORDINATED AND ORGANIZED EGO-STATE (CO): The manager swings into action in quick and controlled manner that ensures rich dividend for the organization. The coordination and the organization that the manager shows in varied activities are symptomatic of the organized and the controlled childhood life. The organization that the manager brings into executive functions of identifying and solving problems, allocating resources, dealing with employees is evident of a strong and robust ego state.

2.2.3. THE BIG-PICTURE EGO STATE (BP): Wide focusing and inclusive thinking imply that the manager is always able to have a big picture of the organization and/or the departmental activities. Big picture entails unified and wholistic view of the organization where the ultimate goal of the organization becomes the driving factor and the micro processes are never segregated from the main frame of the organizational processes. A manager with this ego state is capable of including the relevant and excluding the irrelevant in the scheme of activities. “Allow me to study its repercussions and after effects” is a saying that comes out of this ego state.

2.2.4. SUB-ANALYTICAL EGO STATE (SA): In this ego-state of functioning, the mind follows the commands of being unintelligent and illogical in management activities. Instead of actively processing the information, the mind actively and passively sidelines critical reflections and reflective thinking.

FIG.2 (B) ADULT EGO STATE SUB-COMPONENTS

The mind acts by the ill-formed thoughts that have its base in patterns of negative thinking. “We will disregard the weaknesses and we will implement the programme as early as possible”.

2.2.5. DISORGANISED/UNORGANISED EGO-STATE (DU): The main characteristic of this ego state is that the individual’s thoughts and behavior never centre on organizing and coordinating managerial activities in a systematic way. The loosening and the haphazard arrangement seen in physical, social, official and intellectual activities point to this particular ego state of functioning. The non-methodical style of functioning can be traced to childhood experiences which are largely in an atmosphere of clumsiness and awkward settings. The office room and the table they use often present a chaotic picture.

2.2.6. NARROW-FOCUSED AND RESTRICTED THINKING (NR): Besides the refusal to see the big picture, the manager acting in this ego state shows a constricted thinking without any flexibility to think on a larger horizon. Inability to use concepts that have wider applications in wider situations of management force the manager to comment, “I am unable to see the utility of this programme in our company or any other concerns”.

The adult ego state is a sort of complex ego state that processes multiple sources of information such that this level can be called an information processor. As an information processor, it deals with the transactional world in a highly methodical and systematic manner.

Stimulated and confronted by the reality and the activation of the cognitive processes, the adult ego states get formed in the individual in different ways. The mechanics of the formation of the adult ego state are dependent upon the nature of the cognitive resources and the processings and the nature of the parent and child data that prove to be functional/productive and dysfunctional/unproductive. Following the blending of the cognitive resources and processings with the parent and child data, the adult ego state takes on productive-unproductive forms. The ego state thus formed can be called the archaic adult ego state. Adult ego state can also get formed in the individual’s own confrontation with the reality where the individual is less influenced by the past data. This neo-adult ego state is purely derived from the individual’s own unique cognitive resources and the rich source of data provided by the environment. That is the adult ego state can have an archaic component and a neo component. The archaic adult ego state is wholly composed of the refinements and the modifications of the parental and child ego state data in the light of the confrontation with the reality. The neo-adult ego state is dependent upon the functioning of the cognitive resources.

The processings of the parental and child ego states data and the emergence of the cognitive resources and processings can result in the formation of two opposite adult ego states of productivity and unproductivity. Distinct and similar levels of adult ego states are acquired by the individual as the individual experiences and the transactional world of each individual differs. The archaic and the neo adult ego states are thus consequent to the interaction among new experiences registered by the individual, the parental and the child data and the evolving information processing activities of the cognitive system.

2.3. THE CHILD EGO STATE AND THE SUB-COMPONENTS

The child ego state is obviously characterized by feelings and emotions that dominated the childhood of an individual. Considered to be the “felt” concept of life, this ego state spring surprises in the form of laughter and cry. The different patterns of significant and eventful emotions that the child experienced in his relations with others programme his emotional life later in the life.

The structural and functional partitioning of Child Ego states yields six ego states, out of which there are three productives and three unproductives Figs.3 (a) & 3 (b). As such an adult worker may come to demonstrate or experience the following components in his work settings.

2.3.1. JOVIAL CHILD (JC): The ego state is manifested in happy and friendship situations of team work and cooperative endeavours. The manner shows the interest and participation in jovial activities of leisure and relaxation. The overwhelming joy and laughter are the predominant expressions in appropriate situations.

2.3.2. ADVENTUROUS AND INQUISITIVE EGO STATE (AI): A playful, experimenting and curiosity-driven childhood ensures an ego-state in a manager that is always innovative, risk-taking and achievement-oriented. Such managers, it may be noted are the ones who take the road less traveled by people implying that they may turn out to be intrapruners and creativity-minded. They are the ones who easily embrace change and become models for others in treading new paths.

2.3.3. SOCIABLE AND INTERPERSONAL (SI): This ego state of the childhood seeks out the company of others and tries to build a network of relations around work processes. Accomplishment of goals through others becomes the nature of the ego state that dominates in a particular transaction. The manager would say, for example, “let us gather together all the members and decide upon the problem”. Sociable and interpersonal ego state is underlined by the emotions for others that warmly receive the suggestions and requests of others. This ego state is reflected in friendship-seeking activities, expressions of gregariousness, affiliations and love.

2.3.4. LONELY AND SECLUDED EGO STATE (LS): Aloof and disinterested, the manager may say, “leave me alone I am just not interested” that is reflective of the child ego state. This ego state leads the manager towards a state of seclusion that results in less interaction with others and an unfriendly approach to subordinates and coworkers. The distance and the separation kept from other potential interacting units like individuals and groups leave a situation where the manager has to work in a rather solitary manner.

2.3.5. LAZY AND ABSENTEE MINDED (LA): Refusing or abstaining from duties and responsibilities can be built into a system of habits that are perpetuated by everyday events and reinforcements. Non-performance of work on a continuous basis leads to a state of negative reinforcement in which the subject comes to deriving extraneous pleasure and satisfaction. In this ego state the subject becomes an expert in devising hideous plans and ways so as to be idle most of the time and the idleness is come to be practiced in relation to the behavior of others for which no blame can be placed on the person. By all means the individual tries to avoid work so as to be

relieved of the pain of work. In TA interpretation, constant rejection and non-participation in childhood activities leads to the development of this ego state that gets unraveled in real life work settings.

2.3.6. COMPLAINING EGO STATE (CE): Frequent and regular airing and expression of complaints mark this ego state of the manager. In this pattern of compulsive and regular complaints about employees, co-workers, senior managers, organization and the world at large, the manager is trying to relieve his insecure and unsatisfactory childhood characterized by discontentment in the satisfaction of needs and wants.

The two path ways that lead to the partitioning of the child ego state are: (1) innate emotionality and (2) learned and learning emotionality. Each child has an innate emotionality that is unique to the child and the child can be placed at different points on the spectrum of emotions. The intensity and the type of emotions that the child experiences differ which is indicative of the differential felt life of individuals. The path way that starts from the external environment of social and interpersonal relations brings in new emotional decisions and the child learns to experience different types of emotions that gradually evolves and stabilizes into distinct emotional patterns.

In the dynamic emotional functioning, the differentiation of positive and negative emotions as experienced by the child forms the major subdivision of the child ego state and it corresponds to the traditional TA theory. Further subdivisions are made possible in the developmental period. As the child undergoes a variety of emotional experiences, the process of innate emotionality gets modified such that it is possible to differentiate between core affect and affective quality (Fernandez-Dols and Russell, 2003). The core affect of the person remains objectless whereas affective quality is experienced in relation to a stimulus. As the core affect becomes the foundational dynamics of all emotional experiences, the individual child learns to associate a specific emotion with a specific stimulus or a class of stimuli, thereby giving rise to categories of emotion linked to specific objects, events, issues places or persons. These linkages established between the internal emotional experiences, which in turn is derived from the core affect system, and the external world provide the individual with the whole emotional system.

In the continuing process of emotional experiences, which is based on the interaction between the core affect and the affective quality, individuals acquire different categories of emotion all of which are linked to the external world of happenings and persons. And as experiences mount and as the innate emotionality undergoes changes, different ego states centered on a specific emotion develop. The child consciously, subconsciously and unconsciously systematizes and differentiates the emotional experiences into different child ego states.

FIG.3 (A) CHILD EGO STATE SUB-COMPONENTS

FIG.3(B).CHILD EGO STATE SUB-COMPONENTS

2.4. PRINCIPLES OF EGO STATE STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL DIFFERENTIATION

1. Differentiation of ego state can take place beyond the traditional subdivisions in response to new transactional stimuli and responses.
2. As the amount of experiences pile up there exists a pressure on the ego states to make further subdivisions in response to the environment.
3. Encountering new stimuli hitherto unexperienced brings in the first driving force to partition the existing ego states.
4. The combination and the recombination of the data stored are the principal ways of ego state differentiation.
5. Similarity and dissimilarity of experiences force differentiation in the ego states.
6. Structural and functional differentiation follows an evolving pattern.

III. MIXED EGO STATE FUNCTIONING

In the arena of the ego state functioning, it is observed that an individual never manifests a single ego state or a single sub component. The complex and unpredictable organizational situation demands the expression of three ego states/subcomponents. The postulation of the mixed ego state functioning is possible because individuals are shown to be expressing patterns of emotions, different thought patterns and behaviors in complex situations of work. The activation of the ego state is contingent upon complex situations of work that demand a complex response that becomes adjustive. In the behavioral functioning of thought, motivation, emotion and acts, the individual may come to express any three subcomponents of parent, adult and child in an interactive manner. In a given behavioral functioning, one sub-component each from parent, adult and child surface in the present functioning leading to the emergence of thoughts, emotions and acts. A sample of behavioral functioning is constituted by cognition, emotion and behavioral acts of micro and macro nature. The three ego states which act in an interactive manner thus define a behavioral sample in a specific situation. It can be seen that there comes into experience 18 subcomponents of the three premier ego states, out of which three ego states dominate at a particular transaction. At the same time it is to be noted that the surfacing of the three ego states does not always take place as a major ego state or a specific component can dominate the behavioral functioning leaving little room for other subcomponents to get activated. As is evident there are 216 possible mixed ego states that can surface in behavioral functioning, that is 216 mixed ego states and three of the premier ego states surfacing independently or in combination in the conscious state of functioning.

The three subcomponents representing the three major ego states transact with the world in a complex and comprehensive manner. The specific sub-components can be diagnosed in macro and micro analysis of verbal and non-verbal expressions. Generally the three sub components are aligned with one another as the diagram shows, Fig 4. Here the cooperative and caring parent,

analytical adult ego state and the jovial child make a perfect blend that the transaction is done in the most fruitful, enjoyable and cooperative manner.

Unlike in contamination, in the mixed ego state, differentiation of data, that is layering of micro and macro messages bring about clear structural and functional differentiations. The internal and the external expressions of the three ego states are consequent to the processing of the multiple stimuli that produce an interactive response.

FIG.4.MIXED EGO STATE FUNCTIONING

IV ANALYSIS OF TRANSACTIONS

Transactions by the medium of spoken language (non-verbal transactions are also subjected to analysis) among the managers/workers in the organization provides the way to diagnose and use the ego state in a healthy manner in organizational functioning. Analysis of the verbal communication unravels the ego state functioning of the individuals engaged in conversation, discussions or negotiation.

In the organizational context the following form of productive and unproductive transactions can be deciphered based on the nature of the ego states. It may be stated that it is the orientation of communication tends to be productive or unproductive in the long run.

4.1. PRODUCTIVE TRANSACTION VS UNPRODUCTIVE TRANSACTION

In a productive transaction the individuals or groups transact from a productive ego state thereby directing the activity in a progressive manner whereas in an unproductive transaction, the individuals or groups transact from an unproductive ego state thereby directing the activity in a regressive manner.

It may be noted that in each category of ego state, that is Parent, Adult Child, there is the possibility of productive or unproductive transaction. That is individuals communicate from one of these ego states of PAC. As communication or transaction is a two way process, a total of four different communication forms may be identified.

A. Productive + + transaction

B. Productive + - transaction

C. Unproductive - - transaction

D. Unproductive - + transaction

In a productive + + transaction, the person A communicates from a productive ego state, that is intended to the productive ego state of the other person called B. B in turn communicates or replies in the intended productive ego state.

In a productive + - transaction the person A communicates from a productive ego state, that is intended to the productive ego state of the person B. B in turn communicates or replies from an unintended unproductive ego state.

In an unproductive - - transaction, the person A communicates from an unproductive ego state that is intended to the unproductive ego state of the other person B. B in turn communicates or replies in the same intended unproductive ego state.

In an unproductive - + transaction the person A communicates from an unproductive ego state and the message is intended to the unproductive ego state of the person B. B in turn communicates from a productive ego state and so we call it an unproductive -+ communication.

Moreover transactions can also originate from an interactive ego state of three subcomponents of PAC. The individual can initiate a transaction from three productive subcomponents or three unproductive subcomponents. The following mixed transactions can be observed:

A. Productive- Productive- Productive + + +

B. Productive- Productive- Unproductive + + -

C. Productive- Unproductive- Unproductive + - -

D. Unproductive- Unproductive- Unproductive - - -

E. Unproductive- Unproductive- Productive - - +

F. Unproductive- Productive- Productive - + +

The signs indicate that the target also responds in the same intended ego states. And it is not always likely that the target will respond in the intended ego state. The individual may respond in any combination of ego states out of the 216 that may result in the continuation or termination of the communication flow.

These are the typical patterns that occur in situations of interpersonal relations and most of the transactions may be identified using these forms. However, three other forms of transactions are also observed in organizational life.

In the blind form of communication, neutral, irrelevant or insignificant messages originate wherein the ego state is neither dominated by productive nor unproductive process. The purpose of this aimless communication is to while away the time or to fill the time interval with some contents. The initiator of the communication, that is A knowingly or unknowingly sends out a message that has no explicit character of productivity or unproductivity that usually evokes the same form of response from the target. And in unusual cases the target can generate a productive or unproductive response that may change the course of the communication.

In the double edge form of communication the recipient of the message is in a position to decode the message in either way of productive or unproductive nature. The target of the communication that is B picks up the productive or the unproductive tone or content of the message and responds and the sender may or may not continue the process of communication.

In the hidden form of transaction, the sender conceals the real purpose of communication from the target. Unlike the ulterior form of transaction, in hidden form the sender has an intention that he deliberately hides from the target so as to understand the target in a better way.

V SCRIPT AND SCHEMATIC ANALYSIS

In neuropsychological terms, scripts are neural formations or imprints that are formed in critical childhood periods that act as key drivers of personality. These neuropsychic structures which are formed in the interaction with others exert a pivotal influence on personality that the central nature of the personality is determined by the nature of the scripts.

In TA theory scripts are parental programmes formed in constant interaction between parents and the child. And upon continuous reinforcements of the programme or manner of behavior, the individual child automatically takes a decision along those lines leading to the formation of neural networks that remain firmly entrenched in personality (Allen and Allen, 1972). The childhood decisions following reinforced parental programming become the pivotal part of script which gets further corroborated as the individual grows older and gets into a larger circle of people who in all probability reinforce the original programme in self-perpetuating manner (Solomon, 2003).

Embedded with the personality functioning, scripts can be classified into superscripts and subscripts. Otherwise called life scripts, superscripts exercise a predominant influence on the personality of the individual in an all encompassing way and that it permeates the entire functioning. Superscripts are so called because of the complexity of the formation and the drastic and the dramatic influence that the script come to have over the life of a person.

Subscripts function independent of superscripts in that its domain of influence is entirely different. Subscripts are so called because of their limited influence on the activities of the person. The individuals can be under the influence of a single superscript whereas many subscripts can be possessed by the individual. The nature of the relation between superscripts and subscripts are shown diagrammatically Fig.5.

The criteria to differentiate superscripts and subscripts are (a) the number of messages received from different sources (b) the frequency with which the messages are registered on the implicit memory of the person (c) the intensity of emotion felt by the person (d) the strength of the message such that strong and loaded messages have greater impact and greater depth and weak messages have lesser impact and lesser depth (e) the force with which messages are transmitted such that messages with greater force have greater scope and application value and messages with lesser force have lesser scope and lesser application value (the difference between strength and force is that the former is tied to the person from whom the message originates and the latter to the relational nature of the message, which is already in the person in undefined ways).

As “unconscious systems of psychological organization” (Erskine, 2009) scripts are dynamic forces with cognitive, affective, motivational and behavioral arenas. In the cognitive level verbal and non-verbal messages are registered in memory and they continue to determine the life of a person. Messages are registered with emotions of any type like fear, anxiety, rejection, acceptance, etc. As driving forces of neuropsychic systems, scripts move and drive the behavior of the individual in a specific path.

The psychological organization of scripts can be further corroborated by script systems and script matrices. Script system constitutes a pattern of interrelationships among cognitive, affective and motivational components that are formed in the process of script transference leading to

FIG.5.THE NATURE AND THE RELATION BETWEEN SUPERSCRIPTS AND SUBSCRIPTS

the operationalization of core beliefs, overt behaviors, fantasies, obsessions, internal physical reactions and reinforcing memories (O'Reilly-Knapp and Erskine 2010).

The diagram illustrates the psychological organization of the scripts Fig.6. Scripts take on psychological organization in that the cognitive, motivational, affective and behavioral components take on a unifying character that the psychological processes become interconnected and interrelated. The script messages transferred are thus characterized by cognitive, affective, motivational and behavioral realms that become deeply entrenched in the intra psychic life of a person.

Relying upon the idea of script matrices, the complexity formation superscripts can be understood. The direct and indirect sources of scripts as understood by TA theorists are the parents and significant others. Besides these influences, scripts can also take their origin from social and interpersonal situations that the individual encounters in daily activities. In his ego-state matrix theory, Steiner(1971) unravels the nature of the script matrices. The complexity of the messages that the child receives and the way it is transformed into an embedded script qualifies it as life script/super script. The complexity is to be understood in relation to the multiple messages of the same nature received from the same source in repeated instances and also similar messages received from other significant persons and social situations. Moreover, complexity also rests with the use of images and meta languages in the formation of scripts. Images and visualizations add to the extensiveness and intensity of scripts that make it a superscript over period of time. The use of images and visualizations make the formation of scripts easy and quick.

The parental messages/injunctions/any forms of communication are cognitive that it affects the thought processes of the child, thereby generating a new system of thought that gives a specific direction to life. The generated thought is converted into a decision that gradually becomes an implicit memory. The message that already carries with it an affective tone generates a specific emotion that is in tune with the innate emotionality and the learned/conditioned emotional experiences of the individual child. The motivating component of the communication directs the individual to a specific group of behaviors. And these intrapsychic changes are expressed in overt behaviors.

FIG.6.THE FORMATION OF THE SCRIPT

Building upon the original theory of scripts, TA theorists have evolved the idea of script matrix that consist of values, don't injunctions and here's how norms of behavior (Dusay, 1977). Scripts thus formed of injunctions and decisions evolve into script matrices Script matrices are parental programming that involves the messages received from different persons, for example, father and mother, in different situations and experiences which later get elaborated in respective situations of life including the organizational life. Some of the scripts that managers/workers formulate or solidify as they become part of an organization involve the following:

“Never to be a leader”

“Do not communicate in group”

“Do not work hard”

“Spend the time in gossip”

“Be anti-management”

The initial messages received from parents/significant others take these behavioral forms in organizational settings that become a stable aspect of work behavior.

A related cognitive structure that has special significance in the area of change and development is schema. Schemata are cognitive structures, generalized across situations, which help the person interpret events, situations or other significant cluster of stimuli (Fiske, 2000). Schemata are “data reduction devices” providing economy of information processing to individuals engaged in the task of interpreting and giving meaning to stimulus array. In the face of an “overwhelming flow of sensations” that involves events, issues or other situations, schemata function as templates to give meaning to events (Bartunek and Moch, 1987).

Further, schemata are cognitive structures of knowledge of procedures or facts. And that the interrelationships formed around a specific procedure or concept resulting in the formation of a new schema. Schemata are either self-generated or second-hand nature (Fiske, 2000). Individual’s own experiences and the abstractions done generate a schema. An organized system of relations learned from others becomes a second-hand schema. Regardless of its origin, schemata help the individual to interpret and deal with the world in a quick, easy and methodical manner.

Unlike scripts, schemata have no unconscious nature and the individual can easily identify and name the schema that influences his behavior. The similarity between scripts and schemata is that both act as a sort of ready-recokner in interactions with the environment and they provide the individual with short-cut keys to carry out a scheme of behavior. The types of schemata studied include person schemata, event schemata, institutional schemata, etc.

Organizational schemata are cognitive structures formed to interpret and understand the organizational processes. Organizational schemata that are shared by organizational members enable them to interpret the organizational processes in a similar manner as the situation demands. The link between the operation of organizational schemata and behavior, more particularly change and development is amply illustrated in

OD literature (for example, Tichy and Nisberg, 1976) which means that successful planned organizational change and development makes use of schematic change as an effective change strategy (Bartunek and Moch, 1987).

Bartunek and Moch (1987) have shown the successful use of schemata at three levels of change, that is first order change makes use of the existing schemata to bring about more effective changes in specified area, second-order change involves replacing the existing schemata with a new schemata as a new method of work is introduced in the organization and third-order change involves more self-generated schemata as the organizational members decide for themselves in an appropriate situation of choice.

Some of the organizational schemata relevant in the area of organizational change and development include the following: Quality improvement schemata, Technology upgradation schemata, Automation schemata, Task restructuring schemata, Communication schemata, Project implementation schemata, Decision making schemata, Interpersonal schemata, etc.

VI ORGANIZATIONAL POSITIONS AND OKAYNESS

Even though life position is viewed as defining the total direction that an individual perceives or the overall life destiny, it is not always the case because it changes in accordance with the situation. That is life position cannot be considered as a static position but it is a dynamic position that shows variation in the positive direction or in the negative direction. Just as an individual holds a life position, an individual joining an organization comes to hold an organizational position in terms of the okayness. White (1994) speaks of a surface life position that is temporary, reactive and situational and a character position that is more basic and stable across many situations. Accordingly White (1994) has added four more positions with reference to okayness besides the usual four OK positions.

Over and above the okayness felt and thought by individuals, other levels of okayness in organizations can be identified. Okayness as an individual organizational position connotes the nature of interpersonal relationships in relation to the state of individual predisposition. Basically, okayness springs from individual tendencies and it is rooted in the early childhood, interpersonal and social experiences. In the organizational context, therefore okayness is also to be studied in collectivity that is individuals who share the same okayness and individuals who do not share the same okayness. Accordingly the following levels of okayness may be deciphered in organizational relationships Table 1.

TABLE 1.DIFFERENT OKAYNESS IN RELATION TO GROUPS AND ORGANIZATIONS

<p>Individual vs Group</p> <p>I' m OK They 're OK</p> <p>I' m not OK They 're OK</p> <p>I' m OK They 're not OK</p> <p>I' m not OK They 're not OK</p>	<p>Group vs Group</p> <p>We 're OK, They 're OK</p> <p>We 're not OK, They 're OK</p> <p>We 're OK, They 're not OK</p> <p>We 're not OK, They 're not OK</p>
<p>Group vs Organization</p> <p>We as a group 're OK They as other groups 're OK</p> <p>We as a group 're not OK They as other groups 're OK</p> <p>We as a group 're not OK They as other groups 're OK</p> <p>We as a group 're not OK They as other groups 're not OK</p>	<p>Organization vs Organization</p> <p>We as an organization 're OK They as another organization 're OK</p> <p>We as an organization 're not OK They as another organization 're OK</p> <p>We as an organization 're OK They as another organization 're not OK</p> <p>We as an organization 're not OK They as another organization 're not OK</p>

The collective okayness has its roots in the social psychological processes of group functioning. Firstly, individuals join an organization and subsequently a group with a life position that gets changed in group interactions. Secondly, if majority of the members hold okayness, the minority may also tend to move in the direction of okayness if other situational processes are favorable and vice versa. Thirdly, the more cohesive, united and goal-directed, the members are okayness easily change in the positive direction. Finally, interventions initiated in the group functioning can tilt the okayness along the intended lines.

In the individual vs. group okayness, leaders come to be tested for their efficiency and effectiveness. The most unfavorable scenarios are that the leaders are not OK and both the leaders and the followers are not OK. In this situation, the group turns into a highly dysfunctional one making the members discontented, non-cooperative and rebellious.

Group vs. group okayness is expressed in intergroup activities of discussion, negotiation, decision-making, goal-achievement and related organizational activities.

Group vs. organisation okayness becomes critical when a group comes to face- to-face with the organization as a whole or when a group confronts the top management. The direction of

activities is primarily dependent upon the okayness position of the powerful unit which means that if the powerful unit is ok, the activities tend to take a favorable turn.

The relevance of organizational vs. organizational okayness is in inter-organizational relationships like financial cooperation, joint ventures, transfer of technology and personnel and sharing of information and knowledge.

VII GAMES MANAGERS/WORKERS PLAY

As stereotypical, repetitive and gripping patterns of behavior, games are played by individuals in a variety of situations of life including the organization. In the hideous nature of games individual enact/ reenact a well programmed repetitive mode of behavior in order to assert in a negative way an underlying programme that now seeks release and satisfaction.

As a transferential phenomena based on an individual script, games represent an unconscious desire to bring to the present life the past programmed data, which is expressed in disguised form (Widdowson, 2010). The challenging and demanding organizational context provide the managers/workers with a field to reenact the script rooted in the intrapsychic processes. The moves and the expected countermoves are designed to reinforce the past so as to derive an ulterior psychic satisfaction of being sunk. Games are overly behavioral in character as the player resorts to a sequence of recurring manifested activities in which there is an ulterior satisfaction. The different games played by managers/workers are explained.

7.1. I TOLD YOU SO

This game is played to conceal one's inferiority complexes in that managers in-charge of departments/projects/plans/other specific activities come out with this accusation whenever the activity fails to materialize. And we call it a game played by the manager because if we trace the entire sequence of activities from start to finish, we can identify his explicit and implicit attempts to scuttle the activity from different sides. The moment the activity fails, the manager makes every attempt to justify it citing well conceived excuses, intellectual arguments and dubious reasoning which may not have a real basis. Managers experiencing deep seated feelings of inadequacy, inferiority and incompetency execute this game so as to derive the payoffs in the form of being limited to his position and related ones.

7.2. The Procastinator

The procrastinator manager is one who procrastinates decisions, plans or any matter that needs to be executed with urgency on silly and irrelevant grounds. If we examine the behavior of this manager, it can be readily seen that no results or outcomes come forward from this manager who is playing this game because of severe lack of confidence in oneself, high amount of experienced anxiety and one who is not sure of himself.

7.3. THE BENEVOLENT MANAGER

In this game play, the manager is too good and concerned and interested in the lives and works of others, especially subordinates and coworkers with whom he is constantly interacting in the pursuit of organizational and individual goals. This goody-goody manager is actually extremely benevolent in his dealings that he never wants to hear criticism from others and that he never antagonizes others. The underlying dynamics of this game is the weak-hearted and servile attitude of the manager. And this motivates him to behave to avoid displeasure from others in all instances of encounter. The manager wants to live in a façade of “everything is alright” when in fact he experiences deep insecurity in his work and life.

7.4. THE ANGRY AND THE TENSED MAN

Opposed to the benevolent manager, the angry and the tensed always sends out signals of anger, dissatisfaction and tension. This manager cannot be easily approached by others just because of his anger and tension-frame of behavior. In a surreptitious way, by this frame of behavior, the manager tries to avoid meeting serious and well meaning co-workers who may pose a threat to his position and power. The demonstration of anger and tension is always to keep a safe and comfortable distance from others and by this behavior the manager constructs a negative world of his own where he cannot be touched by others.

7.5. THE BUSY MANAGER

The busy manager never finds time for others or to do important tasks. Instead he is always busy with irrelevant and insignificant matters that have no outcome relation. This game is sequentially enacted to cover up incompetency, fear of failure and an instinctual like desire to halt progress in the working of the organization. By being busy, the work hours is “effectively” spent in the eyes of others but achieves nothing in the real sense. The constant distraction to which the manager pushes himself creates a sort of mental screen that wards off productive thoughts from the mind, rendering the manager busy and distracted internally and externally. The payoff that the manager derives from this game is that he is not an effective executive.

7.6. THE WORKAHOLIC MANAGER

Workaholic manager is a slave to work in that he continuously and constantly does and repeats the same or different work even when it is not necessary. In a monotonous and self-centered manner the manager “attends to” work on an average of 15 to 17 hours a day and at the end emerges from the workdesk tired and discontented, having achieved nothing. The manager addicted to “work” does nothing in a substantial manner that can be measured in concrete outcomes. In a compulsive manner, he goes through heaps of files again and again or he goes through the cycle of plan and changes that uncovers certain unconscious tendencies of fixation, rigidity or idiotic experiences that remain unresolved. The reward that the manager earns from this game is that of “being intelligent and committed”.

VIII A TA MODEL OF ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE AND DEVELOPMENT

A basic therapeutic assumption of TA is that the wound programmes that the individual carries can be unwound and new healthy programmes can be learned or incorporated by the individual. The wrong or unhealthy “mental software” installed early in life can be uninstalled in a deliberate and conscious way and new healthy and productive mental software is to be installed that overhauls the life of the individual once the programme becomes active or once the individual assimilates the new script. The willingness, the desire and the assumption of responsibility to change life underlies another basic principle of TA therapy.

Fig.7. A TA Model of Organizational Change and Development

In the light of the important concepts discussed, a TA model of organizational change and development may be postulated. The Fig.7 explains the important variables and the relations that exist among them that lead to a productive organizational life.

In the diagnosis of the ego states the individual manager/worker is to be taught the nature of different ego states that surface in interpersonal interactions by the means of verbal and non-verbal expressions. The development of self-awareness and insight into one's own ego states as and when they surface in the conscious mind is the key to change the ego state and transact with others in an appropriate manner so as to derive mutual benefits from the relationships. In the development of self-awareness of ego states, the individual comes to have control over different subcomponents of ego that enable him to execute a suitable transaction.

Ego state analysis involves analysis of the transactions that can be productive ++, productive +- unproductive - - unproductive -+. The communication participants are to have sound knowledge into the changing mode of productive and unproductive transactions. This knowledge prevents a breakdown in communication or it enables the leaders to influence the transaction of others in the desired manner.

Another component of the model is the analysis of scripts and schemata. Maladaptive and maladjustive scripts and schemata that the individual uses in his life are to be identified. The therapeutic help that can be rendered by an expert in the field is a way to erase unhealthy scripts and imprint healthy scripts. The analysis of the script matrix calls for thorough examination into the working of the ego states of the individual.

Bartunek and Moch (1987) have identified a number of ways of identifying schemata that organizational participants come to have. Analysing the language, causing a change in worker's routine, conduct of group reflections in which members express and describe the events and the way they understand them and analysis of collages and biographies go a long way in unraveling the schemata that are either facilitative or inhibitive in the arena of organizational functioning.

Development of healthy scripts and appropriate schemata results in a manifold increase in the productivity of the workforce.

The proper understanding of the organizational positions in relation to okayness leads to the development of constructive relationships.

Game analysis is another significant component of the TA model of change and development. Many a time it becomes difficult for the individual player to understand the game in to which they have fallen or from which they cannot escape. Because the games played go unnoticed or not understood by the players themselves the intervention of an expert is the ideal way of curing the ills that afflict the participants.

IX CONCLUSIONS

As is evident organizational change and development is an area that is complex and in that sense change and development becomes almost impossible without understanding the behavioral

processes. The dynamic nature and the application value of TA theory can be readily seen in the understanding and interpretation of organizational processes. TA theory goes a long way in activating and facilitating the change and development processes in organizations. The TA derivatives are considered to be of great practical value to an OD consultant.

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NURSE ENGAGEMENT IN INDIAN HEALTH CARE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

The emphasis on delivering high-quality healthcare has increased significantly in recent years. Health care is an extraordinarily people-centric industry and as caregivers and organization keepers, nurses represent the key "people factor" in improving and controlling healthcare quality. A critical element of successful health care organization, in the current challenging environment, is the ability to develop and sustain high levels of employee engagement, especially the nurses, in shaping the work environment and team governance. This study is undertaken to gain a more in-depth understanding of employee engagement among nurses. Data were collected primarily through interviews from one hundred and twenty nurses working with three leading hospital in Hyderabad and Secunderabad. The results showed that 73 percent of nurses were actively engaged, 19 percent were disengaged and 8 percent were actively disengaged, which is similar in healthcare industries across countries. Nurses, while indicating various drivers of engagement, strongly believed that organizations should infuse their mission and core values throughout all aspects of their operations to improve engagement. It is concluded that creating a culture of Engagement can make organizations as "destination workplace" and a more profitable — and hospitable — organization.

KEYWORDS: *Employee Engagement, Healthcare Industry, Healthcare Quality, Nursing.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality of care, safety and patient satisfaction are obvious priorities to the Indian healthcare industry which has become a major focus of public policy in the recent times. Health care

organizations are challenged to achieve this goal, operating amid highly complex environments. In achieving these, apart from research, technology and governance, the most basic consideration is people who play a significant role. Performing dual roles as caregivers and organization "keepers", nurses represent the key "people factor" in improving and controlling healthcare quality.

Nursing is a unique profession in which compassion, knowledge, skill and critical thinking are harmoniously blended. Nurses have the opportunity and privilege to provide holistic care by creating intimate connections by engaging personally with every patient, every day. This personal aspect of nursing care empowers nurses to tend to the emotional and personal needs of the patient by purposefully taking steps to begin building a relationship even before administering clinical care. This makes a positive difference in the quality of care delivered. It creates a more meaningful and valuable hospital experience for the patient and result in increased satisfaction for both parties. In many a case, the emotional impact may last well after discharge. As a result, nurses are considered as the key connecting point through which systems, patients, and physicians work together to not only identify and prevent potential medical errors but also to improve the overall quality of services provided and ultimately, improving the bottom line.

Nurses are known as dedicated professionals who work tirelessly for their patients. However, after years of working, witnessing and participating in miraculous and life-altering events of patients, nurses tend to experience significant stress. They commonly become desensitized to situations and as a result become complacent about their roles and duties. Most of them feel distanced from their work and become far less connected to their patients and colleagues. Since, healthcare quality is a team-dependent variable, nurses' connectivity, physically and emotionally, to their work and organization is of crucial importance. The healthcare industry identified and actively adopted an innovative solution to this issue by 'ENGAGING' nurses which allows them to reconnect with each patient and the organization. Employee Engagement leads to a variety of great things for an organization and its employees compelling the industry to build it. The incorporation of nurse engagement has demonstrated improvements in many areas affecting nursing including satisfaction; loyalty; and pride in the organization, recommending it to others for care or to work, especially in a time when there is high staff turnover, extreme economic pressures and an unpredictable nursing job market. This study is specifically aimed at getting conceptual clarity about employee engagement among nurses by understanding the theoretical underpinning from myriad studies about nurse engagement and providing empirical direction for future research.

2. EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AMONG NURSES

Employee Engagement is the central issue for 21st century professionals and specifically for nurses in the health care industry. Conceptualized by psychologist William A Kahn and developed by a succession of management and behavioral thinkers, Employee Engagement is a positive, fulfilling state of mind about work and organization that is characterized by vigour, dedication and absorption. It is the extent to which employees are motivated to contribute to organizational success, and are willing to apply discretionary effort (extra time, brainpower and effort) to accomplish the tasks that are important to the achievement of organizational goals

(Kanexa, 2006). The Concept rapidly gained widespread recognition and endorsement as it moved beyond HR discussion and concepts into main stream strategic and operational management. The driving force behind the popularity of employee engagement is the positive consequences that the concept can bring into the organizations. Empirical research has repeatedly demonstrated that the impact of engagement can manifest itself through productivity and organizational performance, outcomes for customers of the organization, employee retention rates, organizational culture, and advocacy of the organization and its external image. An organization can be a competitive market leader and a driving force in its industry if it has a team of employees who are truly engaged.

Extensive research by Gallup Organization, an international US based consultancy firm, that has been studying employee engagement across the globe over the years, found that nurse engagement is the key factor for quality in healthcare industry. They reported a strong link between employee engagement and patient satisfaction: Developing their research on the accepted principle: if employees are happy and feeling secure in a job, it's easier for them to focus on the challenge of taking care of doctors and patients, they found that as organizations improve their engagement levels, there is a positive linear relationship with growth in patient satisfaction and loyalty.

Purdue University researchers also found a direct link between nurse satisfaction and patient satisfaction and between patient satisfaction and financial performance. The study revealed that the outcomes of engagement of nurses are higher levels of personal initiatives that are contagious, decreased hospital mortality rates and significantly higher financial profitability of organizations.

Kalisch et al. conducted a study looking at an intervention to increase teamwork and staff engagement on a nursing unit and their results showed that improved teamwork and staff engagement was influential in improving patient outcomes and patient satisfaction. They strongly opine that what hospitals do for their employees, nurses in particular, is directly related to how well it is doing on quality measures.

Research indicates unequivocally that Employee Engagement also plays a major role in achieving the dual goals of cost reduction and improved productivity. It is a proven, cost-effective way to attract and retain motivated nurses and increase their morale. Howell (2003) offered that engagement can support five business objectives, those being "attracting the right people with the right skills, retaining employees, developing their skills and capabilities in a focused way, successfully managing change and motivating them to support the organization's business direction. Thus, efforts to increase engagement have become a lifeline for hospitals, especially as economic concerns and competition for top talent increased.

Many hospitals have opted to reduce the size of their workforce to save costs to address economic concerns. Researchers found that the commitment and emotional involvement of the nurses is more important than their numbers. Maszal et al. (2002) reported that highly engaged employees consistently speak positively about where they work to the outsiders, demonstrate behavior that shows a desire to be part of the group, and express willingness to go above and

beyond the call of duty in their contributions to the organization. Engagement addresses the issue of low staffing problems and makes the organizations survive the rocky environment.

Nurses are the core of the patient care team and the critical element of successful organizations is the ability to develop and sustain high levels of nurse engagement. Many hospitals are actively engaging nurses through involvement, while ensuring they understand the processes and tools. This has made a positive difference in the quality of care that is delivered. It is imperative for any industry, more so for health care industry, to aspire for engaged employees, who are psychologically committed to their jobs and workplaces and go beyond their job expectations to fulfill their organization's mission. Nurse Engagement is No. 1 Quality Priority

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research study is exploratory in nature with a combination of literature review and in depth interviews as data collection methods. First, for the secondary data, in keeping with accepted practice, various research articles and books were reviewed to understand the broad area of Employee Engagement. Primary data was collected through In-depth interviews, a qualitative research technique that involves conducting intensive individual interviews with respondents to explore their thoughts and behaviors on a particular idea, program, or situation. The chief advantage of in-depth interviews is that they provide much more detailed information than what is available through other data collection methods, such as surveys. They also may provide a more relaxed atmosphere in which to collect information— people may feel more comfortable having a conversation with you about their program as opposed to filling out a survey.

One hundred and twenty (120) in-depth interviews were conducted on nurses working with three leading hospital in Hyderabad and Secunderabad who volunteered to participate. The respondents were asked about their knowledge, experiences and expectations related to Employee Engagement programs and about any changes they perceive in themselves as a result of their involvement in the program. The interviews were planned and conducted at the convenience of participants. Each interview lasted about 30 minutes. While conducting the interviews, the interviewee was made comfortable and interested in the topic. Efforts were also made to use effective interview techniques, such as avoiding yes/no and leading questions, using appropriate body language, and keeping personal opinions in check to elicit detailed and rich data. Due to confidentiality reasons, the names of the participants and the organizations have been kept anonymous. The data was then systematically analyzed using SPSS (v.17).

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The results show that 73 percent of surveyed nurses were actively engaged, 19 percent were disengaged and 8 percent were actively disengaged. Engaged nurses (73%) were highly satisfied, more loyal and had pride in their organizations. They have good attitudes about the organization and would recommend it as a place to work.

The remaining 27 percent of nurses are putting forth minimal effort, doing just enough to keep their jobs. According to Gallup research, disengaged and actively disengaged workers are the excuse-makers of the organization. They tend to stir things up and blame others for problems.

This combined group is a drain on the bottom line of the organization. Not surprisingly, according to many studies, this pattern of engagement levels is mirrored in healthcare industry across countries.

Nurses indicated the following as important and perceived them as strong drivers of engagement - an opportunity to influence policies and decisions affecting their work; receiving recognition; a balance of work-life responsibilities; organizational, managerial and collegial trust; members of the work group asking for employee opinions; and leaders listening to employees. Many a nurse opined that successful nurse engagement requires leadership support. Laschinger and Leiter (2006) concluded in their study that leadership is a driving force that strongly influences the degree of engagement. Further, Luther et al.(2002) in their research felt that organizations need to build a culture that values nurses' engagement in all aspects of the initiatives that affect their work environment requires support and enthusiasm from the organizations' leaders at all levels.

It is found that forty percent (40 %) of nurses did not fully understand the impetus and rationale behind the engagement initiatives taken up by the organizations. For engagement to happen, nurses need to be familiar with the activities and more importantly at an early stage itself. This is reiterated in the research conducted by Gawlinski (2008); Kalisch, Curley, & Stefanov (2007), where they found that successful engagement of nurses require an early involvement and commitment to the process. Involvement helps increase creativity and active participation (Gawlinski, 2008). Therefore, nurses should strive to fully understand that it is extremely important to get it right from the start.

Nurses strongly believe that organizations should infuse their mission and core values throughout all aspects of their operations to improve their engagement. Engagement can be increased by explicitly relating all decisions to the furtherance of organization's mission. According to the Gallop Organization, Employee Engagement is higher at religious hospitals, than at non-religious hospitals, as their employees have a stronger sense of commitment to their jobs. The basis for this is more about the institutional differences than differences in the type of employee. Religious hospitals put their mission and values into practice by communicating them and encouraging positive employee behaviors consistent with the values. The benefits are obvious - if employees feel it is their mission to treat each other well, they will also extend that behavior to patients and their families. Health care organizations should leverage this strength by placing more emphasis on their missions and operationalizing it. In fact, this finding can guide in improving employee engagement in any industry.

Nurses felt that organizations should create a culture of engagement which invites its members to participate in their work in ways that are meaningful to them as individuals. The added benefit is support and respect for achieving their own personal goals and affirming individual values, which could in turn result in greater satisfaction with their work environment. Organizations should focus on valuing and empowering its members by forming partnerships in which employees feel satisfied and engaged and creating an environment in which employee develops emotional bonds with colleagues and the organization (Antoinette Bargagliotti, 2011). This expectation empowers and compels the nurse to more responsible member of the organization.

Nurses emphasized the need for organizations to provide several resources to improve teamwork both within units and interdepartmentally to provide the best quality of care to patients. This is in tune with the findings of Kalisch et al. (2007); Triolo, Hansen, Kazzaz, Chung, & Dobbs (2002) who felt that teamwork improves quality of care, increases job satisfaction, enhances patient safety and provides greater patient satisfaction, thus leading to increased employee engagement. When the multidisciplinary team is engaged and teamwork is visibly enacted, it also improves communication, improves processes, reduces error and prevents adverse events (McFerran, Nunes, Pucci, & Zuniga, 2005).

5. CONCLUSION

The credibility of the healthcare system is on the quality of the service offered. It is beyond doubt that nurses are key people in delivering it. A critical element of successful health care organization is the ability to develop and sustain high levels of employee engagement, especially the nurses, in shaping the work environment and team governance. Many organizations in this brave new world of healthcare are stepping up to the challenge and are experimenting with new ways of engaging their nurses by implementing practices that heighten job autonomy and ownership. Creating a culture of Engagement can make them as "destination workplace" and a more profitable — and hospitable — organization.

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WORKING TOWARDS ECO-SOCIAL JUSTICE: REFLECTIONS ON AN INTERNATIONAL, CROSS-INSTITUTIONAL SOCIAL WORK COLLABORATION

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ABSTRACT

The environmental challenges facing the globe are becoming increasingly clear. As the social implications of these challenges for individuals, communities and societies also become clearer, professions such as social work must begin to explore and clarify their role in responding to issues of ecological, as well as social, justice. In November 2011 an international conference on the theme of 'Eco-social Justice' was held at the De Paul Institute of Science and Technology (DIST), in Kerala, India. This conference was one outcome of a developing collaboration between the social work departments of DIST and James Cook University (JCU) in Australia.

This paper reflects on the nature of this collaborative enterprise, with a particular focus on how such international, cross-institutional partnerships may represent an important strategy in moving the global social work profession towards a more effective engagement with issues of eco-social justice. Partnership and collaboration has traditionally been an important dimension of social work education and practice, but have also emerged as key elements of effective environmental and sustainability education. Drawing these various elements together, the DIST-JCU collaboration serves as an example of the ways in which effective international partnerships may contribute to the quest for eco-social justice.

KEYWORDS: *social work; collaboration; eco-social justice; global/international.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Across the globe, the scale and ramifications of the emerging environmental crisis are being recognised. Report after report document both the scientific evidence and the projected physical and social impacts of the unfolding disaster (see, for example, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2007). Issues relating to pollution, energy, biodiversity, land degradation, deforestation and climate change, amongst others, have all been identified as having significant environmental and social consequences in countries around the world, including India and Australia (Parikh & Parikh, 2002; Nagdeve, 2002; Department of Climate Change and Energy Efficiency, 2011; Garnaut, 2011; Preston & Jones, 2006). The nature of the emerging environmental problems also highlight the fact that the most dramatic negative impacts of these issues are falling, and will continue to fall, on those individuals, communities and societies that are already amongst the most disadvantaged and marginalised (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

The inevitable consequence of this realisation is that the dualistic thinking which has traditionally characterised social work as a profession, whereby issues pertaining to social justice were seen as separate from and unrelated to issues of the natural environment, has been revealed as woefully inadequate and in need of urgent revision (Besthorn, 2000; Coates, 2003; Jones, 2008). A number of authors and activists have drawn our attention to the significance of the concepts of environmental and ecological justice and their relevance for social work as a profession (Hillman, 2002; Keefe, 2003; Rogge, 2008). Recognition of the interdependency and interrelationship that exists between notions of social and environmental justice suggests that a synthesised concept that signals the end of the human-nature binary approach might now be required.

A conflation of 'ecological' and 'social', the term eco-social is a shorthand way of indicating issues or approaches where the traditional human-nature dichotomy is rejected and explicit recognition is given to the interrelatedness and interdependence between humans and the non-human world. An eco-social orientation would argue that both the ecological and the social are inextricably related and cannot be considered in isolation from one another. Eco-social justice thereby emerges as a desirable goal for a social work profession that recognises this interdependence and utilises it as a focal point for action to produce change (Jones, 2012).

Striving for eco-social justice may represent a new agenda for social work as a profession, but many of the traditional approaches, models and strategies that have been employed in the past are equally valid and useful as we move into this uncertain future. Developing partnerships and collaborations, for example, has long been a feature of social work practice and education (Graham & Barter, 1999). Collaborative approaches have also emerged as crucial to the developing practices of eco-activism, environmental education and education for sustainability (Austin, 2004). Such partnerships at the local level will be an important strategy for an eco-

socially oriented social work. However, in the same manner that environmental issues such as climate change and pollution transcend national boundaries, collaborative efforts directed towards achieving eco-social justice should also look for opportunities to cross borders and boundaries to build meaningful partnerships.

The emerging partnership between the social work departments at the De Paul Institute of Science and Technology, in Kerala, India, and James Cook University in Queensland, Australia, represents an example of both achievement and potential in the development of collaborative relationships with an eco-social justice orientation. Reflecting on the nature of this collaboration, in the light of an understanding both of social work's relationship to environmental issues and the lessons to be learned from collaborative activities in both social work and environmental education movements, highlights the possibility that such collaborations may be a significant strategy for working towards eco-social justice.

2. SOCIAL WORK AND THE ECOLOGICAL CHALLENGE

The degree to which social work as a profession has neglected and marginalised issues pertaining to the natural environment and its relationship to human wellbeing has now been well documented (see, for example, Coates, 2003; McKinnon, 2008; Molyneux, 2010; Zapf, 2010). A recent review of Australian social work courses and both Australian and international social work journals revealed a paucity of material relating directly to ecology and the natural environment (Jones, 2011). This is despite the continuing influence of the person-in-environment perspective and the existence of a deep interest in (social) ecological approaches to social work practice (Gitterman & Germain, 2008; Saleeby, 2004). Moving from the almost exclusively social orientation of these theoretical foundations to an approach that recognises and embraces the natural environment and broader conceptualisations of ecology has been a slow and fitful process.

However, clear signs are emerging that the profession is beginning to engage with these issues and to explore the ways in which an expanded ecological perspective may contribute to both practice and education. Increasing numbers of relevant journal articles are beginning to appear and significant publications are emerging that will almost inevitably draw greater attention to this important issue (see, for example, Kemp, 2011; Gray, Coates & Hetherington, 2012; Dominelli, 2012). Kemp's assessment of the current state of play is both accurate and optimistic:

Reviewing the profession's environmental record leaves me chagrined, but also heartened. Too little progress has been made in closing the intransigent gap between social work's expressed commitment to the contexts of human experience and its actual investment in environmental practice and research. Nonetheless, the 'green shoots' of renewed interest in environmental issues and interventions are clearly identifiable, and I am cautiously optimistic that environmental concerns are at last gaining real traction in the profession (2011, pp. 1205).

However this author also sounds an important note of caution, warning that without systematic efforts these 'green shoots' will not flourish and social work as a profession will miss the opportunity to make a meaningful contribution to addressing the environmental crisis and its social consequences. Significantly, Kemp (2011) argues that such systematic efforts must

include developing partnerships, forging alliances and engaging in collaborations across a range of boundaries. In this respect social work as a profession is well placed to draw on traditional approaches to practice and education, as well as efforts in the field of environmental education, where the importance of such collaborative efforts has often been recognised and promoted.

3. COLLABORATIONS AND PARTNERSHIPS

In social work, collaborations and partnerships are seen as integral dimensions of both practice and education. Graham & Barter (1999) reviewed the existence of collaboration as a ubiquitous theoretical perspective within social work, tracing examples back as far as the 1920's, and argued that the concept of collaboration could be used as a unifying method for all fields of social work practice. They noted that

...collaboration captures the need for professions, agencies, communities, and client systems to work differently – to begin pooling resources, linking and allying with one another in efforts to rethink current practices, and to develop innovative, new responses to rapidly changing social problems. (Graham & Barter, 1999, pp. 6)

Examples of the use of collaborative approaches in practice settings are common, but still noteworthy for their articulation of the benefits which may flow from such strategies. Moses (1974), for example, writing almost four decades ago, highlighted the importance of collaboration in medical social work settings. Blacker & Deveau (2010), bring a similar perspective into the present day in their account of the development of interprofessional collaborations in a palliative care setting. Golden (2011) has advocated for the importance of collaboration in efforts to reform health care, while Snow & Gilbertson (2011) report on the importance of collaborative relationships when working with families facing multiple, complex issues.

The link between social work practice and educational settings is the focus of other collaborative efforts, including, for example, a partnership involving schools of social work, law and nursing working alongside local communities to address violence against women (Busch-Armendariz, Johnson, Buel & Lungwitz, 2011). Other examples of collaborative approaches being utilised in social work education include initiatives established between schools of social work (Crowell & McCarragher, 2007) and between disciplines (Bronstein, Mizhari, Korazim-Korosy & McPhee, 2010; Stone, Ekman, English & Fujimori, 2008), where such collaboration may involve both staff and students. It has been noted that there is increasing interest in social work practice and education on the potential benefits of international collaborative relationships. Cornelius & Greif (2005) reviewed the nature and extent of collaborations between schools of social work in the US and their foreign counterparts. They concluded that such partnerships were mutually beneficial across a number of dimensions, including the acquisition of cross-cultural insights and perspectives. Sullivan, Forrester & Al-Makhamreh (2010) highlight this dimension, noting that

... it is incumbent upon social workers to facilitate this type of engagement to develop an understanding of different cultures, given a variety of social and economic partnerships between countries, current patterns of immigration and social work's role in promoting humane change and development across the globe. (pp. 219)

Interest in the usefulness and efficacy of collaborative approaches extends, of course, beyond social work. Given the emerging urgency of developing a social work perspective that includes the connections between the social and environmental as discussed above, it is instructive to recognise that partnership and collaboration models have also been a feature of environmental activism, environmental education and education for sustainability. Generally speaking, environmental education, in its different forms, is predicated on the belief that a deeper level of education and knowledge about the environment and ecology will increase the likelihood of action now to preserve nature and address environmental problems into the future (Nkonya, Pender & Kato, 2008). Environmental education as an activity may take place across all levels of education and is being increasingly integrated into mainstream curricula (ICEE, 2008). The final declaration from the 4th International Conference on Environmental Education, held in 2007 in Ahmedabad, India, provides a clear sense of the goals of environmental education in all of its forms:

Our vision is a world in which our work and lifestyles contribute to the well-being of all life on Earth. We believe that through education, human lifestyles can be achieved that support ecological integrity, economic and social justice, sustainable livelihoods and respect for all life. Through education we can learn to prevent and resolve conflicts, respect cultural diversity, create a caring society and live in peace. We can learn from indigenous and traditional patterns of living that respect and honour the Earth and its life-support systems and we can adapt this wisdom to our fast-changing world. (ICEE, 2007)

The importance of partnerships is a recurring theme in environmental education (Austin, 2004; Davis, 1997; Roberts, 2009; Ryan, 2003). Such partnerships may take many forms, including partnerships with a focus on a particular school linking with an NGO (Salter, 2011), partnerships involving groups of professionals linking with multiple schools (Wormstead, Becker & Congalton, 2002), or those that focus on a social issue such as health as the gateway into multiple partnerships (Kruger, Nelson, Klein, McCurdy, Pride & Ady, 2010). In India, a striking example of successful environmental education collaboration is provided by the 'eco-club' movement (Orr & Kumar, 2010). This initiative involving school children across the country is part of wider efforts to integrate environmental perspectives into all educational activities (Almeida & Cutter-Mackenzie, 2011; Ravindranath (2007). There are also numerous examples of successful collaborations involving higher education institutions with communities or community-based organizations (for example, Molnar, Ritz, Heller & Solecki, 2010; Allen-Gil, Walker, Thomas, Shevory & Elan, 2005; Boylan & Collin, 2006). Indeed, the scale of collaborative possibilities covers all levels of social organisation, from programmes focused on single pre-schools (Larimore, 2011) through to the GLOBE program, an environmental education project running in over 5,000 schools in 60 countries (Finarelli, 1998; GLOBE, 2012).

The existence of a tradition of partnership and collaboration in social work, and a parallel emphasis on the importance of such an approach in the field of environmental education and its related activities, suggests that there is great potential in exploring this approach as a strategy to promote an eco-social orientation within the profession. This potential, coupled with the emerging desire for the social work profession to address eco-social justice as a key issue, has led to a unique collaboration between two Indian and Australian departments of social work.

4. THE DIST-JCU COLLABORATION

Forging international collaborations has become an important initiative for many Australian universities (Lyons, 2006) and James Cook University is no exception. A recent statement describing JCU's strategic intent makes a clear commitment to "produce graduates with the expertise and ...the knowledge and understanding needed to meet the challenges facing northern Australia and the tropics world-wide" (James Cook University, 2010). Complimenting this institutional sanction, the Department of Social Work and Human Services at JCU has prioritised the inclusion of international dimensions within the programs offered by the Department. The Department's Mission Statement was modified in 2009 to articulate a commitment "to education and practice which ... through high quality teaching and research, critical scholarship and active community service... values diversity and recognises the international context of practice" (Department of Social Work, 2009).

There is no lack of persuasive arguments for including an international perspective and international content in social work education or in fact higher education in general. The international priorities of James Cook University reflect a national trend in higher education as economic, cultural and academic imperatives drive the quest for links and partnerships between universities across the globe (Healy 2001). As a profession, social work claims an international dimension that can reflect a number of different though related social work activities. International social work can mean social work that has a focus on international issues or it can refer to activities and exchanges that take place at international or global level (Healy 2001; Gray & Fook 2004). The Department of Social Work and Human Services at James Cook University is well positioned to engage in activities which reflect all these perspectives.

In 2010 a number of factors serendipitously contributed to furthering the Department's international aspirations. The first was the introduction of a two-year Masters of Social Work program, accredited by the Australian Association of Social Workers and developed in anticipation of the growing number of potential International students particularly from South East Asia and India. At the same time a growing number of domestic social work students articulated a developing awareness of international social work as an important field of practice and sought advice and support in securing international field education placements. The appointment of a social work lecturer educated in India provided the impetus and capacity for two staff from JCU to make a brief but fruitful visit to India.

One of the institutions visited included DIST – a college located in Angamaly, in the state of Kerala, and affiliated with the Mahatma Gandhi University. DIST offers a Masters of Social Work with an annual intake of approximately fifty students and the social work staff of the college indicated strong interest in collaborations with JCU, sharing the aspiration to develop international links, activities and partnerships for all the reasons described above. A dialogue began, exploring opportunities for the two institutions to develop a range of mutually beneficial, collaborative endeavours, including an international conference. A framework for the conference organisation already existed, as DIST had facilitated and hosted an annual series of "De Novo" gatherings, and in February 2011 a convening committee of both JCU and DIST staff was formed to facilitate an International De Novo conference. Discussions about a theme or

focus for the conference uncovered many similar concerns despite the significant and obvious differences that exist between India and Australia. One that emerged with some clarity was the enormous challenge relating to environmental problems and the ways in which these impact on humans. In both Kerala and Queensland, and more broadly in India and Australia, the impacts of issues such as climate change are becoming increasingly apparent and the social justice implications startlingly clear (Jones, Miles, Francis & Rajeev, 2011). The decision to use the De Novo '11 conference to focus attention on issues of eco-social justice reflected the commitment and intention of both social work departments to contribute in a meaningful way to addressing these issues.

The conference and student meet, De Novo'11- Eco Social Justice: Issues, Challenges and Ways Forward, took place over four days in November 2011. The conference attracted 275 participants representing researchers, activists, academics, practitioners and students of social work and related disciplines from all over India and from Australia. The conference featured 60 paper presentations and 16 plenary addresses which encouraged critical reflection, discussion and exploration of policy and practice methods relevant to social work with individuals and communities in the face of the environmental crisis. In addition to traditional paper presentations the 'student meet' which immediately followed the conference provided the opportunity to consider eco-social justice issues as depicted through street plays, dance, role play and debate. A small contingent of Australian students joined over 300 Indian social work students in presenting thought-provoking interpretations of the conference themes. While the De Novo 11 conference represented the culmination of the short-term goals established in this partnership, its success proved a catalyst for the development of an ongoing process of international collaboration.

5. BENEFITS OF COLLABORATION

The DIST-JCU collaboration has emerged as a strategy with great potential for contributing to the wider struggle for eco-social justice. There are a number of specific dimensions of the collaboration which point to the possibilities for progress in this area.

AWARENESS RAISING

One of the key aims of an international conference is to bring together stakeholders from a range of settings, expose them to new ideas and facilitate the exchange of information and energy. In the case of the DIST-JCU collaboration, the focus on issues of eco-social justice represented an opportunity to raise awareness of an important new arena for social work education and practice. The mix of presenters and participants at the conference, including academics, practitioners, policy makers, activists and students, ensured that there was a lively and productive exchange of ideas, thereby maximising the likelihood that participants would come away with new insights and enthusiasm.

THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT

In her discussion of the place of environment in social work theory and practice, Kemp (2011) noted the importance of developing research, theoretical perspectives and practice experience in this field. One of the highlights of the DIST-JCU collaboration has been a significant

contribution to this process through the publication of the volume “Eco-social Justice: Issues, Challenges and Ways Forward” which brings together the work of academics and practitioners with a focus on eco-social justice. This publication includes material with both theoretical and practical orientations, demonstrating the connections between eco-social justice and areas such as social work education, mental health, physical wellbeing, ethical consumption, women’s empowerment and social capital. In developing these ideas and disseminating this information through this publication, the collaboration itself makes a contribution to the ongoing theoretical development of the concept of eco-social justice and an understanding of its relationship to the social work profession.

CROSS-CULTURAL UNDERSTANDING

Sullivan, Forrester & Al-Makhamreh (2010) noted the importance of developing cross-cultural understanding through international collaborative activities. The nature of an international collaboration means that such understanding is essential in order to meet the logistical and organisational imperatives of the activity, but the DIST-JCU experience has shown the importance of going beyond this instrumental focus. Working in a collaborative fashion with a focus on eco-social justice has allowed participants an opportunity to begin developing an understanding of the issues faced by individuals and communities in their respective countries and the cultural context that surrounds these. The collaboration has begun to reveal differences in social work approaches in India and Australia but also the commonalities that exist and how these might be enhanced and amplified. It has become clear to all parties involved in the collaboration that there is a great deal to be learned from each other that will be mutually beneficial.

LOCAL REALITIES

The environmental issues facing the planet today are often global in nature and do not respect political and geographical boundaries. However, their experience on the ground will vary dramatically from place to place as the political, social, cultural and economic contexts exert their influence. Drawing on insights from community development we must remember that in eco-social practice, valuing the local, as well as recognising the global, will be essential (Ife & Tesoriero, 2006). One of the key benefits of the collaborative international conference and subsequent publication has been the opportunity for academics and practitioners to report on grass-roots experiences of injustice, and the responses to these, as a way of grounding theoretical discussions firmly in the lived reality of individuals and communities.

LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES

The central role of social work education in promoting an eco-social orientation within the profession has been noted previously (Jones, 2011). Exposing current students to this new perspective means that we are effectively equipping future practitioners with the knowledge and skills required for eco-social practice. The DIST-JCU collaboration has included the development of opportunities for student exchange and collaboration as a key part of its activities. JCU students travelled to Kerala to attend the international conference and have

completed field placements in India, while DIST students are scheduled to travel to Australia for field placements later this year.

ACTION FOR CHANGE

All of the above dimensions –raising awareness; facilitating theoretical development; developing cross-cultural understanding; documenting local realities; and creating opportunities for learning – are essential prerequisites for action to produce change. Efforts to achieve eco-social justice and address the major environmental challenges facing the globe cannot emerge in a vacuum but rather must rest on a foundation that includes all of these elements. At the conclusion of the eco-social justice conference, participants were invited to sign a pledge that committed them to taking action to address issues of eco-social justice and work towards a better, more sustainable environment. Providing the foundation for such action is a key element of this international collaborative effort.

6. CONCLUSION

As it becomes clearer that social work as a profession can no longer afford to ignore issues relating to the natural environment and the impact of these on human wellbeing and, indeed, survival, we must begin to search for ways forward. The nature of many of the environmental issues impacting on individuals, communities and societies today is that they are boundary-crossers, global in nature but local in their impact. It makes sense then to explore options for addressing such issues that are also both global and local and that involve crossing boundaries and reaching across barriers. International collaborations represent an opportunity to do just this, and may bring with them a number of benefits both for direct participants but also in the longer term for the broader profession and for the people with whom social workers will practice in the future.

The DIST-JCU collaboration, while still in its early stages, has already shown very positive signs that it will indeed be a productive strategy in this regard. By raising awareness of eco-social justice as a social work standpoint or imperative, the collaboration is set to contribute to the theoretical development of this concept, but also to provide grounded, meaningful opportunities for learning and action in both India and Australia.

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ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN ACQUIRING ADEQUATE MANPOWER IN TOURISM SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Today, most of the countries promote tourism to earn foreign exchange, to encourage developmental activities, improve local economies and to generate employment. In India, the industry as well as Government stresses lot on tourism infrastructure but not much attention is focused on proper Human Resource Management. It is high time to realize that our country is aiming seven million foreign tourists to visit each year and is trying to build enough infrastructures to cater to the needs (Airports, Resorts, Highways, connectivity, etc) but is lagging in trained manpower to handle the same and to serve the tourists. It is mandatory that the industry requires trained manpower and the emphasis on HRD in Tourism need to be broad based at different levels in all diverse sectors of Tourism. The changing nature of Tourism and growing specializations demands much more than mere smiling faces and good communication of persons rendering services. It now demands a structured knowledge packed behavior and systematic approach too. There is also a strong need to train the existing employees in the Tourism field so that the quality of services rendered could be standardized. As per the WTO statistics, international tourism receipts totaled US \$ 733 billion and Tourism represents around 35% of the world export of services. (WTO, Tourism Vision 2020) The International tourists arrival World wide is expected to be 1.6 billion by 2020. According to the study conducted by Tourism Ministry, Government of India, the supply for manpower in Tourism sector is not even 40% of the demand. This paper is the outcome of an effort initiated by the researchers to probe on to the present HRD scenario prevailing in the nation and hence an attempt is made to define the set of

factors determining the tourism employment generation and to incorporate them into a model that is able to present their respective role and their inter relationships.

KEYWORDS: *Employment, Human Resource, Tourism.*

INTRODUCTION

1. OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Tourism Education in India commenced during 1962-64. The National Council for Hotel Management and Catering Technology was formulated in the Year 1984 which has now around 26 institutes' country wide. Few training centers are established in the Private sector owned by some major hotel groups aimed to meet their own requirements. There exists a strong need to train the existing employees in the Tourism field so that the quality of services rendered could be standardized. Earlier studies carried out in the field were analyzed and it reveals that a striking gap exists in the field of research in this highly potential but understudied area. The study is carried out with the mission to diagnose the existing human resource management in diverse sectors of tourism and related data were collected from the Directorate of Tourism, Govt. of Kerala, KTDC, Kerala Institute of Travel and Tourism Studies, Institute of Hotel Management and Catering Technology, District Tourism Promotion Council, selected resorts/travel inns in the private sector and from the published research reports on related topics. Among the classified resorts and travel inns, selected ones were visited and primary data were collected on acquiring prior permission from the respective management. Faculty members and some students of travel and tourism institutes were interviewed to arrive at the final judgment. The survey was carried out from December 2010 to March 2011 and responses were collected from 116 students and 76 employees in various tourism sectors.

2. TOURISM IN INDIA

India - one of the prime holiday destinations where tourists from all around the world are willing to spending their holiday. Our country, India, is the land of vivacious culture, amazing contradictions, diverse geography but despite shows unity in diversity. It is a vast country and all regions of this country have their own distinct charm. If truth to be told, it is not just a country but is the combination of several mini countries which are its various states with their own distinct charm, culture & tradition, languages, cuisine, dress sense, etc. And this is India's unity in diversity which is the single most predominant factor that makes it one of the most prime holiday destinations in all over the world. Tourism in India is the largest service industry, with a contribution of 6.23% to the national GDP and 8.78% of the total employment in India. India witnesses more than 5 million annual foreign tourist arrivals and 562 million domestic tourism visits. The tourism industry in India generated about US\$100 billion in 2008 and that is expected to increase to US\$275.5 billion by 2018 at a 9.4% annual growth rate. In the year 2009, 5.11 million foreign tourists visited India. Table 1 shows the annual growth in the Foreign tourists arrivals in India from 1999 to 2009.

TABLE 1: FOREIGN TOURISTS ARRIVAL IN INDIA 1999-2009

Year	Foreign Tourists Arrival	Annual Growth
1999	2481928	5.2
2000	2649378	6.7
2001	2537282	-4.2
2002	2384364	-6.0
2003	2726214	14.3
2004	3457477	26.8
2005	3918610	13.3
2006	4447167	13.5
2007	5081504	14.3
2008	5282603	4.0
2009	5108579	-3.3

Source: Bureau of immigration, India

Delhi, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh Tamil Nadu, and Rajasthan (Land of Kings), were the top five states to receive inbound tourists. Table 2 indicates the top 10 States/Union Territories in India regarding foreign tourists arrivals from 2006 to 2009

TABLE 2 FOREIGN TOURIST ARRIVALS TO INDIA - TOP 10 STATES/UT

SI No	State	2006	2007	2008	2009
1	Delhi	1974836	1995123	2339287	1958272
2	Maharashtra	1712302	1762005	2056913	1969992
3	Uttar Pradesh	1328974	1396932	1610089	1532573
4	Tamil Nadu	1319501	1338521	1594680	1534787
5	Rajasthan	1220164	1250056	12677646	1073414
6	West Bengal	998029	1024220	1133671	1080418
7	Andhra Pradesh	669617	69732	789180	795173
8	Karnataka	505524	555798	571846	614316
9	Kerala	428534	468480	598929	609880
10	Goa	380414	416355	433375	444576

Source: India Tourism Statistics – 2009

Ministry of Tourism is the nodal agency to formulate national policies and programmes for the development and promotion of tourism. In the process, the Ministry consults and collaborates with other stakeholders in the sector including various Central Ministries/agencies, the State Governments/ union Territories and the representatives of the private sector. Concerted efforts are being made to promote new forms of tourism such as rural, cruise, medical and eco-tourism. The Ministry of Tourism is the nodal agency for the development and promotion of tourism in India and maintains the Incredible India campaign. According to World Travel and Tourism Council, India will be a tourism hotspot from 2009–2018, having the highest 10-year growth potential. The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report 2007 ranked tourism in India 6th in terms of price competitiveness and 39th in terms of safety and security.

3. ROLE OF HRD IN TOURISM

The terms tourist and tourism were first used as official terms in 1937 by the League of Nations. Tourism is traveling for predominantly recreational or leisure purposes or the provision of services to support this leisure travel. In 2006, there were over 842 million international tourist arrivals. Tourism is vital for many countries, due to the income generated by the consumption of goods and services by tourists, the taxes levied on businesses in the tourism industry, and the opportunity for employment in the service industries associated with tourism. These service industries include transportation services such as cruise ships and taxis, accommodation such as hotels, restaurants, bars, and entertainment venues, and other hospitality industry services such as spas and resorts. As certain types of tourism (like rural or nature-based tourism) can provide a development alternative for currently under-developed regions, tourism seems to be an effective and efficient tool in creating new jobs and thus decreasing unemployment even in these areas which, due to their low level of economic and infrastructural development, are the least attractive targets for other investors (Tamara Ratz & Laslo Puczko) The demand of manpower in Tourism sector far exceeds the supply and its adverse impact is that industry is being managed with an unacceptable percentage of untrained manpower which seriously affects the quality of services rendered to the tourists. The tourism sector mainly comprises of small /medium sized enterprises and hence the HRD practices are not standardized.

Human Resource Development often focuses on the employment needs of large Multinational companies but neglects the needs of the broader areas of Tourism (Abby.L& Geoffrey W, 2006). Human Resource Management is a phenomenon of special significance in the case of Tourism. Here, the customer is not only buying a service or product but is also experiencing and consuming the quality of service which is reflected in the persons delivering the same. Human resource management, planning and development in Tourism have to be taken both at the Macro as well as Micro levels. At Macro level the educational and training infrastructure available in the country and the efforts taken at the Government level is taken into account while at the Micro level, how best the individual organizations plan and manage their resources is taken into account. The emphasis of HRM in tourism has to be broad based taking into consideration all the sectors and services rather than mere hotels and ticketing. The changing nature of Tourism and growing specializations demands much more than mere smiling faces and good communication of persons rendering services. It now demands a structured knowledge packed behavior and systematic approach too. Contextual understanding of situations and ability to develop

appropriate managerial response by the concerned personnel too are crucial to the effective management of any tourism organization. (Clarke & Chen, 2007). It is a matter of regret that the curriculum of various Tourism related courses are not standardized and is failing to impart those qualities which an international Tourist expects from a service facilitator. The various topics that needs to be covered in any Tourism based course should include Economics of Tourism, preparation of a business plan, marketing management, personnel management, funds management, budgeting, conduct of meetings and of course Government rules and regulations pertaining to Tourism industry. Airline services and accommodation providers are getting established day to day with the increased inflow of international Tourists. The main fields to be investigated during a proper HRM planning for a tourism industry shall be the following:

- Market entry constraints for new companies in tourism,
- the nature and volume of investment,
- geographical distribution of new jobs,
- differences in the number and type (full-time vs. part-time, seasonal vs. annual) of jobs created,
- average wages and salaries,
- on-the-job training needs and costs,
- employee turnover,
- recruitment sources and procedures,
- qualification and skills requirements for employees, employment criteria,
- social status of jobs in tourism,
- main difficulties in human resource management.

4. EMPLOYMENT IN TOURISM SECTOR

Tourism is generally known as one of the sectors where the costs of a new job are significantly less than in other industries. Obviously, the characteristics of employment and the effects of tourism development vary according to the type of tourist activity, some types of tourism being more labour-intensive than others. The report by World Travel and Tourism Council states that the tourism sector provides around 17.4 million jobs country wide. The point was made that tourism has a very positive capital to labour ratio, with 89 jobs being created in the hotel and restaurant industry per 1 million rupees of investment, compared with 45 jobs in agriculture and 13 jobs in manufacturing. Accommodation facilities and the hospitality sector in general employ a substantial proportion of the tourism labour force, but they also require relatively large capital investments. The financial resources required to generate employment also vary with the size of

companies, the types of skills needed, the economic development of the destination area, etc. Tourism employment can be categorized as (Mathieson & Wall, 1982)

- Direct employment resulting from visitor expenditure in tourist services,
- Indirect employment in the tourist sector, not resulting directly from visitor expenditure, and
- Induced employment, resulting from the effects of the tourism multiplier.

If employment creation is to be analyzed in a wider sense, the costs of education needed for new employees should also be taken into consideration. Employment criteria include academic qualifications, language proficiency, computer literacy, driving license, professional experience or personality traits. The candidate's performance in interviews or the results of IQ tests or any other evaluation methods can also be of great importance. Finding and retaining staff is a key area of concern for employers in the tourism industry. Low worker commitment and a shortage of skills are also frequently cited problems facing the industry by both the trade itself and by industry practitioners and organizers. Skills at management level are particularly lacking in our country and a shortage of those with leadership qualities appears to be a common problem in most destinations. A fact of regret supplementing the situation is that academically superior candidates do not offer tourism education at any level of induction just because the traditional career options are still looked upon as superior, both status wise and monetarily. It has been argued that tourism jobs are not rent jobs but are usually low skilled, low paid, seasonal and part time for which women are favoured (Lea J, 1988). There is also a strong need to train the existing employees in the Tourism field so that the quality of services rendered could be standardized. In general, while there is wide agreement on the need to improve the supply of well-educated and -trained staff for the travel and tourism industry, it is also clear that resources are lacking (ILO,2003). Often, there is an absolute shortage of trainers, and the attraction of top quality trainers is often hampered by low public-sector pay scales within the training and education sectors.

Two most important criteria to be taken into consideration concerning new employees are the applicant's foreign language skills and their professional experience. Foreign languages have traditionally been very important in the tourism industry. In the case of Kerala, it is a basic need for all employed in Tourism related industries to have proficiency in at least Spoken English. Personality traits like friendliness, communication skills, openness, dynamism, a positive approach to problems, etc., all are so crucial in tourism where the human factor plays a major role in the overall experience of the tourist. Age of the candidates is another factor that needs to be considered while recruiting. It is obvious to prefer young candidates because they are supposed to be more flexible and more willing to learn new things, even though their professional experience is minimal. The fields where employees particularly need to develop their knowledge are the following:- foreign languages , computer skills, sales knowledge, marketing fundamentals, communication skills, accounting & taxation, professional knowledge in general, etc. If an employee, sincerely willing to build up a career in Tourism industry,

acquires the above mentioned desirables, it shall be beneficial mutually for both the industry and the person.

In India, the salary paid to the employees by Tourism industry is far less than the same when compared to IT, banking, retail, finance, retail etc. There is a perception among the job seekers that it is often difficult for staff in Tourism industry to progress through the organization that employs them. For example, hotel staff working in rooms or food & beverage operations can find it hard to advance themselves to more senior levels. If this situation could be improved, it would create a “virtuous circle”, by providing better opportunities for skills upgrading. This could help to eliminate the perception of an industry which offers poor career perspectives, thereby improving its ability to attract new recruits. By 2015, the Government of India has identified that as many as 6 million additional jobs in the tourism sector may be created, most of which will be generated by domestic tourism demand. The need for imparting likelihood among educated youth towards Tourism industry could become a key issue in the expansion of the sector. It is also the morale of Government to develop and promote tourism education and employment portal and to organize awareness campaigns regarding the upcoming opportunities so that the most drastic ailment of unemployment in the country could be cured. The tourism related courses offered by many universities are too theoretical in nature and do not fulfill the industry requirements. Considering its globalised nature, more emphasis shall be given on personality development, soft skills and effective communication, both written as well as oral. Government should also encourage and provide provisions for the existing institutions offering tourism courses for academic tie ups with Universities in UK, Switzerland etc, the countries which have taken tourism education with supreme importance, so that the faculty members also could be well versed with the cross cultural practices through refresher/ faculty development courses and faculty exchange programmes. As may be the case of Kerala is concerned, the Government owns just three organizations namely Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel Studies (KITTS), Institute of Hotel Management and Catering Technology, Thiruvananthapuram (IHMCT), and State Institute of Hospitality Management, Kozhikode (SIHM) to impart effective tourism related courses. Apart from these many of the private organizations too run tourism courses. The striking feature here is that none of the Universities in Kerala runs an approved graduation programme in tourism.

5. RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The study was being proceeded with the objective to identify the reasons for why a talented and enthusiastic young pool of aspirants with meritorious school records are not getting attracted towards the industry to opt it as a career , to study the expectations and pre – requisites for a tourism student/professional to reach heights and to suggest some solutions to improve the quality of manpower supplied. The following factors were studied in detail to arrive at the final conclusion:-

1. Ratio of students who have chosen to pursue Tourism as their dream career
2. Whether the management of selected and reputed resorts is satisfied with the available human resources.

3. The effectiveness of the tourism courses and the coverage of essential pre- requisites by the same.

TABLE 3: STUDENTS OPTION FOR TOURISM STUDIES

Whether opted Tourism as a dream career	Count	Percent
Yes	76	65.51
No	21	18.10
NA	19	16.37

TABLE 4: AWARENESS ON CAREER PATH BY EMPLOYEES IN TOURISM INDUSTRY

Employees are well aware on the career advancement path	Yes		No		Total		χ^2	p
	Count	Percent	Count	Percent	Count	Percent		
NA	3	17.6	0	0.0	3	7.0	5.21	0.157
NO	7	41.2	15	57.7	22	51.2		
YES	3	17.6	4	15.4	7	16.3		
Both	4	23.5	7	26.9	11	25.6		

TABLE 5: SATISFACTION OF MANAGEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES

Management Satisfied with the present employees	Count	Percent
Yes	11	25.58
No	23	53.48
NA	9	20.93

- The students were of the opinion that the courses were run as a mix of various subjects but lacks specialization.
- Some students opinioned that the industry lacked glamour and society acceptance when compared to professions like Engineering, Medicine etc.
- Most of the employees were disappointed with the salary packages and possess the fear of loosing the job if they asked for its hike. It was known that no career advancement path is clearly defined in any of those organisations.
- It was shocking to see that majority of the employees working in tourism sector are mere graduates/ under graduates and even the personnel occupying senior posts lacks a degree/ Post Graduation in tourism courses.
- There exists no specific recruitment policies in filling specialized posts and the desirable skill sets are trespassed.
- About 90% of the employees in Government owned organisations in tourism sector works on temporary basis with daily wage/consolidated pay and hence lacks commitment to the profession.
- Majority of the Managements where of the opinion that they are facing scarcity in attracting meritorious employees with excellent academic and career track in Tourism.
- The faculty members were of the opinion that the students getting admitted are of very poor quality and the existing curriculum does not include specific courses on Language learning and effective communication skills.
- Obsolete syllabus and the students doing industrial training are being utilized as mere room boys.

6. CONCLUSION

The tourism industry is a combination of different sectors and each sector has its own specialized requirements in terms of human resources. The diversity of this industry places additional responsibility on the planners and promoters of Tourism services. Each country should emphasis on the ability of Tourism to create employment opportunities and its overall contribution to the overall economic and social developments (Tom B & Edith S, 2007). It is predicted that the Indian Tourism industry will grow at an annual rate of 8.8% over the next decade by the World Travel and Tourism Council. The future success of Tourism may depend largely on whether or not each country is prepared to educate not only tourism employees but also the tourists and the population of Tourists receiving areas so as to impart adequate level of culture and etiquette which is essential for this widely growing sector (WTO, 1987). Workers in tourism organizations that seek to be competitive must be highly skilled, reliable and educated individuals (Duffey, 1988). It is the moral responsibility of each country to adopt a greater role in developing sufficient human resources for the industry. Co-operation and cordial relationship

between the public and private sectors need to be ensured for effectively satisfying the employment constraints in tourism sector. Due to the lack of a widely accepted categorization of employment in tourism sector, together with the complexity of factors to be taken into consideration, the main contributing factors to the overall employment creation in tourism are not clearly defined. Lack of standardized HR practices, absence of a well defined growth path, non competitive salary packages have resulted in high dissatisfaction and attrition rates among the existing employees which in turn shall result in scarcity of next generation young and talented pool.

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A STUDY ON SINGING METHOD OF SAMA GANA

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ABSTRACT

Sama Veda has the credit that it is the earliest music of India. Even in early pre-historic period, Sama Veda developed the notes from one to three, that is Samika, Gathika and Archika. This method paved way to give birth the Saman Saptakam, the seven notes Krurta, Prathama, Dvitiya, Tritiya, Chaturtha, Mandra and Atisvarya. As Sama Veda is the treasure house of resource, it is the necessity to analyze Sama Veda to acquire knowledge of history of music of early days. This research will throw light on the following of Sama Veda; text-Saman Samhita, arrangement of Sama Veda, technical terms and definitions of Ganas, various Recensions (Vedic Schools), notes utilized by Recensions, singing method (with notation), Stobhas, Saman Saptaka, Musical hand utilized to denote notes, Singers and their duties, Laya and metre(rhythm), Sama Veda paved way for forerunners, Laukika ganas- four kadais and so on.

KEYWORDS: *SamaVeda, Recensions, Singers, Ganas, Music.*

1. INTRODUCTION

‘Vedanam Sama Vedo asmi’

-Sri Krishna

Vedic period comes under pre-history period. ‘Prehistory is a term used to describe the period before recorded history. ‘Prehistoric music’ is a term in the history of music for all music produced in preliterate cultures, beginning somewhere in very late geological history. In pre-

history period, music was not written and was orally taught from one person to another person. Chandra Banerji Sures in his book 'A Companion to Indian Music and Dance' conveyed that 'Vedic music represents pre- historic culture'. Sathianathan Shantisheela stated in his book titled 'Contributions of Saints and Seers to the Music of India' that "Vedas came down orally from teacher to disciple, and were written down only 2000 years back. It was considered to be a great sin to reduce them to writing". Dasgupta Surendranath in his book 'A History of Indian Philosophy' stated that the four Vedas 'were learnt by heart by the Brahmins from mouth of their preceptors and were hence called Sruti (literally anything heard). That is why 'Vedas are known as 'Sruti'-eternal truths heard through intuition.' It was Vyasa, the son of sage Parashar and the grandson of the great Vashishtha who gave Veda a written source. Hence he was called Veda Vyasa by great people then. The Vedas are the earliest literature of India and a mile stone in the field of history. Likewise, the earliest musical form is Sama Veda.

SAMA VEDA

Rig, Yajur, Sāma and Atharvana are the four Vedas. Ram avatar veer? Quoted in his 'The Music of India, Vol. I', that the Rig Veda is a treasure of knowledge (gyan), the Yajur Veda throws light on duties (karma) of all concerned, the Atharvana Veda deals with Ayurveda, building construction, agriculture, science and general behaviour and Sāma Veda contains mantras for offering prayers to the Almighty. Though Sāma Veda or Veda of Holy songs are third in the usual order, it ranks next to the Rig Veda. The earliest music of India is the chant of Sāma Veda. Rig, Yajur and Atharvana Vedas are recited, but Sāma Veda is set to tune. Hence almost all the writers on music proclaimed: "From Sāma Veda, Brahma got music". Sri Krishna declared, "Vedanam Sāma Vedo asmi" – that is "I am the Sāma Veda of all Vedas". The term Sāma gāna itself makes it clear that it was not merely recited like the other three Vedas. V.Raghavan opined that Kallinatha, in his commentary on the Sangeetha Ratnakara, draws attention to this , citing "Sāma Veda Geeta pradhāna....

The Aitareya Brāhmaa and the Bhadārayaka Upaniad stated that the two parts-s and ama together formed the term Sama. S stands for Ric and Ama for the musical notes which the ric is sung. To have a clear picture of SāmaVeda, the arrangement of the Sāma Veda of Caland's Table is as follows:

A). SĀMAN SAMHITA: (SĀHITHYA)

“The Chandogya Upanishad (1-6-1) says, ‘Rk adyudham Sama’, which means that Sāma is based on the Rk”. It is clear that the matu or words or the verses for sāma veda are from Rig Veda. Rig Veda potrays the nature-Gods, such as Surya(Sun), Soma(Moon), Agni(Fire), Dyaus(Sky), Maruts(Storms), Vayu(Wind), Apas(Water), Ushas(Dawn) and Prithvi(Earth). It also contains prayers, asking for wealth and more men, ‘Dhanam and Praja’. The verses or hymns collected for Sāma Veda from Rig Veda are known as Sāman Samhita. The verses, so collected and compiled into the whole samhita are called Uttarārchika. These are sung to certain prescribed melodies called Purvārchika. Ārayaka samhita is but a continuation of Purvārchika. There is no clue to the date of the compilation of the Sāma Veda hymns, nor has the compiler's name been handed down to us. The Sāhitya(Samhita) of Sāma Veda consists of an arranged series of verses, directed to be sung especially at the Soma Yaga or the Soma sacrifice. It is the duty of the priests to sing them at the time of sacrifice, which was given in a format called Suktas. One ric is the basis of the sāman. If the same sāman is chanted with the two other rics of the sukta, a stotriya is formed. These stotriyas make a stotra, while specific number of rics chanted like 9,15,17,21 and so on forms a stoma. The method of singing, more specifically the number of notes used in singing, varied from one Vedic school to another.

RECENSIONS: (VEDIC SCHOOLS)

Griffith. R. T. H. says that there are three recensions of the text of the Samaveda Samhita: the Kauthuma recension is current in Gujarat, and since a few decades in Darbhanga, Bihar, the Jaiminiya in the Carnatic and Kerala, and the Rāṇāyanīya in the Maharatta country.

B) GĀNA

The song books of different schools are termed as ganas. Kauthumas, Ranayaniyas and Jaiminiyas, for centuries, remained faithful to their own traditions, hence song books (**Gana**) with different types of musical notation have emerged . The ‘Gānas are song books’ from which the melodies of the Sāmans are sung or learnt. In the Sāma Veda Samhita, ‘thousand eight hundred’ verses have been borrowed from the Rig Veda and about seventy five seem to have been independently composed. There are four Gāna texts – (1).Grāmageya gāna or Veya gāna, (2).Ārayageya gāna, (3).Uha gāna and (4).Uhya or Rahasyagāna. The terms Āraya geya gāna and Grāma geya gāna, the names themselves signify that music of Āraya was heard in the forests, sung by the great Yogis and Grāma geya gāna was developed by the village people. Uha gāna was sacrificial music. Uhya or Rahasya gāna was open only to the initiates. The Grāma geya gāna and Āraya geya gāna are attached to the Purvārchika and termed as Prakritigāna. These four patterns clothed appropriate verses chosen from the Sāma Veda. Prof. RanedaG.H. stated that according to Caland , the Jaiminiyas have 1232 verses in Grāma geya gāna ,291 in Āraya ,1802 in uha ,356 in Uhya gāna . The Kauthumas possess 2722 gānas. In course of time Sāma gāna enlarged its scope. The Āraya geya gāna improved the quality of its music and ‘included prose’

and verse passages from Upanishads. Of all these , Āraya was bound by strict rules and could not be followed by ordinary people and could be followed only by those who attained great heights in spiritual growth and meditation. Besides these Vaidika gāna, the laukika gānas were composed by Brahmanas and Kshatriyas, to be sung at the time of Ashvamedha and Mahāvṛta. These sāhityas are named as Kadai-s, and are of four kinds .They are ‘Hilluka, Himpini, Asvavara and Samvathsaram’.

C). SĀMAN NOTES AND THE SĀMAN SINGING:*

The note material of the gānas is more profuse than in the Samhita .In the Samhita there were three notes- sāmansu vyantaram-as the svara nomenclature,Udāṭṭa, anudāṭṭa and svarita. These musical notes are marked with numbers 1,2 and 3 denoting the musical pitches. Sāman singer is loaded with precise tonal acoustical devices including absolutely no particular or textual meaning – Him, A, Au, Ho, Vi, Iha, Have, Ye, etc., which number nearly ten thousand, and are called stobhas, phulla or pushpa.

Now we can see the text or hymns of Sāma Veda from Rig and also how the svaras and stobhas were applied in singing them.

The verses collected for Sāma Veda from Rig (first specimen) is as follows:

Om agnimie purohitam | yagnasya devamrutvijam | hotaram | ratna dhatamam| Rigveda,I-i-1

MEANING

I glorify Agni, the family priest as wellas the divine sacrificial priest who presents the oblations(to the Gods) and who is the possessor of ratna or great wealth (that is ,the reward of religious rites) .

The above mentioned Rig for Sāman singing is as follows:

Hau hau hau va agnimile purohitam devesu nidhimam aham Hau hau hau va yagnasyadeva
 S s S s S s S srGRs s G R s g sGr g s g r s g r S s S s S s S s g r rsgr
 Mrutvijam devesu nidhimam aham Hau hau hau va ho ta ram ratna dhatamam
 S g r g sGr g s g r s g r S s S s S s S Ggr Gggg S d s G R S
 Devesu nidhimam aham Hau hau hau va yeha devesu nidhimam aham devesu
 G sGr g s g r s g r S s S s S s S G r s g sGr g s g r s g r g sGr
 nidhimam aham devesu nidhimam aham
 g s g r s g r g sGr g s g r s g r

D) Sāman Saptakam : (seven notes) In due course, ‘the notes have been developed into seven notes. Naradiya, Manduki and Panini Shikhas mentioned that seven notes have evolved from these three notes²⁰. The nomenclature of the seven notes are (1) Krusta (2) Prathama (3) Dvitiya (4) Tritiya (5) Caturtha (6) Mandra and (7) Atisvarya. Ramaswami Aiyar. M.S. stated that Manduki Siksa denoted that,

Sapta svarastu giyante samabhi : samagairbudhai : |

and also indicated that,

Laukike ye nisadadasya: saptasvara : prasiddha :, sa yeva samin kurtadaya: saptasvara bhavanti | tadyatha- yo nishada: sa krusta: | dhaivata: prathama : | pancamo dvitiya: | madyamastrutiya : | gandharasracaturtha : | ksusbho mandra : | sadjoitisvarya yiti |

and the order of that was – Ma Ga Ri Sa Dha Ni Pa-in a descending manner. Varadarajan Brinda opined that the names of the Sāmic seven notes first appear in the Sāma-Vidhana-Brahmana and also denoted the numerical as 1,2,3,4,5,6 and 7.

While singing, the hand fingers were utilized to denote the notes and termed as ‘MusicalHand’. The Sāman singer intonates musical tunes with the help of right hand five fingers.²⁴

- (1) 1st finger- the thumb denotes the first note to be sung.
- (2) 2nd finger –next to thumb denotes the 2nd note lower than the first.
- (3) 3rd finger – the middle finger denotes the third note lower than the second.
- (4) 4th finger –denotes the fourth note.
- (5) 5th finger – denotes the 5th note.

The Sāman begins only with these five notes and identified as the fundamental tone of the Sāman, ‘pratyekam sadjabhāvena’ that means adhara shadja. To be more clear, as per the rule, the first letter of Sāman was indicated between only by these five numbers and the numbers 6 or 7 were never used in the beginning. Though the Sāman notes are developed into seven, different schools stick on to their own traditions to adopt the notes. The Kauthumas and Ranayaniyas sing in seven notes –Krushta, Prathama, Dvitiya, Tritiya, Chaturtha, Mandra or Panchama, Shastha or Antya or Atisvarya. The Jaiminias in six; Kauthumas have seven notes only in two Sāmans²⁵. Keith, Caland believed that different kinds of sacrifice and rites used to be performed in the Vedic time and different kinds of Sāman were used in them.

The Sāma gāna’s singing process is termed as Bhaktis. The first one is (i) Humkara, that is the priest will utter hum at the beginning of the singing, (ii) Prastora, (i.e) the Prastotris (Prastotri- priest) used to sing at the beginning of the sāma gana, (iii) Udgitha, the Udgatris used to repeat the tune of Sāma gāna, (iv) Pratihara, the Pratihatris used to sing the part of the song

after the third stanza of the Sama gana, (v) Upadrava, the Udgatris used to sing at the end of the third stanza, (vi) Nidhana, to be sung by the sacrificial priests at the end of the Samans and (vii) Pranava (i.e) omkara. This is the pattern of singing Sāma gāna. Simon recognizes only five bhaktis- Prastava, Udgitha, Pratihara, Upadrava and Nidhana. The five bhaktis are used only for Brahma Yagna prasna. These seven bhaktis are used in Yagakarya.

E) LAYA

There was clear understanding of laya. Hsva, denoted one matra ,dirgha two matras and pluta three matras. Moreover, various metres were applied for various rituals. In the Soma sacrifice the Gāyatri and Pragatha metres are sung²⁶. Even in the pre-historic period, the words arrangement and modifications of the samic for one function to another function; application of different musical notes for the same samic; following a specific pattern for their own school(pani); hrasva ,dirgha pattern and the implementation of various metres as laya or rhythm are breathtaking. These laid path for newer things to accept innovations, varieties, novelties and creativities.

F) COMPOSITIONS UTILIZED

In the Vedic period, the types of compositions utilized are:

Grāmageya gāna

Ārayageya gāna

Uha gāna

Uhya gāna

Hilluka

Himpini

Asvavara

Samvathsaram

G) VEDIC MUSIC PAVED WAY FOR THE FUTURE AS

Stobhas of the Sāman –Akara of later music.

The four types of gānas (Grāmageya, Ārayageya ,Uha and Uhya)-various types of compositions to be evolved.

Five bhaktis gave rise in latter music to Udgraha, Anugraha, Sambodha, Dhruvaka and Abhoga.

Three notes and the development into seven notes – seeds for musical scale system.

Various metres and chandas- tala or rhythm

Sāman singing method –to evolve a system of notation.

The starting note of Sāman, which was considered as the key note changed automatically giving rise to the murchana system.

It is believed that from four faces of Brahma, the four Vedas originated. Later, Rishis, Munis, Brahmanas, Kshatriyas made an attempt and composed their own compositions²⁷. Hence, in due course of time, 'different types of songs'²⁸ were sung during ceremonies, Yagyas, sacrifices, rituals (vaidika); Ashvamedha, Mahavrata, war, hope of rainfall, love (laukika) and so on. The changes, variations in Sāman singing and in laukika gānas paved way for the Akhyanas like Rāmāyaṇa.

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IMPLICATIONS OF EDUCATIONAL DEPRIVATION FOR THE SELF OF THE OUT OF SCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Education is one of the basic right that all children are entitled to. However, many children remain out of school and hence face the worst form of deprivation. Out of school children refers to a group of children who should be in school but are not. These children have either never been to school or haven't even completed the basic five years of regular schooling. Around the world in spite of a global resolve to end educational deprivation, a large number of children remain out of school. The present paper presents Implication of Educational Deprivation for the self out of School children

KEYWORDS: *Educational Deprivation, Economic development, illiteracy.*

1. INRODUCTION

Education is one of the basic right that all children are entitled to. However, many children remain out of school and hence face the worst form of deprivation. Out of school children refers to a group of children who should be in school but are not. These children have either never been to school or haven't even completed the basic five years of regular schooling. Around the world in spite of a global resolve to end educational deprivation, a large number of children remain out of school. According to a survey conducted by the Ministry of Human resource Development, GOI (2005) the estimate number of out of school children in the country was 1.34 crore, of which majority were in the age group of 6-13 years. Further, the Ministry's 2007 report pointed out that one out of every four students do not go beyond class five. By class eight, the dropout rate got worse at 50.8% and around 20% teachers do not attend school. Ravallian and Datt (1996) noted that very large number of Indian children continue to be out of school, most of

those who enroll in Class I do not complete the first eight years of education. About 75% of these children live in six states namely, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. Over the years there has been a rapid increase in the literacy status of children in India. The country is now tackling the last segment of out of school children, who are the toughest to bring back to school and include the migratory population, schedule castes, schedule Tribes, minority communities and girl children.

Researches have indicated that the children who drop out of school continue to face the damaging effects for rest of their lives. The implications of educational deprivation are manifold not only for the nation's economic development but also for the individuals facing it. The major psychological problems of dropout girls include unassertive behavior, inferiority and low self esteem, while the main social problems include feeling of shyness, loneliness and poor communication skills (Liang et al, 2002). Students who have been eliminated out of the school system because of school failure are usually frustrated, are alienated and are more likely to show anti social behavior (Chung, 2011). Omokhodion et al (2006) and Kumar (2007) have noted that school dropouts are more likely to be involved in crime, drug use and health and material problems compared to those who complete school. MacInnaes (2006) also reported that high prevalence of psychological problems among out of school children especially low self esteem and self acceptance, depression and anxiety.

With this as background the present study assesses the psycho social development of out of school children of Kathua district of Jammu and Kashmir. It would be interesting to assess how they perceive themselves in event of the educational deprivation they face

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Sample: The sample for the study comprised 300 out of school children, of which half were boys and rest girls. All the selected sample children were in the age group of 10-14 years and were residents of Kathua District. The sample was drawn in such a manner that 100 each of these children belonged to withdrawn, eliminated and excluded category. Withdrawn refers to the category of children who attended school but were pulled out by the parents due to family conditions or other related aspects. Eliminated category of children is those who dropped out because of school underachievement, continued absenteeism, repetition of grades and other similar factors. Excluded category children are those who were never enrolled at any school and hence have no exposure to schools at all.

Sampling Technique: The sample out of school children were selected through a combination of random and purposive sampling techniques. Sarva Sikhsha Abhiyan personnel were contacted who were already working for such children of Kathua district. With their help and assistance of the community leaders those localities were surveyed where there was comparatively high incidence of out of school children, and then the children were selected randomly.

Tools used for data collection: A self devised interview schedule was used along with standardized rating scales for measurement of the sample children's self acceptance (Kakkar, S.B., 2004) and self esteem (Eagly, A.H., 1990).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The sample out of school children were in the age group of 10-14 years, with 28.7% in the age range of 13-14 years and 27.6% in the age bracket of 12-13 years. 54.7% of them belonged to nuclear families. 33.3% of them were completely illiterate, 29.6% were able to read and write, 22.3% had attended school up to elementary level, 9.3% of them had finished junior school and only 5.3% of them had received education till even secondary level.

1. REASONS FOR EDUCATIONAL DEPRIVATION:

The reasons for educational deprivation were analyzed and the results reveal that these can be classified as: Family related, school related or environment related factors. For every sample child multiple factors existed that led to their being out of school. Among the familial factors the most predominant were poverty, domestic responsibilities or illiteracy of parents. Poverty in the family had forced most of the children to stay out of school, also most of these children were used as assistants in performing of household activities such as cooking, cleaning, washing, sibling minding and even cattle rearing and caring. Also, it was found that parents who themselves were uneducated failed to realize its importance for their children also.

Reasons for educational deprivation	Withdrawn children			Eliminated children			Excluded children			Out of school children		
	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100
Family related reasons												
Poverty	22(44)	17(34)	39(39)	28(56)	15(30)	43(43)	18(36)	13(26)	31(31)	68(45.3)	45(30)	113(37.6)
Illiteracy of parents	9(18)	9(18)	18(18)	24(48)	19(38)	43(43)	21(42)	8(16)	29(29)	54(36)	36(24)	90(30)
Migration	13(26)	8(16)	21(21)	6(12)	10(20)	16(16)	12(24)	21(42)	33(33)	31(20.6)	39(26)	70(23.3)
Parental pressure	12(24)	8(16)	20(20)	9(18)	15(30)	24(24)	16(32)	16(32)	32(32)	37(24.6)	39(26)	76(25.3)
Family crisis	7(14)	6(12)	13(13)	8(16)	12(12)	20(20)	6(12)	2(4)	8(8)	21(14)	20(13.3)	41(13.7)
Domestic responsibilities	38(76)	29(58)	67(67)	29(58)	21(42)	50(50)	11(22)	23(46)	34(34)	40(26.7)	70(46.7)	110(36.7)

The school related factors which were noted to have a significant contribution in making the sample children out of school were poor infrastructure, no separate toilet facility, poor seating arrangement and irregular attendance of the student due to poor health.

Distance form school was also cited by 47% of the children, who reported lack of school in the vicinity.

School related reasons												
Regular failure	6(12)	7(14)	13(13)	4(8)	7(9)	11(11)	-	-	-	10(6.6)	14(9.3)	24(8)
Lack of attendance	7(14)	11(22)	18(18)	7(14)	9(18)	16(16)	-	-	-	14(9.3)	20(13.3)	34(11.3)
Teacher irregular	16(32)	10(20)	26(26)	9(18)	19(38)	28(28)	-	-	-	25(16.6)	29(19.3)	54(18)
Student ill health	14(28)	17(34)	31(31)	15(30)	19(38)	34(34)	-	-	-	29(19.3)	36(24)	65(21.6)
Poor class room	7(14)	6(12)	13(13)	4(8)	6(12)	10(10)	-	-	-	11(7.3)	12(8)	23(7.6)
Poor infrastructure	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	50(50)	50(100)	100(100)	-	-	-	100(66.6)	100(66.6)	200(66.6)
No separate toilet facility	42(84)	44(88)	86(86)	48(96)	47(94)	95(95)	-	-	-	90(60)	91(60.6)	181(60.3)
No play ground	14(28)	19(38)	33(33)	7(14)	9(18)	16(16)	-	-	-	21(14)	28(18.6)	49(16.3)
No sitting arrangement	21(42)	17(34)	38(38)	26(52)	29(38)	55(55)	-	-	-	47(31.3)	46(30.6)	93(31)
Lack of water facility	7(14)	8(16)	15(15)	15(30)	9(18)	24(24)	-	-	-	22(14.6)	17(11.3)	39(13)
No friend at school	8(16)	10(20)	18(18)	8(6)	2(4)	10(10)	-	-	-	16(10.6)	12(8)	28(9.3)
Environmental related reasons												
Distance from home	28(56)	30(60)	58(58)	33(66)	21(42)	54(54)	17(34)	12(24)	29(29)	78(52)	63(42)	141(47)

2. ACTIVITIES PERFORMED BY THE CHILDREN

The different activities of the out of school children were analyzed and the results show that 60% of these children were involved in some economically gainful activities such as working as cheap labour or working at small shops or kiosks. The rest of them were assisting the parents in household tasks, sibling minding or in agriculture related activities. It was rare that the child not attending school was also not involved in any activity. Involvement of a large chunk of the

sample population in labour market actually shows that child labour continues to flourish in various forms.

Working/non-working status of out of school children

Working status	Withdrawn children			Eliminated children			Excluded children			Out of school children		
	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=150	Females N=150	Total N=300
Labour	28(56)	11(22)	39(39)	30(60)	29(58)	59(59)	19(38)	17(34)	36(36)	77(51.3)	57(38)	134(44.6)
Shop/ kiosk helper	20(40)	-	20(20)	10(20)	-	10(10)	18(36)	-	18(18)	48(32)	-	48(16)
Non -working												
House hold Chores	13(26)	39(78)	52(52)	18(36)	14(28)	32(32)	13(26)	25(50)	38(38)	44(29.3)	78(52)	122(40.6)
Sibling minding	13(26)	31(62)	43(43)	20(40)	18(36)	38(38)	18(36)	9(18)	27(27)	51(34)	58(38.6)	109(36.3)
Agricultu re Activities	20(40)	25(50)	45(45)	15(30)	19(38)	34(34)	10(20)	17(34)	27(27)	45(30)	61(40.6)	106(35.3)

3. SELF ACCEPTANCE OF OUT OF SCHOOL CHILDREN

TABLE-3

SELF ACCEPTANCE OF OUT OF SCHOOL CHILDREN

Level of Self acceptance	Withdrawn children			Eliminated children			Excluded children			Out of school children		
	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=50	Females N=50	Total N=100	Males N=150	Females N=150	Total N=300
Very high	4(8)	9(18)	13(13)	7(14)	6(12)	13(13)	10(20)	5(10)	15(15)	21(14)	20(13.3)	41(13.6)
High	11(22)	7(14)	18(18)	13(26)	7(14)	20(20)	12(24)	8(16)	20(20)	36(24)	22(14.6)	58(19.3)
Low	16(32)	26(52)	42(42)	19(38)	25(50)	44(44)	15(30)	21(42)	36(36)	50(33.3)	72(48)	122(40.6)
Very low	19(38)	8(16)	27(27)	11(22)	12(24)	23(23)	13(26)	16(32)	29(29)	43(28.6)	36(24)	79(26.3)
Total	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	150(100)	150(100)	300(100)

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Calculated χ^2 Self acceptance b/w categories of out of school children =1.86, $\alpha = 0.05$, Table value = 12.6, df =6,

Calculated χ^2 Self acceptance b/w males and females =7.96*, $\alpha =0.05$, Table value=7.81, df=3,

* Significant differences at 5%

Results from table 3 reveals that on the whole majority (40.6%) of the sample out of school children (33.3% males and 48% females) had low level of self acceptance, followed by 26.3% of them had very low level of self acceptance. Calculation of chi-square reveals that there was insignificant difference between the three categories of out of school children namely; withdrawn, eliminated and excluded children with regard to their level of self acceptance, showing that irrespective of the category to which they belonged, these children mostly had low to very low self acceptance. However, statistically significant differences were found between males and females on the dimensions of self acceptance. The girls were found to have lower level of self acceptance than boys as there were more girls (48%) than boys (33.3%) in the low categories. Overall, the number of the sample children having lower level of self acceptance was more than those having higher level of it, as only 19.3% and 13.6% of the sample children had high self acceptance and very high self acceptance respectively.

FIG. 1

Overall most of the, sample out of school children had low self acceptance and were not very happy about their living conditions. These children were mostly conservative, dependent and narrow in interest. They were also found to be more shy, self- abasing, passive in action and were followers rather than leaders. The respondents who however; showed high self-acceptance were found to be more outspoken and self-confident; they had ability of verbally communicating their feelings to others and were self-assured and had a better perception of their own self. The children with very high self acceptance were noted to be very sharp, strongly demanding, strongly aggressive, self – centered and were over confident but again for the sample group this number was very small. Liang et al (2002) also found that school dropout children tend to have low self acceptance. Low self acceptances tend to have a link with shyness, aggressiveness, rejection, disruptive behavior and later maladjustment. It was noted that these children with low acceptance had feelings of loneliness and social dissatisfaction and did not feel good about themselves.

4. SELF ESTEEM OF OUT OF SCHOOL CHILDREN

TABLE-4

Level of Self Esteem	Withdrawn children			Eliminated children			Excluded children			Out of school children		
	Males	Females	Total	Males	Females	Total	Males	Females	Total	Males	Females	Total
	N=50	N=50	N=100	N=50	N=50	N=100	N=50	N=50	N=100	N=150	N=150	N=300
Very Low	9(18)	6(12)	15(15)	10(20)	11(22)	21(21)	7(14)	3(6)	10(10)	26(17.3)	20(13.3)	46(15.3)
	21(42)	18(36)	39(39)	23(46)	18(36)	41(41)	20(40)	29(58)	49(49)	64(42.6)	65(43.3)	129(43)
Low	19(38)	22(44)	41(41)	14(28)	20(40)	34(34)	21(42)	18(36)	39(39)	54(36)	60(40)	114(38)
High	1(2)	4(8)	5(5)	3(6)	1(2)	4(4)	2(4)	-	2(2)	6(4)	5(3.3)	11(3.6)
Very High												
Total	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	50(100)	50(100)	100(100)	150(100)	150(100)	300(100)

Self esteem of out of school children

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Calculated χ^2 Self esteem b/w categories of out of school children =7.16, $\alpha = 0.05$, Table value = 12.6, df =6

Calculated χ^2 Self esteem b/w males and females =1.192, $\alpha = 0.05$, Table value = 7.81, df =3

Table-4 reveals that on the whole most of out of school respondents (43%) had low self esteem followed by 38% who had high self esteem. 15.3% of the sample children had very low self esteem as compared to only 3.6 % of the respondents had very high self esteem. Category wise results show that the excluded (49%) and eliminated children (41%) had lower self esteem as compared to withdrawn children (39%). Statistically there was no significant difference on the level of self esteem between the three categories of out of school respondents ($\chi^2 = 7.16$) as well as between males and females. Children with a healthy sense of self-esteem felt that the important adults in their lives accept them, care about them, and would go out of their way to ensure that they are safe and well and also tend to be motivated and positive. They felt that those adults would be upset if anything happened to them and would miss them if they were separated. Children with low self-esteem, on the other hand, felt that the important adults and peers in their lives did not accept them, did not care about them very much, and would not go out of their way to ensure their safety and well-being. On the other hand, Further, these children reported having a difficult time dealing with problems, were overly self-critical, and easily become passive, withdrawn, and depressed. They were hesitant to try new things, spoke negatively about themselves, were easily frustrated, and often saw temporary problems as permanent conditions. They were pessimistic about themselves and their life; most of them saw no future for themselves.

Children who had high self-esteem had an easier time handling conflicts, resisting negative pressures, and making friends. They laughed and smiled more and had a generally optimistic view of the world and their life. Similarly Baumeister et al (2003) noted that high self-esteem also enhances interpersonal relations, creativity, and conflict resolution and helps people cope with stress and deal with prejudice and mistrust.

Overall the results indicate that sample children had very low to low self esteem. These results are similar to the findings of Donahue (1995) noted that school dropouts tend to have more negative self esteem as compared to learners who attend school. This implies that most sample out of school believed that they were neglected persons. Probably of their harsh living condition and lack of opportunity for education, learning new concepts and peer interaction had lowered their self esteem. Most of these children felt that their future was gloomy and uncertain and thus were pessimistic.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

On the basis of the findings of the study it is evident that children tend to face educational deprivation because of multiple factors. There are certain factors which may be related to the home environment especially domestic responsibilities, poverty and illiteracy of parents, but at the same time school related factors play a significant role in influencing educational decisions also. Many school environment factors such as poor infrastructure, distance from school, uninteresting subject matters may act is deterrents in the educational pursuits of the children. Family and school related factors are supplementary and complimentary in making children out of school. Further, when children are not attending school they are used either as a source to family income or as assistants to their parents in performing various household and agriculture related activities. Not only these children face educational deprivation but also are deprived of

their carefree childhood. This has implications for the self of these children also, because as the results highlighted that many out of school children tend to have low self esteem and self acceptance. These children were generally noted to be dissatisfied with their lives and were not confident of their own selves.

There is a need to view educational deprivation in its broader context and understand its implications for the young and growing children's lives and wellbeing. Being out of school can be detrimental not only for a developing nation like India but also tends to have adverse effect on the self of such children.

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IMPACT OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT AND TRADE ON INDIAN ECONOMIC GROWTH - AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Foreign direct investment (FDI) and trade are often seen as important catalysts for economic growth in the developing countries. Past studies show that FDI and trade have a positive impact on economic growth, the size of such impact may vary across countries depending on the level of human capital, domestic investment, infrastructure, macroeconomic stability, and trade policies. The literature continues to debate the role of FDI and trade in economic growth as well as the importance of economic and institutional developments in fostering FDI and trade. The present paper presents an econometric analysis of impact of FDI and Trade on Economic Growth. The paper uses Econometric tools to present the results

Key words: Foreign Direct Investment, Growth, Technology

INTRODUCTION

Foreign direct investment (FDI) and trade are often seen as important catalysts for economic growth in the developing countries. FDI is an important vehicle of technology transfer from developed countries to developing countries. FDI also stimulates domestic investment and facilitates improvements in human capital and institutions in the host countries. International trade is also known to be an instrument of economic growth (Frankel and Romer). Trade facilitates more efficient production of goods and services by shifting production to countries that have comparative advantage in producing them.

Even though past studies show that FDI and trade have a positive impact on economic growth, the size of such impact may vary across countries depending on the level of human capital, domestic investment, infrastructure, macroeconomic stability, and trade policies. The literature continues to debate the role of FDI and trade in economic growth

as well as the importance of economic and institutional developments in fostering FDI and trade. This lack of consensus limits our understanding of the role of FDI and trade policies in economic growth processes and restricts our ability to develop policies to promote economic growth. This article analyzes the role of FDI and trade in promoting economic growth of developing country like India and the interaction among FDI, trade, and economic growth. We examine data from India over nearly the last two decade. Our results suggest that FDI, trade, human capital, and domestic investment are important sources of economic growth for India. We find a strong positive interaction between FDI and trade in advancing economic growth. Our results also show that FDI stimulates domestic investment. The contribution of FDI to economic growth is enhanced by its positive interaction with human capital and sound macroeconomic policies and institutional stability.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Studies based on the neoclassical approach argue that FDI affects only the level of income and leaves the long-run growth unchanged (Solow, De Mello). They argue that long-run growth can only arise because of technological progress and/or population growth, both considered exogenous. Thus, according to neo-classical models of economic growth, FDI will only be growth advancing if it affects technology positively and permanently. More recent endogenous growth models, on the other hand, imply that FDI can affect growth endogenously if it generates increasing returns in production via externalities and spillover effects. In these models, FDI is considered to be an important source of human capital and technological diffusion. FDI introduces new management practices and organizational arrangements in addition to providing labor training in the host country production facilities. FDI encourages the incorporation of new inputs and technologies in the production systems of host countries.

Applying endogenous growth theory to a cross section of forty-six developing countries, Balasubramanyam, Salisu, and Sapsford show that the growth-enhancing effects of FDI are stronger in countries that pursued a policy of export promotion rather than import substitution. Their econometric analysis indicates that the elasticity of output with respect to FDI exceeds that of domestic capital investment, which implies that FDI is the driving force in the growth process.

Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee examine the role of FDI in promoting economic growth using an endogenous growth model. They analyzed FDI flows from industrial countries to sixty-nine developing countries during 1970–1989. Their results also show that FDI is an important vehicle of technology transfer, contributing more to economic growth than domestic investment. They make a case for a minimum threshold stock of human capital necessary to absorb foreign technologies efficiently.

Several other studies, including Feder, Ram, and Salvatore and Hatcher, have analyzed the export-led economic growth hypothesis. They argue that exports increase factor productivity because of better utilization of capacity and economies of scale. They

also argue that exports are likely to alleviate foreign exchange constraints and thereby facilitate importation of better technologies and production methods. Grossman and Helpman argue that open-trade regimes go hand-in-hand with good investment climates, technology externalities, and learning effects.

Empirical studies by Dollar, Sachs and Werner, and Lipsey generally support the view that open economies grow faster. There are other studies, however, that question the wisdom of trade openness. Rodriguez and Rodrik, for example, present a critical view of the link between open-trade policy and economic growth. They argue that past studies fail to account for institutional differences among countries resulting in an upwardly biased estimate of trade and other policy restrictions. Their analysis shows that the relationship between average tariff rates and economic growth is only slightly negative and nowhere near statistical significance.

The question of whether FDI and trade trigger economic growth or the economic development brings FDI and trade is an unresolved issue. Past studies either analyzed the impact of trade and FDI on economic growth (Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee; Balasubramanyam, Salisu, and Sapsford) or analyzed the effects of economic growth on FDI (Barrel and Pain, Lipsey). A positive effect of FDI and trade on economic growth may simply reflect the fact that FDI is attracted to countries that are expected to grow faster and follow open-trade policies.

It is, therefore, important to understand the interrelationships among FDI, trade, and economic growth. Since theory is unclear, this issue has been the subject of empirical studies.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA

Our econometric model is derived from a production function in which the level of a country's productivity depends on FDI, trade, domestic investment, human capital, and initial gross domestic product (GDP) per capita. The model is based on endogenous growth theory, in the tradition of Balasubramanyam, Salisu, and Sapsford and Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee, where FDI contributes to economic growth directly through new technologies and other inputs as well as indirectly through improving human capital, infrastructure, and institutions (see Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee for the theoretical derivation of this model approach). To assess empirically the effects of FDI and trade on economic growth, we specify the following basic formulation:

$$g = a + b_1 \text{ FDI} + b_2 \text{ TRD} + b_3 \text{ HC} + b_4 \text{ K} + b_5 \text{ G}_0 + c_1 \text{ FDI} * \text{TRD} + c_2 \text{ FDI} * \text{HC} \\ + c_3 \text{ FDI} * \text{K} + d_1 \text{ IRT} + d_2 \text{ TX} + d_3 \text{ GC} + e$$

where g is the per capita GDP growth rate; FDI, the foreign direct investment; TRD, the trade (exports plus imports) of goods and services; HC, the stock of human capital; K, the domestic capital investment; G_0 , the initial GDP (initial stock); IRT, the inflation rate; TX, the tax on income, profits, and capital gains in the host country expressed as percentage of current revenue; and GC is government consumption. The variables FDI, TRD, K, GC are measured as ratios to GDP. Our model extends the work of Borensztein,

Gregorio, and Lee to include the decade of the 1990s when FDI and trade grew rapidly in the developing countries. We also account for interaction of FDI with trade and domestic investment, in addition to human capital.

Past empirical studies have indicated that FDI, trade, human capital, and domestic investment have a positive impact on economic growth in developing countries. We expect the estimated coefficients for these variables to be positive. We also expect positive interactions between FDI and trade and FDI and domestic capital investment in promoting economic growth.

The stock of human capital in a host country is critical for absorbing foreign knowledge and an important determinant of whether potential spillovers will be realized. We postulate not only a positive relationship between FDI and the GDP growth rate but also a positive interaction between FDI and human capital in advancing economic growth. The application of advanced technologies embodied in FDI requires a sufficient level of human capital in host countries. That is, the higher the level of human capital in a host country, the higher the effect of FDI on the country's economic growth.

One of the key questions regarding FDI and economic growth is: "What is the interaction between FDI and domestic investment"? The answer to this question seems to be less controversial in theory than in practice. As argued before, FDI is an important vehicle for the transfer of capital, technology, and knowledge to host countries, thereby generating high-growth opportunities. In practice, however, the growth-enhancing impact of FDI depends critically on the absorptive capacity of a host country and whether FDI "crowds out" its domestic investment. Thus, an important question to be addressed is: "What is the extent to which FDI substitutes for or complements domestic investment"? In our empirical model, we include FDI and domestic investment separately as well as an interaction term between FDI and domestic investment ($FDI * K$). The interaction term estimates the combined impact of FDI and domestic investment on growth and indicates the nature of the relationship between the two. A positive coefficient for the interaction term would suggest that FDI and domestic investment (K) reinforce (complement) each other in advancing economic growth.

The initial GDP, measured in terms of constant U.S. dollars, controls for preexisting economic and institutional conditions in the host economy. We expect the initial GDP (expressed in logarithms) to be negatively related with GDP growth rates. The inflation rate is a key indicator of fiscal and monetary policies of a country. A lower inflation rate should mean a better climate for investment, trade, and, therefore, economic growth (Fisher and Modigliani, Froot and Stein). Government consumption and tax on income, profits, and capital gains are proxies for institutions and infrastructure in the host countries. Since our objective is to quantify the effects of FDI and trade on economic growth, we focus on India.

Parameters of data for our analysis are obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) database. The WDI database, published by the World Bank and International Monetary Fund, includes variables such as GDP, per capita income,

GDP growth rates, FDI, trade in goods and services, domestic capital investment, human capital, market openness, inflation rate, tax income, and government consumption. The data cover Indian scenario for the years 1992-93 to 2008-09 from the sources like Reserve bank of India ;National Council for Applied Economic Research ;Economic Survey of India ;Union Budget of various issues. However, we limit our analysis to 1992-93 through 2008-09 because the flow of FDI to most developing countries began in 1970s. All variables represent the average over the following years: 1992-93 to 2008-09.

We estimate a system of three equations, where the dependent variables are the mean values of per capita GDP growth rates in each year. We estimate the system of equations using the seemingly unrelated regression (SUR) method approach. The SUR estimation allows for different error variances in each equation and for correlation of these errors across equations (Greene), while the instrumental variable technique allows us to overcome potential biases induced by endogeneity problems between FDI and economic growth.

EMPIRICAL RESULTS

The purpose of our empirical investigation is to analyze the effects of FDI and trade on economic growth and to examine how FDI interacts with trade, human capital, and domestic investment in advancing economic growth in developing countries. We control for preexisting economic conditions by including initial GDP as one of the explanatory variables. We also account for differences in macroeconomic policies and institutions in the host country by including variables, such as inflation rate, tax burden, and government consumption.

We test the effects of FDI and trade on economic growth in a framework of cross-country equations utilizing data from developing country like India over the last one and half decades 1992-2009. The system has three equations, where the dependent variables are the per capita GDP growth rates (mean value) in each year. We constrained the model such that all three equations yield the same coefficients in the seventeen time periods with the exception of the intercepts.

Table 1 presents the econometric results and compares alternative specifications. Regressions 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, different variants of equation (1) above, are estimated using the SUR method. Regression 1.1 is our basic specification with explanatory variables of FDI, trade, human capital, domestic investment, and initial GDP. Regression 1.2 extends 1.1 to include interaction of FDI with trade, human capital, and domestic investment. Regression 1.3 (final specification) builds on regression 1.2 by controlling for inflation rate, tax burden, and government consumption. Our results show that most coefficients have the expected signs, particularly in specification 1.3. Note that signs change for some coefficients across specifications. The estimated R^2 are generally high given the cross-sectional nature of the data used.

Regression 1.1 reveals that FDI and trade have a negative impact on economic growth

after controlling for human capital, domestic investment, and initial income (table 1). The estimated coefficient for FDI is negative and statistically significant while the estimated coefficient for trade is not statistically significant. Since the coefficient of FDI is larger than the coefficient of trade, it indicates the differential impact of FDI in the host country's economic growth. The coefficient for human capital is negative, implying that human capital contributes negatively to economic growth. The coefficients for domestic investment and initial income are not statistically significant.

Including interactions between FDI and trade, FDI and human capital, and FDI and domestic investment not only improves the overall performance of the estimation but also allows us to capture their interaction effects on economic growth (table 1). In regression 1.2, the interaction of FDI and trade yields a negative and statistically insignificant coefficient while the effects of FDI and trade, by themselves, are negative but not statistically significant. Regression 1.2 also reveals that the FDI interacts negatively with domestic investment in advancing economic growth. The estimated coefficient for domestic investment is negative and statistically insignificant. The estimated coefficients indicate that host countries benefit negatively both from FDI, itself, and through FDI's negative interaction with trade and domestic investment. The interaction between FDI and human capital, although positive, is not statistically significant.

Regression 1.3 includes additional variables to control for macroeconomic policies and institutional stability that could have a significant impact on FDI and trade and, thus, on economic growth. Recent literature indicates that FDI is greatly influenced by host country policies, such as monetary, fiscal, and open-market policies. We include inflation rates, tax income, and government consumption to be proxies for monetary and fiscal policies, as well as institutions in the host nations. Inclusion of these policy variables significantly increases the explanatory power of the estimated system (table 1).

The results of regression 1.3 reveal that FDI and trade contribute positively to economic growth, but the estimated coefficients are not statistically significant (table 1). The stock of human capital and domestic investment, on the other hand, have positive and statistically insignificant coefficients. The results also indicate that FDI negatively interacts with trade, human capital, and domestic investment. But only FDI-trade interaction is statistically insignificant. This implies that FDI and trade do not complement each other in advancing growth rate of income in India. This result is inconsistent with the idea that flow of advanced technology brought along by FDI can increase the growth rate of the host (India) economy by interacting with that country's trade.

The experience from India suggests that FDI and trade, by themselves, may not guarantee economic growth. A country's economic growth is also affected by its macroeconomic policies and institutional stability. Sound macroeconomic policies and institutional stability are necessary preconditions for FDI-driven growth to materialize. The estimated coefficients for the three policy variables—inflation rate, government consumption, and tax on income, profits, and capital gains—are negative and statistically insignificant. This implies that lowering the inflation rate, tax burden, and government

consumption would promote economic growth. Lower inflation rates would indicate that the host country's macroeconomic policies are stable and disciplined. Lower tax burden would make the investments, both foreign and domestic, more profitable. Decreasing the government consumption would leave more money for investments.

FDI "CROWDS-IN" DOMESTIC INVESTMENT

One of the important questions raised in the literature is whether FDI augments a host country's capital investment or crowds out domestic investment. Even though not statistically significant, the positive interaction between FDI and domestic investment in regression 1.3 implies that domestic investment is unlikely to be crowded out in India.

To further strengthen our argument, we estimate the contribution of FDI to domestic investment after controlling for trade, human capital, initial income levels, and various macroeconomic policy variables. Regression 1.4 in table 1 presents the results of this estimation using the SUR method. The results indicate FDI has a positive effect on domestic investment, as the estimated coefficient is positive and statistically insignificant. This positive relationship implies that FDI stimulates or crowds-in domestic investment. This finding is consistent with Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee. Even though trade, by itself, is not statistically significant, trade interacts negatively with FDI on domestic investment. The estimated coefficient for the FDI–trade interaction term is negative and insignificant.

ENDOGENEITY PROBLEMS

The correlation between FDI and growth rate could arise from an endogenous determination of FDI. That is, FDI, itself, may be influenced by innovations in the stochastic process governing growth rates (Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee). For example, market reforms in host country (India) could increase both GDP growth rates and the inflow of FDI simultaneously. In this case, the presence of correlation between FDI and the specific error term would bias the estimated coefficients.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper analyzes the role of FDI and trade in economic growth of India within the endogenous growth-theory framework. Using cross-section data relating to India over seventeen years, we show that FDI and trade contribute toward advancing economic growth in India. There is a strong, positive interaction between FDI and trade. FDI is often the main channel through which advanced technology is transferred to India. Our results imply that the benefits from such investment would be greatly enhanced if the host (India) country has a better stock of human capital. We also show that FDI stimulates domestic investment. Sound macroeconomic policies and institutional stability are necessary preconditions for FDI-driven growth to materialize. Our results imply that lowering the inflation rate, tax burden, and government consumption would advance economic growth in India.

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TABLE-1
SUR ESTIMATES

	Dependent Variable Per Capita GDP Growth Rate	Dependent Variable Per Capita GDP Growth Rate	Dependent Variable Per Capita GDP Growth Rate	Dependent Variable Domestic Investment
Independent Variable	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
Intercept	12.557 (8.58)	-18.184 (23.87)	-13.114 (40.787)	-9.861 (15.883)
FDI	-1.134 (1.06)	9.349 (10.228)	13.56 (13.027)	1.031 (3.436)
Trade	-0.901 (1.148)	6.271 (4.858)	7.146 (6.461)	-3.159E-02 (1.781)
Human capital	-9.889 (7.995)	-3.245 (15.541)	2.775 (22.158)	-0.142 (12.182)
Domestic investments	0.127 (0.428)	2.503 (1.656)	3.336 (2.071)	
Initial GDP per capita	1.052 (0.608)	1.93 (0.797)	2.148 (1.046)	3.839E-02 (0.523)
FDI * Trade		-3.139 (2.240)	-3.819 (2.793)	-0.119 (0.556)
FDI * Human capital		1.863 (7.177)	-5.888E -02 (8.673)	-0.79 (5.159)
FDI * Domestic investment		-1.235 (0.850)	-1.461 (1.029)	
Inflation rate			2.061E-02 (0.027)	-1.088E-02 (0.015)
Tax rate			-0.286 (4.484)	-0.509 (2.642)
Government consumption			-0.989 (1.348)	1.149 (0.677)
System R2	0.544	0.668	0.733	0.953
DW	0.917	1.594	1.872	2.005
F-value(sign.)	0.085	0.171	0.430	0.001

Calculated F-value
E is attached with (-02)

2.621;F(5,11)	2.014;F(8,8)	1.245;F(11,5)	15.719;F(9,7)
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Note:-figures in parenthesis under the concerned estimated coefficient show their standard error of estimate.

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WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH SELF-HELP GROUPS: SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF WOMEN IN ASSAM WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO NALBARI DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The term women empowerment and self-help-groups are closely interrelated. Now-a-days, every individual want to be self-dependent for which the opportunity of engagement is utmost important. Even women want to do something for earning to them as well as to support their families. In this regard, the formation of Self-Help-Groups will play a vital role in women empowerment. In fact many of the women forming Self-Help-Groups as a source of income. It has been widely recognized that unless women's potential is properly developed, transformation and economic development is not possible. Therefore to accelerate the growth and prosperity of the nation, it is very important to create opportunities for socio-economic development especially for women. The present paper is a modest attempt to highlight some of the basic ideas to reflect the economic status of women through Self-Help-Groups in different areas. It is also aimed to create the awareness among the women to generate income in order to contribute by them towards the development of the economy. Women are still considered in rural areas that they must be within the boundary of the household. So this study has been carried out with the object to make the people aware how they can explore their skills and mobilize the resources available in the area of the study.

KEYWORDS: *Self-help-Groups, unemployment problem, women empowerment, generation of income.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Women are the creator of society. Once the first Prime Minister of India Jawaharlal Nehru said, “You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women”. The status of women has been a matter of scholastic dispute which remained unsettled everywhere is it in Asia, Africa or Europe or in other parts of the world. Women are the backbone of a nation. So the improvement of social status of women in Nalbari district through Self Help Groups can contribute positive role towards the economic development. The District of Nalbari basically agrarian place where more than 80% people are dependent on an agricultural sector. Now the question is how women are engaged themselves in economic activities. Now-a-days the rural women are also aware about their earnings for which they form the groups and start functioning as a group. It helps not only them but also to the society.

The study has been conducted among the Self Help Groups of different blocks to make sure that women are no more behind than men. Every individual want to be Self-reliant for which the opportunity of engagement is vital matter. In fact it is true that contribution of each individual towards economic development has a positive impact. So, unless women’s potential is properly developed, transformation of rural economy and economic development is not possible.

In Assam there are total 12878491 female and 13777037 male which states that the population status of female are 48.31% which is almost half of the total population. In Nalbari district the female population is 48.44%, which is almost half of the total Population of the district (as per census 2001). At the same time the literacy rates of female in the district is 57.26% which is more than female literacy rate of Assam i.e. 54.61%. The total number of self Help Groups in Assam is more than 90000 working in diverse fields in Assam.

Therefore, to accelerate the growth and prosperity of the district it is important to create opportunities especially for women. This study has made an attempt to create awareness among the women of the district about the scope of Self-Help Groups. In fact state and Central Government have given the due importance on formation of Self-help Groups through the aim of Self Help Group is to boost up the Human resources in the form of economic activities.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the socio-economic status of women in the district of Nalbari through the activities of Self Help groups.
2. To measure the performance of Self-Help Groups in the district.
3. To include the savings and Credit habits among the members of the Group for creating a common fund through small Savings to meet the future needs.
4. To encourage rural poor women to promote their economic status by utilizing the skills and knowledge owned by them and acquired through training.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

“A sustained effort to empower women is essential to deliver are commitment to ensure equality with respect to political, economic and social rights” – President Pratibha Patil said.

It is an accepted fact that women play a matchless role in the progress of a man and the family. In the district of Nalbari more or less 85% women are household wife, therefore development of women is essential. Now-a-days women also want to earn something by themselves. The role of women in the economic progress of a nation is also valuable. Another fact is that in the rural area there is a drawback of the women in each family that they are supposed to stay in the family boundary. But this misconception has been waved out and women are now playing a major role in socio-economic development.

Women empowerment is critical to the process of the development of the community. Bringing women into the main stream of development has been a major concern of the Government since independence. Yet, despite significant steps taken by the Government, the participation of women in all Spheres of life varies in the context of differences in the social economic, cultural and regional factors. It is being increasingly realized that the goal of poverty alleviation can't be achieved without the full and achieve participation of women who constitute a large section of the work force in the States economy. In order to empower women and bring them into the mainstream, an enabling environment with requisite policies and programmes, institutional mechanism at various level and employment has special components for women in all programmes need a certain amount of funds is earmarked as 'women's component' to ensure a flow of adequate resource for women in the SHGS and user Groups.

They also take on the responsibility of operation and maintenance of the assets created. The major significance of the study lies in examining and evaluating Self Help Groups as a change agent which has been designed systematically to create income generating opportunities for rural women.

4. METHODOLOGY

Keeping in mind the aims and objectives of the study the following methodology have been applied:

1. The blocks of the district randomly selected on the basis of certain criteria such as population, awareness among the women attitude of the women etc.
2. From the selected blocks, the Self Help Groups have been taken and few blocks have been visited.
3. The study was conducted in the period of 2009 Oct- November on the Self-Help groups.
4. The activities Performed by them are verified and individually meet the members of some groups.

5. A few Non-Government organizations such as AASHA, Pancharatna have been visited in order to collect information about the activities performing by them.
6. The selected blocks were-Pachim Nalbari Development blocks, Chamata; Barkhetri Development blocks, Mukalmua; Tihu Development Blocks, Tihu; Madhupur block.
7. Primary data have been collected from SHGS in the district through field survey.

In order to collect information from Self-Help Groups a designed questionnaire has been prepared. We personally meet the members and distributed the questionnaires among them to collect information.

5. SAMPLE SIZE

The study was carried out with 10 Self Help Groups of each visited blocks of the district and some working women who were interested to work as a team through SHGS.

6. AN EMPIRICAL EXERCISE

The concept of SHGS got a major impetus after New Delhi launched the Swarnajayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY)- a programme aimed at bring families above the poverty line by ensuring a sustainable level of income over a period of time. The SHG Schemes have led to silent economic revolution sweeping through rural Assam. This is a good sign as people are getting involved in Self-Enterprise. Under this programme, SHGS can avail themselves of assistance in the form of bank loans, supported by back-ended Government subsidy-a group can avail itself of a Govt. Subsidy up to Rs. 1,25,000. From dairy to mechanized farming, weaving, poultry, food processing units and mushroom cultivation, people of the district are busy setting up micro enterprise by forming SHGS. It can be mentioned that by forming SHGS being transformed to same of the women can earn their livelihood. Aiming to encourage Self reliance among women across the country the central Govt. had allocated Rs. 20 Core for extending women SHGs to every block in the Country. The women and child development Ministry Swayamsidha Scheme for holistic empowerment of women through SHG formation has its presence in 650 blocks of the country, catering to 9,30,000 women in 53000 such groups. At the same time the groups would also be given access to micro-credit from various financial institutions for taking up projects-earnings from which would in turn add to economic resources of the groups. Finance Minister Pranab Mukharjee said, at least 50% of all rural women in the country would be enrolled in SHGs over the next five years and these in turn would be linked to banks.

In the area of Naroa, few SHGs formed by women started their functions in the area of weaving some are in piggery and many more. Basically women of Nalbari district are more efficient in weaving sector, so they formed their groups and motivated the other women who have not yet formed their groups to think over it. It is also observed that in a village there are minimum 10 SHGs involving in different activities.

The performance of SHGs as per the report of Block officials is as follows:

Sl.No.	Name of the Block	No. of SHG Formed	No. of SHG in 1 st grading	No. of SHG in 2 nd grading	% of 1 st grading to total no. of SHG	% of 2 nd grade to total SHG
1	Mukalmua/Barkhetri Dev. Block	420	210	128		
2	Tihu Block	745	310	111		
3	Paschim Nalbari	512	315	58		
4	Madhupur Dev. Block	319	25	15		

Source & Field survey Oct-Nov-Dec 2009.

Generally a SHG may consist of 10-20 persons. However in difficult areas like disserts, hills and areas with scattered and sparse population these members may be from 5-20. All members of the Group should belong to families below the poverty line, However if necessary 30% of the members may be above the poverty line. After formation they are allowed Rs. 25000 as loan out of which Rs.15000 is subsidy to the groups.

6. CONCLUSION

Empowerment process starts with the very beginning of group formation. Gradually the members of the groups became aware about various social and technical issues related to the activities of the group. At first they gather the information from each member by experience sharing. They also get the opportunity to be exposed with Govt. agencies, panchayats, Bank, Block, officials etc. They prepare the project based on different views and opinions of members and fixed their area of activities accordingly the groups working as a group.

The members of Self Help Groups are very much aware about their savings. The women of the groups have been able to access the information about their activities. Looking the achievement of the existing groups other household wife are also interested to become self department. The vision of Assam is Endeavour for creating a Self-sustained habitat with secure livelihood for the poor and the disadvantaged section of the society with the perspective of living in harmony with nature and one another.

7. LIMITATIONS

Although women constitute almost half of the worlds population, but they are under privileged in some cases. The head of the family member don't allow the women to constitute the groups for working outside the area. They must be within the boundary of their residential area in case of social activity. The difficulties found out from the study are:

1. Lack of awareness
2. Poor infrastructure facilities.
3. Fear of failure.
4. Fear of competitiveness.
5. Fear to get properly equipped of opportunities.
6. Lack of finance etc.

8. SUGGESTION

1. Need local resources based training programmes for SHG members to enable them to collect raw materials, production and marketing.
2. Since most of the SHG members are housewife, home based production should be promoted so that the members can make optimum use of their time to get required assistance form her family members.
3. Publication at local level by Government regarding the success stories of SHGs to encourage the members and more motivation towards their goals.

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INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY A DEVELOPMENT KEY FACTOR OF TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

This is the age of technology and if we go through deeper levels its sound that this is the age of information technology. In this era man does not deserve, information deserves and this information helps man to be update and would be the fittest in this world where only one law of survival is applicable fittest will survive.

Today the tourism industry also got the information hungry and without the help of today's information technology it's impossible to deserve in the world of information. The tourism industry is a such type of industry where it has an un-organized form where only one man army is working and also well organized sector where is a giant corporate world do the same job. In this diversified industry only correct information will help the tourists and also the industry to do their job perfectly and with satisfaction to himself and their customers also.

Accordingly, various high tech information and communication technologies are in use in the tourism sector around the world. they are used for tourism product development, marketing, providing services, getting information, distribution and training of tourism sector personnel. These technologies are so indispensable in order to find out and satisfy the ever-changing demands for tourism products. One of the unique characteristics of tourism products is the need of the role played by the so-called travel intermediaries. These travel intermediaries are travel agents, tour

operators, conference organizers booking agent etc. They are so important because of the nature of the tourism product, intangibility and it's highly perishable.

This paper discuss thoroughly that what is the role of information is tourism and how technology affect it. How technology meets the requirements and need of the tourists to a tour facilitator and the correct information to a tourist about destination and facilities which he can got. Also it discusses how information helps manage the huge process of this service sector.

INTRODUCTION

Sporadic travels by the nomads in ancient times has now become the world's most flourishing industry namely Tourism. Early man traveled under compulsion primarily to satisfy his biological needs. In letter ages, the travel led for political, business and religious purposes. As technology and science advan ced inleaps and bounds, coupled with industrialization it led to economic and social progress. Today tourism is concerned with pleasure, holidays travel and going and arriving somewhere. These are the motivation that make people leave their "normal" place of work and residence for short term temporary visits to "other" places.

In order to travel to a particular area there must be a reason just like a person many travel for leisure. business , visiting friends and relatives ; health , education rtc. The person many choose a destination for one or the other reason . Today Travel and Tourism is the industry of moving, Housing feeling and entertanning people as they go from a place of their habitat of another for bussness or pleasure. Transport is necessary to travel and accommodation to stay at the destination. So tourism as an industry has three major compondnents: Attraction, Accommodation and Transport. in the devlop world, today all these components have reached at their zenith in satisfying their customers need aided by modern technology. These components have also come a long to offer a range of products which suit the need of multitude tourism around the world and are still working hard to cater to an ever changing test of them ,Now tourismbecame a socio –economic phenomenon and this has evolved into one of the largest and fasted growing industries of the world .

TOURISM INDUSTRY – A MINGLING OF MULTI-COMPONENT

Tourism is a multi-component industry, many parts of which are inextricably linked to other economic sactors such as airlines to tranportatio; souvenir shops, concession stands and restaurants to retail or service ; hotel and other accommodation to commercial. development as indicated above the tourism industry is made up of there majior component :namely ,

- I. Attraction sector which comprises man made and nature attraction which are developed it satisfy visitors' educational, recreational, aesthetic needs etc.
- II. Transport sector, which includes air, water, and surface transport.

- III. Accommodation sector, all type of establishments that offer lodging to visitors (Hotel, Motel, Guest houses, Youth hostels etc.)
- IV. According to a survey of the World Travel and Tourism named ' Broadening the Mind , published in the 'Economist 'state that the size of the travel and tourism business is difficult to comprehend because of its multi component model and vast distribution .

TOURISM COMPONENT & INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

In this throat cutting competition scenario each component want to maximum benefits and want to attract person towards it. Also the technology change man's behavior and today person want to thing can be getting easily; effficently and on his doorsteps, that why every sector now equipped with the new tools of Information technology.

ATTRACTION SECTOR: In the case of attraction both man made and natural attraction owner need to communicate or inform their customers and potential about their production. information about the kind of attraction .where they are located and how to get there is of vital information .the attraction owner particularly the national tourism offices discharge their duty of promoting their country.s tourism attraction through promotional video . Internet web Sites,television advertesments and travel documentaries are the ,main imformation dissemination tools .

ACCOMMODATION SECTOR: In the accommodation sector also the contribution of information technology is prominent .Any individual or group to any part of the world now has an easy access to the accommodation service providers. A visitor can access information about the kind of hotela at the destination, their ranges of product, the price and other relavant information without leaving his/her office or home .What one has to do is to ring up a travel agency and get the export advice. this will help any visitor greatly as to where to stay during any kind of away from home. Here the information can be obtained aided by still or moving pictures in order to give an exact feature of an accommodation , facilities and services of ones choice .At a destination also visitors are at ease during their stay in every respect , in getting information about their business ,family or other information back home. They are also at ease to relax with the video and Television entertainment programs, which nowadays are part and parcel of many accommodation units.

In the case of buses coaches and taxies in many countries with develop tourism business they are equipped with radio communication systems for various uses . For example , the driver or the tour guide update the Tour Company headquarters about the period of the tour throughout the touring period. This communication ensures the safety of tourist . Fast and easy information flow is of paramount importace to build confidance in the traveling public . In recent years the confidance built due to the use of modern I.T. has been demonstared by a tremendous increase in the number trevelrs worldwide.

WHY .I.T. IS NEEDFUL BY TOURISM INDUSTRY

There are some basic reasons which are applicable to all over the world justified the need of the information technology in the tourism industry.

1. Being a competitive industry with new entrance of global players coming from abroad.
2. Continuously change in customer demands.
3. Expectations of a tourist are increased and look for more convenience and value.
4. Tourists are getting knowledgeable.
5. There is a need of automated technologies.

WHO NEEDS AND WHICH TYPE OF INFORMATION?

There are several components, sectors and organizations which consist in Travel and Tourism Industry. Mainly travel and tourism industry is made of tourist, travel agents, service providers and Govt. & Private offices of consultants and they need the information according to their needs.

Tourist a key consumer needs details on destinations, facilities, availabilities, prices, and geography & climate information. If it is out of country then border controls relations. With application of e-tourism, the travelers would be able to make online reservation, bookings and receive immediate confirmation; this would remove a lot of obstacles that are faced by a tourist.

Travel agents look information & details about tourist (consumer) trends in the market, service providers, destinations, facilities, availabilities, prices, tour packages and direct contact with other branches.

Service providers need to know details of consumer, travel agents, competitors and agencies, and also he become directly accessible to a customer and this remove many mediators between customer and him, which benefits both the service providers and customer also.

Tourism Offices search for trends in industry, size and nature of tourism flows, policies and plans for development.

THE NEW I.T. TOOLS USING IN TOURISM INDUSTRY

Tourism and Travel Industry – a heterogeneous industry made of complex and consists of many components parts. Intangible and international service industry is getting right business curve backed by information technology now days. The revolution in I.T. field provides us tremendous tools that make I.T. more powerful and much easy to reach on the appropriate information. There are so many types of tools which make it powerful, easy and popular such as:

DATA MINING SOFTWARE: Collaborative filtering and Personalization softwares are some data mining software. These applications use the customer database to identify of customers like preferences, interests, travel patterns, people needs and their consumerist behaviors like preferences, interests, travel patterns, people needs and their consumerist behaviors etc. This can help service providers to customize their products, and planning of marketing strategy.

KNOWLEDGE-BASED SOFTWARE: These are the softwares based on the belief that people want more choice but they just do not be burdened with those choices. This type of software takes criteria set by customers and goes into digital databases. It then gets available choices for the customers. This type of software not only automatically finds information for customers but also narrow down the choices and lets customers find th best deal. The emergence of this type of software may challenge the eservices and products of intermediaries. In this scenario, products/ services have to be extremely competitive to be picked. In customers will not rely on advertising to obtain the desired information which is a threat to the very nature of advertising.

EMAILS AND WEB SITES: The system of E-mails and web sites more simplified the life of general public. If a company wants to promote itself, can use these services to promote. If a person wants some information regarding such places or particular services he can also meet his desire with these services.

ELECTRONIC PAYMENT SYSTEM: This type of software enables electronic transaction. It has five significant impacts on business operations. These impacts are:

- It simplifies a very complex buying payment process that leads to a bypassing of intermediaries,
- It assists in monitoring/tracking causal relationship between the effect of ads and purchase patterns,
- It facilitates the efforts required for niche marketing and narrow casting,
- It lowers the barriers into the tourism industry and increases competition, and
- It augments the competitive capability of small organization to expand their business.

VIDEO CONFERENCING

video conferencing is the type of software that allows people to communicate with each other visually, regardless of their physical location. It helps geographically dispersed business to cooperate. That may reduce the need for business travel. However, this technology is still in an infant stage and communications are difficult because certain clues are missing.

VIRTUAL REALITY AND WEB CASTING

Virtual reality displays three-dimensional worlds. Web casting provides online live videos and events. Two things could happen: One is loss or intrigue is one of the reasons that motivate

people to travel. If people can go on the internet and experience vacations, they may lose their motivation to visit that place in the world. The other thing is the balance between advertisement and reality. If people obtain an accurate view of the destination before they visit it, they are going to have really well formulated expectations of what they will see at their travel destination.

CRS (COMPUTER RESERVATION SYSTEM)

Today the CRS system very much simplified and put on some click away the travel and tourism industry. The airline CRS system were the pioneers of computer applications in the 1950s these days' hotel and car hiring companies are also employed these CRS systems. The technology works by using computer of special kind and leased telephone lines. The travel agent is connected on line to the central host computer system or CRS. The host computer is almost always a mainframe with massive database attached. The mainframe host polls each travel agent terminal every second or so, to see if it possible that airlines, Hotels and car rental companies can talk to the travel agent and visa versa. This system contributes to a great extent in increasing sales volume and giving precise information on the availability and selling the products efficiently ensuring substantial gain.

GDS (GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM)

GDSs are system, which distribute reservation, and information services to sales outlets around the World. Unlike the CRSs (Computer Reservation System) used solely by an airline or hotel chain, GDS distribute more than one CRS to users who usually travel agents. Some leading GDS are Amadeus, Galileo, Sabre and World Span.

These world leading GDSs are switches or simply computers that connected on the one side to many end users. The end users of switch comprise travel agents with a single reservation system to support the sale of airline seats and related travel products such as hotel and car hire, via a single computer terminal, usually a Personal Computer. GDSs require massive investment because they are extremely large computer system that link several airlines and travel principals into a complex network of PCs, telecommunication and large mainframe computer.

GIS (GEOGRAPHY INFORMATION SYSTEM)

Geography Information system (GIS) is now recognized widely as a valuable tool for managing, analyzing, and displaying large volumes of diverse data pertinent to many local and regional planning activities. Due to the complex nature of tourism planning issues, the potential of GIS in resolving these issues is increasingly acknowledged. Generally, GIS application in tourism have been confined to recreational facility inventory, tourism – based land management, visitor impact assessment, and recreation–wildlife conflict ; and have been limited by lack of funding and uncoordinated and inadequate data collection procedures.

E-COMMERCE: All those web sites and portals launched by government as well as private organization would offer a wide range of tourism products and services like airlines, hotels, restaurants, camp-site, tours, activity centers, concerts, festivities, shopping and many more with

choicest of assortments of services. By these online sites customer can book his air, train, bus tickets or hire a taxi or reserve a room in a hotel himself without going any where.

Conclusion

Tourism industry is a chain of many service providers. In long term solutions, cost cutting & effectiveness information technology meets the need of these and customers. Information Technology is a unified scheme that brings together all of the components being used (raw data, information, reports, and models) in order to meet specific marketing objectives. The following chart explain it self.

According to the report of WTO (world Tourism Organization) of 2000 “Tourism clearly counts one of the most remarkable economic and social phenomena of the last century. In undoubtedly will keep this position for the century to come. Every year a bigger portion of the world population takes part in tourism activity and for the majority of countries tourism has developed as the most dynamic and fasted sector of economy.”

The tourism sector has experienced rapid technological development. In this new tourism environment innovation and knowledge creation are important for establishing a competitive advantage. This advantage can be accomplished by integrating information systems and organizational knowledge creation creation methodologies. The paper discusses the fields related to tourism and the various technologies available that enhanced infrastructure and can be more enhance the existing infrastructure. The technologies not only solve many problems of this industry but also give a powerful tool for marketing; a one man army can promote himself and his destination via email, website and their blogs also. Hence the Information technology is new tool that not only benefits the service providers of tourism industry but also the super king “Customer” benefited and the environment and destinations also because of current status of site and the situation of services also very much open to all through this Information Technology.

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EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TRIPURA, NORTH-EAST INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper is divided into five sections. The first section present a background and problems of the educational experiences of the indigenous people with relation to their ethnic composition, representation of knowledge and culture; and economic challenges in nutshell from Tripura and adopting few cases from the north-east India. The following sections will discuss the empirical study of the educational experiences of Indigenous people of Tripura. In section two, it deals with the composition of ethnic group and their relationship to understand how they shaped the question of mother-tongue (Kokborok) and their impact on the educational experiences of the indigenous people. The third section, deals with the question of whose culture and knowledge is embedded in the educational experience of the indigenous people. It assumes the curriculum as a bulk of knowledge and a method to assess whose knowledge it represents through the educational experiences of the indigenous people. It will further deal with the controversy of Kokborok language, representation of folktale, indigenous games, indigenous festivals and representation of history to identify the question of representation of culture, knowledge, curriculum and their impact on educational experiences. Fourth section will identify the indigenous people's experiences of socio-economic challenges and how it has an impact on their educational experiences. The final section is an option for change and the author's argument and thought process.

KEYWORDS: Educational experiences, Indigenous people, Representation of Knowledge, Curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

“I wish to read, write and speak in Kokborokⁱ. For example you cannot force a cock to make the sound of a cow rather you also cannot make a tribal student to learn Bengali in the curriculum whose culture is not represented in it...even histories that I read are only that of Indian history and none of the Tripura history are mention in the textbooks”- Nabar

The above statement relates to the crux of the study and is directly quoted from the respondent's opinion whose expression is very similar to their affinity for their mother-tongue and their desire to represent Kokborok in the school curriculum. In the course of their affinity to represent their language “Kokborok”; the indigenous people of Tripura also wish to represent their life and culture. The present curriculum is oppressive to their emotion and psychology. The policy makers have forgotten that the curriculum is embedded in the socio-cultural context of the indigenous people. For a child if reading depicts just a print and does not involve personal engagement or interpretation or if text that they are given has little meaning or relevance, then the outcome will be a cruel kind of literacy, which will remain isolated from the genuine intellectual and emotional development. If Kumar (2011)ⁱⁱ could interpret “reading is a basic to democracy”, then I would subscribe to add that even to read a curriculum with the representation of indigenous life and culture is also a basic to democracy.

The tribes in the North-East Hill states are distinctly different from the tribes in central India since they are not poor or oppressedⁱⁱⁱ but rather being largely reduced to poor peasant (Goswami, 1984). Their opportunity to education is enhance due to the activity of missionaries. The oppression of untouchability does not exist for these tribal's. Their society is not structured in hierarchical social divisions like the social division of Hinduism in the “mainstream” Indian Society. However they equally share marginalization with other tribal's of mainland India (Chanana, 1993). This region finds its attention in the media and public consciousness with the demand of secessionism and ethnic conflict and the operation of military. In such a conflict situation between the different ethnic composition and diversity of ethnics how do we response to the educational experiences of the indigenous people of this region is a challenge. Their educational experiences have not received any attention from the scholars. There is almost absence of similar research done on the educational experiences of indigenous people from 130 major indigenous tribal groups of North-Eastern India whose socio-economic formation is distinct from the tribal's of the mainland India (Sengupta, 2002).

This study is of significance in the context of educational experiences of indigenous people of Tripura. In Tripura there is always a different dimension of question of access, equity and quality in the educational experiences of the indigenous people. Even though a large number of them get admission in school their experiences of education are not similar. Their educational experiences are always shaped with the emergence of social context, ethnic composition and their relations, representation of knowledge and culture and the socio-economic challenges. Since their educational experiences do not represent their life and culture the children from this community experienced education as a form of discrimination, humiliation and alienation.

However, we speak about the access, equity and quality in education it cannot be met in a state of diverse ethnic composition without the representation of indigenous people in educational experiences. The educational experience for indigenous people is not just curriculum, teacher and student alone; rather how they experiences with it. Their educational experiences include in terms of accessing formal education and being there. It also includes their experiences of interaction within and outside the classroom, with curriculum, authorities, teachers, examination and morning assembly. The school rituals and celebration and the representation of their folktales, indigenous games in existing curriculum are all influence by the forces of larger socio-economic context.

The vexed issue of school instruction in the language of the dominant culture has become the most vexed issue in Tripura but it has a different facet due to its ethnic composition and relation of different ethnic groups to each other (Barbora, 2002). The composition of different ethnics and their relation to education gives diverse educational experiences to the indigenous people. Attainment of education by the indigenous people in Tripura has been a dream for many of the educational aspirants. But as they grow within the arena of classical^{iv} type of curriculum they experienced education in an alien forms. They have to face the symptoms of the bad policies which neither have relevance to their life nor they are represented. Education which is supposed to be the mechanism to social change rather has demoralized them. Education is no more considered an agent to bring change for this indigenous people rather it has imposed on them to appreciate other life and culture without questioning rationally. The curriculum has imposed on them to hate their own cultures and diverted their attention and appreciation to other cultures and instilled on them to feel inferior on their own cultures and accept the culture of dominant people forcefully.

This same kind of educational experiences is also shared by some other indigenous people of North-East Hill States. The demand for mother-tongue in the medium of instruction has been noted by ethnic indigenous community of North Cachar Hills, Assam. In the case of this Dimasa community (largely inhabit in North Cachar Hills) as examined by Barbora (2002) from his field work experiences, he writes that though there was a strong affinity from the Dimasa community to introduced Dimasa language at the primary school, the district committee have neglected it. Thus Dimasa textbooks for the primary classes are prescribed and published by the Assam Text Book Production and Publication Board. Most of these prescribed textbooks still remain in the godown without finding its scope to be use by the Dimasa community. Consequently when the Dimasa youths demanded for the introduction of Dimasa language in the Primary Schools of North Cachar Hills (N C Hills), the district council later encourages the replacement of Bengali and introduction of English in the Primary school. Later on, non-tribal job seekers who were appointed in the schools neither knew Dimasa nor Bengali (Misra 1990:194, cited in Barbora, 2002). As a result most of the State runs Schools still use Bengali as the medium of instruction.

In this study indigenous people refers to the term “tribes” who has the same kind of characteristics and nature. The term indigenous is also referred as synonyms to first people, aboriginals and ethnic groups. Thus the issue of the educational experiences of the indigenous people of Tripura cannot be understood without referring to its history. The indigenous people

who are original inhabitant of this State in course of time have lost their representation almost in all the spheres.

Tripura was a Princely state with its mythology that traces back their history to the epic age. The indigenous people with its Huk Khaimani (Shifting cultivation) always like to adhere and habitat in the hilly region while the valley has been populated by the Bengali ethnic group. Surrounded by pre-partition Bengal, the culture and way of life of the valley, the life and culture of the hill dwellers (indigenous people) have been akin to those of any outsider in spite of their own dialect, dances and attire (Das, 1986). "Tripura is the only state in India where successive migration has reduced its original residents to a minority in their own land. Tripura demographic change is a rare event in world history" (Bareh, 2007: 11-17). Thus to understand the sudden demographical shift in Tripura it is necessary to understand the educational experiences of the indigenous people.

The study is an attempt to understand the subjective educational experiences of the indigenous people and the related factor how it shaped their educational experiences. The study is therefore a question to the existing system in educational curriculum. It will question to the controversy of mother-tongue (Kokborok) with the composition of ethnic relations and their representation in the schools. It will also examine to find an answer to how the diversity of ethnic composition and their relations to each other shaped the educational experiences of the indigenous people. It will also make an attempt to relate to the family background, socio-economic challenges and how they are related to each other in shaping the educational experiences of the indigenous people. Finally it will look closer to the educational experiences of the indigenous people to identify whose culture and knowledge get represented in the school curriculum and how they shaped the educational experiences of indigenous people.

This study is conducted through a case study as a qualitative approach to examine the educational experiences of each respondent. Thus a fair exhaustive study of a respondent as to what he does and has done, what he thinks he does and had done and what he expects to do says he ought to do is elicited through the educational life experiences of each respondent through the purposeful sampling technique according to the conveniences of ease to access.

ETHNIC RELATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES

There is a diversity of ethnic composition amongst the different ethnic groups. Some of the compositions of the tribal teachers are "chakma", "Jamatia", 'Kalai', 'Debbarma', 'Tripura and Reang'(ethnic groups). It is noticed that most of the teachers belong to the Bengali ethnic groups.

For the indigenous students the concept of "good teacher" is synonyms to the concept of "guru". It is easily understood that this concept is not drawn from the indigenous concept of teacher or good teacher. It is literary observed that the tribal education does not associate its concept of teacher-student relationship like the Gurukul system of education like that of the Hindu culture. The above concept may have been influenced by the constant celebration and idolisation of Saraswati puja which is imposed compulsory in every state government run schools. In the indigenous peoples world some of the traditional educational systems of Tribal's are like the institution of "Youth Dormitory" practiced among the Oraon of Chotanagpur. Among the Munda

and Ho, the institution of traditional education system is called “*Gitiora*”. Like the Oraons, similarly the “*Naga Morung*” strengthens the sense of social unity to develop the strong competition between the Morungs (there are more than one village) and it stimulates the activities of the whole village (Sachchidananda: 1985). Similarly like many tribal’s community the indigenous people of Tripura also associate their traditional education for boys with skills and knowledge in hunting and Jum cultivation, folk songs and dances, skills in handicrafts, performing rituals and for women the skills in weaving is consider as alternative to education in their society till the modern concept of education was practice.

Generally there is a feeling of invisible biasness felt by the Tribal student in the class. In the case of Manosh (one of the respondent) in one of the incident he was abused by his headmistress by adding filthy words, “*uncivilized and unorganized people*” to denote him. Later he was also labelled by her by calling “*uncivilized people*” for dragging the line during the morning assembly. The above abusive words are used to undermine him for being a tribal student and she finds it advantageous to abuse him in public in front of his friends. The use of the terms “uncivilized and unorganized” to the indigenous people is a telling instance of the re-enactment of the colonial stereotype about the natives. The European colonization has categorized the Asian and African people as uncivilized and irrational. Bengali were at the fore front of countering these colonial description. But in the course of colonial experiences the educated indigenous elite also have internalized these colonial perceptions vis-a-vis the masses and the tribal’s. Since the Bengali themselves perceived as a group endowed with rich cultural heritage it is use to portrait the indigenous people of Tripura as uncivilized.

Both Bengali medium and English medium school do not prescribe to use Kokborok as the subject. The language of mother-tongue is not prioritised by the state government school curriculum. This relates to the reflection or imposition of cultural capital (Bourdieu and Jean: 1973) of the Bengali language that are dominant in their forms of knowledge, skills, and education. Thus educational experiences for these indigenous people are alien to them.

The tribal’s remain silent as soon as they reach at city schools and remain quiet and passive till they adjust with the new environment. The “culture of silence”^v is embedded with the indigenous people after they mingle with the people from the mainstream. Non-Volunteering for class representative by the indigenous people is a generic case of the culture of silence by them.

After the tribal students get admitted in the urban school they experience a sense of inferiority and inability to excel. Thus they remain passive and introvert and they neither speak out to the non-tribal nor do the non-tribal class mates speak to them. They act timid in the class to ask question if they do so they are lead with an assumption that other non-tribal students would level them as scapegoat or impose inferiority complex. This represents the symbolic cultural capital which acts as a multiplier of the productive of the education of educational capital in the form of language, superiority through academic excellence. This power to dominate the disadvantage groups in society was what Bourdieu called as symbolic power. The exercise of this power is called as symbolic violence as introduced by Bourdieu (Saigol: 2000). Thus indigenous people experience education as a form of symbolic cultural capital and embedment of symbolic violence in the school environment.

The concept of proxy teacher has emerged from the respondents. The practice of proxy teacher was related with the reasons of absence of teacher in the schools. Proxy teachers are untrained teachers who work as assistant teacher to the regular government teacher. Kingdon and Rao (2010) added a new concept “Para-teacher” which is very similar to this concept of proxy teacher and define it as contract teachers. According to National council for Applied Economic Research (NCAER, 2008, cited in Kingdon and Rao, 2010:60), it defines Para-teacher as a “universe of teachers in primary and upper primary schools who have been appointed on contract and/or on terms and conditions which are different from the regular cadre teachers in the state”. Proxy teacher in this context is define as the universe of teacher who are employed by the government as regular teacher up to a minimum monthly salary who gives a proxy (attendance) on behalf of the regular teacher and the regular teacher remain at home. An experience teacher (regular teacher) and a trained teacher will always make a difference in the growth of students to understand the basic psychological issues. A child cannot be blame for any silly mistake without questioning to the rationale of its cause and effects. For every mistake a child does in the classroom has a valid reason. This can be understood only by an experienced teacher and not by a proxy teacher. Some of the reasons for the practice of Proxy Teacher that are elicited from the respondents are; the political affiliation to the present ruling political party by the proxy-teacher; conspiracy also happen with the party chairman to avoid the faulty attendance from the inspector of the school.

The education system in Tripura has become commercialized with the practice of forceful system of tuition. According to the respondent commercialization of tuition is practice from the kindergarten to the university level. It can be thus interpreted that there is a creation of market with the sole motive of profit making by the teacher from the student. The teacher acts as a seller and student as a buyer in this case of capitalization of knowledge. At this junction the most oppressed are the indigenous people (students) who cannot afford for private tuition. Profit has become the sole motive of education for the tuition teacher and not the service. If public schools itself becomes privatize than from whom shall the people seek free education. Is this the kind of education the schools would like to impart to the students? The knowledge of the teachers has been capitalized and imparted selfishly to the students. The state government has earlier banned the practiced of private tuition by the government school teachers. But the notification has failed to meet its objectives after the left front backed teachers union opposed the decision. On Dec 27, 2010 the Tripura government has again issue fresh circular to ban the private tuition by the government school teachers after finalizing the implementation of the Right to Free and compulsory Education Act, 2009.^{vi}

REPRESENTATION OF LIFE AND CULTURE: KNOWLEDGE IN CURRICULUM

The medium of instruction of the school is Bengali language if it is a government run school. Whereas they also have one compulsory English subject as second language. English is the first language for the private schools run by the private missionary’s schools.

If the policy makers wish to represent the life and culture of the indigenous people in curriculum it must then strictly introduce Kokborok in all the schools and colleges which is under the control of Tripura State Government. Representing mother tongue can be the best means of representing

their life and culture. Ani (Name of the respondent) seems to be very emotional when she shared her affinity to her mother tongue and the desire thereby to pursue education in her own mother tongue. The curriculum in an instance of making a common language in the school according to the state language in order to achieve nationhood has become an instrument of destruction to the tribal's language, culture and identity. It is been found that even outside the schools the children speaks English with their peer group to mark themselves off from the uneducated or illiterate peer group. Loss of language means absence of knowing certain things in the existing world. Several languages which are spoken by the minority are dying out and vanishing.^{vii}

Thus there is a creation of cultural distance between the Bengalis and the tribal's. The presences of cultural capital with the dominance of Bengali language lead the role. This schools regime of timing, discipline and hierarchy is alien to the tribal children in the socialized world where individual is respected from the early childhood (Sarangapani, 2001 cited in National focus Group, 2005)^{viii} in tribal's world.

The folktale of this indigenous people is very unique and confined only to them. Traditionally it has been practiced during an important occasion to alarm the episode of certain festival or sudden announcement. For example, unexpected death occurrences are notified in the villages by beating a strange rhythm of drum which is understood by all the villages. Like the above folktale and other folktales do not find their representation in the curriculum. If they are not represented at this junction the new generation will forget their culture and traditions. The present situation is slowly becoming difficult to find an indigenous people who can narrate folktales. Retaining of these folktales is a challenge in the curriculum of education. Their detachment from the present curriculum is one of the reasons for being dropout. It was found that some chapters in their English subject depict some probable folktales. Ani (respondent) said that she read a folktale of indigenous people like "Khumpui". Other respondents also said that they have not come across any folktales in their curriculum. Manosh (respondent) has experienced some partial experiences of representation of folktale in their annual school programme. But visibility of folktale is very partial and occasional in the school curriculum. Thus their failure to perform excellent in their academic is not because of their lack of individual efforts alone but it is also the effect of the alienation from their culture and language.

Tripura being a princely state does not find its representation in any of the school curriculum. In the context of these indigenous peoples "history" has a significant role in the formation of the identity and self. There is a celebration of violence and the distinct knowledge of the dominant culture and the legitimacy of the dominant culture.

In another case Saraswati Puja is generally celebrated in all the state-run government school. Attendance is compulsory irrespective of their religion. The indigenous student comes to school on this day not for worshipping or offering ritual but for engaging in entertainment. It was contradictory for an indigenous student what to celebrate between 'Saraswati Puja' and 'Garia Puja'¹ New identities and belief come to shape in response to older cultural identification. This forceful celebration of Saraswati Puja is a domination to accept the culture of dominant people.

¹ Indigenous harvest festival for indigenous people of Tripura

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHALLENGES AND EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES

There is an excessive difficulty for the indigenous people (students) to enhance with minimum educational experiences. They go through a socio-economic challenge for enhancing resources for pursuing education. As they reach to higher standards their expenditure for education increases and it becomes a bottle-neck for them to support their educational expenses. They remain disturbed both emotionally and psychologically to cope up with the challenges to decide whether to continue their studies or leave to surrender it. In one of the respondent's case he certainly even gave a thought to leave his education and to go back to his village like any of his friends. Later on after making a several thoughts he realized education is the only factor which can change his family and society. Again when they come for higher education to Agartala city, they live life with subsistence expenditure to manage their monthly expenditure. For them persuasion of education is never decided according to their interest and aptitude. Their career is plan according to their availability of resources (financial availability) to complete their courses.

There is very little amount of support system received both from the missionaries and non-profit organisations. There are limited government schemes to support them for the requirement of educational expenditure. Neither parents nor the society support them to pursue education. There were utterly different relationship between the parents and the students. Even the environment set up or the social set up is not conducive for pursuing higher education. Their relatives also live in subsistence life and could hardly manage their family by living through hand to mouth. Thus to seek financial support from their family is a far option to decide.

It becomes a turning point for some of the indigenous people student when missionaries admit them in a state's best school like Holy Cross School, Agartala. In one of the case from the respondent it is noticed that he has managed his schools expenditure with the subsidized monthly fees in the missionary's school. If missionary would have not been in his rescue to support his education his parents would have not been free from the clutches of private debt.

Thus an indigenous school going student has to face double burden to receive a favourable higher education with a blend of economic challenges and social challenges. Moreover being a first generation learner and to be a successful educator is all the more a greater challenge. The solution is that one has to just keep on working on their goal in spite of explicit bottle neck while they strive for success. The educational challenges are not only embedded on financial requirement alone but the necessity for educational performances are also relying on the social challenges.

Thus the education experiences of the indigenous people are the assertion of both economic and social challenges. It does create an artificial bottleneck for them to achieve education. It was examined by Chanana (1993) that some of the reasons that affects them in accessing and meeting adequate education needs are lack of schooling facilities or provision of poor quality facilities; lack of financial help and incentive at an early age, discriminatory treatment and attitude of teachers; indifference in parents;(p-86), poverty and lack of economic resources; single teacher schools; utility of their time for earning to make two ends meet-while the young boys earns and girls may either work or look after their younger siblings and relief their mothers

from domestic work; irrelevance of education for immediate 'productive function' instead of deferred 'productive function'.

CONCLUDING REMARK

It can now be analysed and derived to understand that the existence of political agenda in education is complicated and is in a contradictory situation. It also simultaneously inhabits the corridors of powers relations, the socially construction of curriculum, the alien imposition of knowledge to the disadvantaged people who are not in a position to question and reason (Advani: 2009). The educational experiences of the indigenous people are encompassed on certain ideology, aspiration and struggles. The present education system is also embedded on the educational experiences of indigenous people not for a reason to grow as inclusive but just being in the part of the inclusion of education while without actually not being represented in the necessity to inclusive education.

As the nation discusses the construction of nationalism and modernity we also need to ponder upon the identity and indigeneity in the case of indigenous people. For indigenous people their nation is built upon their identity and indigeneity. Nation building and inclusive growth in any country is not possible without the inclusion of identity and indigeneity of the indigenous people in a state of indigenisation. Nicholls (2009) argue that in stereotype approach and he advocated "the prior and ancient claims of indigenous political and cultural sovereignty, while acknowledging indigenous companionship in the metropolitan subject are experience on contemporaneity" (Nicholls, 2009:211). Thus the modernity must be present in the representation of life and culture of the indigenous people without letting behind the representation of the life and culture of the indigeneity.

Thus in a state of Tripura where diversity is enormous with the composition of indigenous people (Tribals) and non-tribals (Bengalis) the impact of educational experiences has different dimension with the increase in the controversy of language. In a situation like this what is the role of the education system in the cultural formation of the self and identity? Do the education experiences here speak about the necessity of self, identity and representation? There is always a question of "yours" and "mine" in the educational experiences context of indigenous people of Tripura. From the words of one of the respondent (*Boyar*)², "*kanborok, chaborok, daborok*"² the above fact is very true.

The purpose of composition of ethnic relation and how it shaped the question of mother-tongue comes from the history of the State. If one cannot understand the history of this state one will fail to relate to the ethnic relations between the tribal and non-tribal and their impact on the education experiences of the indigenous people. Nevertheless the education system has to proceed with the composition of the different ethnic groups and their relations with the mother-tongue of the indigenous people.

² Literary derived from Kokborok languages which means their "life and culture"

The question of whose culture and knowledge has linkages with the representation in their curriculum. Language is one of the factors to represent the culture of individual or community. If language itself is oppressed and suppressed then the question of knowledge and culture will remain hindered and submerged. The language acts as a medium of propagating the culture and representation of self and community and must find its existence together with the life and culture of the dominant culture. The knowledge and culture represented in the case of Tripura is that of cultural capital of the privilege people. The opportunities of the indigenous people to represent and practice their culture and language have been forced to act as dormant in practical. This deculturation (erasure of culture and language), assimilation and policing is a signal of colonial power relations (Carlson, 1997:137, cited in Jain, 2008).

Together with ethnic composition, their relation and their representation of culture and knowledge the indigenous people have experienced socio-economic challenges in their educational experiences. The educational experiences of indigenous people have double challenges together with social construct and economic necessity. Being a first generation learner and an indigenous people their educational experiences have double difficulties to match with the mainstream ethnic groups. The indigenous person from the inception of their education at early childhood experiences the blockage in the economic challenges to support their financial requirement for their education. They are occupied and pre-occupied with emotional and psychological effect due to their socio-economic challenges faced by them since their childhood. Socio-economic challenges of this kind sometimes led the indigenous people to forceful discontinuation of their education.

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END NOTES

i Widely accepted mother tongue for all indigenous people at Tripura, India

ii <http://www.thehindu.com/opinion/lead/article1103118.ece#comments>
(Retrieve on 20th January 2011)

iii Denote to oppression through purity and impurity by birth like the case of Hindu world.

iv Traditional form of curriculum which depict only the life and culture of dominant people

v This concept is derived from Freire Paulo (2005): *Pedagogy of the oppressed*, translated by Myra Bergman Ramos

vi <http://www.tripurainfo.in/Admin/ArchiveDet.aspx?WhatId=9392> retrieved on 27th December 2010 and 7th January)

vii http://www.ncert.nic.in/new_ncert/ncert/rightside/links/pdf/focus_group/position_paper_on_sc_st.pdf

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HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN VIRTUAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Based on environmental changes, especially because of globalization, transformation from the traditional organizations into the new form is critical important issue in today's business world. Further, as human resources are the most important assets of an organization, applying and managing these important resources need to be understood by managers of today's post-industrial organizations (virtual organizations). Thus, this paper attempts to clarify human resource management in virtual organizations. Firstly, by reviewing the relevant literature, various definitions of virtual organization are introduced and its concept is discussed. In the next part, we explain human resource management; and thereafter, we clarify HR activities in a virtual context. Moreover, this paper suggests that electronic human resource management assists HR professionals cope with the new challenges emerging in virtual organizations.

KEYWORDS: Human Resource Management, Virtual Organization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's organizations need to transform from traditional industrial enterprises into the modern post-industrial ones, which contributes to the flexibility and innovativeness of them; and they should pay more attention to factors which facilitate this transformation. Therefore, they should focus on knowledge sharing among personnel and their partners which leads to increase attention toward the use of information technology and helps organizations to adapt themselves to the

rapid environmental changes. Further, the rapid changes in today's global market have contributed to changes in the structure and functioning of organizations (Davoudi and Fartash, 2012a). Considering this, explain the need for a new form of organizational structure i.e. "virtual organization" in today's uncertain environment.

In virtual organizations, personnel operate at a remote distance from one another and also from their managers (Cascio, 2000). As a new concept, a virtual organization (VO) has established an entirely new kind of relationship among organizations, and personnel. There will be no physical presence of workers in such post-industrial enterprises. Further, personnel of a VO, work together through computer network and information technology, though geographically divided.

According to Price (2000), in the virtual era, traditional departments and offices disappear, leaving an amorphous mass of people connected electronically and sharing information through video-conferencing and e-mail, when required. According to Davoudi and Kaur (2012a), over the past decade, large companies and small/medium-sized firms (SMEs) have been required to go global, and with the emergence of "global village" concept, many issues arise in the field of human resource management and organizations are involved in new methods for managing their human resources in Action.

Considering this, explain the need for a new form of Human Resource Management in organization that meets the demands and needs of the management and the employees of today's organization (Davoudi and Fartash, 2012b). Thus, as Davoudi and Fartash (2012b) stated, the requirements for the new form of HRM become apparent; and that is because of the need for HR managers who should be available at any time in any place, and have appropriate interaction with organization's personnel, though they are divided.

2. VIRTUAL ORGANIZATION

In 1986, Mowshowitz coined the term "Virtual Organization". Since then, there have been various researches on this new type of networked organizations. By reviewing the relevant literature, it is inferred that there exist various synonyms to the term Virtual Organization, like: Virtual Corporation, Virtual Enterprise and Virtual Company. But in this paper we use the term virtual organization (VO) for our purpose. Thus, first of all we extracted various definitions of VO from researches as follows:

TABLE 1. DEFINITIONS OF A VIRTUAL ORGANIZATION

AUTHOR(S)	DEFINITION
Dubinskas (1993)	The terms 'virtual team' and 'virtual organization' evoke the special status of groups created through the use of groupware such as computer conferencing.
Byrne (1993)	A virtual corporation is a temporary network of independent companies - suppliers, customers, and even rivals - linked by information technology to share skills, costs, and access to one another's markets. This corporate model is fluid and flexible - a group of collaborators that quickly unite to exploit a specific opportunity.
Klein (1994)	Virtual corporation consists of the company that faces the customer and a network of other companies that co-operate to achieve what none of them could achieve alone. This arrangement permits each participant to concentrate on what each does best and to limit its risks and investments to its core competencies.
Coyle and Schnarr (1995)	A virtual corporation is a temporary network of companies that come together quickly to exploit fast changing opportunities, for example, the making of films.
Hale and Whitlaw (1997)	The virtual organization is the name given to any organization which is continually evolving, redefining and reinventing itself for practical business purposes.
Townsend et al. (1998)	Virtual teams are groups of geographically and/or organizationally dispersed co-workers that are assembled using a combination of telecommunication and information technologies to accomplish an organizational task.
Fitzpatrick and Burke (2000)	The virtual corporation can be defined as a temporary network of independent companies, suppliers, customers, even erstwhile rivals—linked by information technology to share skills, cost, and access to one another's market.
Allert (2001)	A virtual company is where work is performed outside of the definition of place. There's no factory floor, no retail store, no conference room, no cubicle farm. Virtual work is primarily the manufacture, retail, and distribution of intellectual property.

Moreover, there are some factors causing VOs to form. According to Fairchild (2004), the trends that lead to VO have increased in business world. The trends towards VOs are reviewed by (Bleeker, 1994) and are widely cited in the literature. According to Bleeker (1994), four key trends toward VOs can be named as follows:

A) PACE: It is important to note that today's businesses run forward in a high speed which demand flexible organizational structures that able to response to environmental changes immediately. According to Toffler (1970), the business market would turn into "survival of the fastest, not the fittest". And according to Fairchild (2004), this can be witnessed by the compressed life cycles for all activities in the value chain, and hierarchical organizations that cannot respond to new demands.

B) COST: According to Bleeker (1994) the decreasing cost of market entry, like the cost of information services and other technology-driven industries, can be named as second trend toward the formation VOs. Based on Bleeker (1994), in today's industries, "even small undercapitalized startups can have an enormous impact on innovation". Thus, it is inferred that to survive in such competitive market, demands special organizational structure like, that of the VOs.

C) PERSONALIZATION (CUSTOMIZATION): In today's business world, various groups of customers demand different goods or services. As we know, the survival of all organizations depends on their customers satisfaction from the quality of the services and goods they receive. Thus, it is critical important for organizations to identify these different needs of all customers and satisfy their needs; to have a loyal base of satisfied customers. To serve the mentioned purpose, organizations need flexible and responsive structure. As inferred, VOs have appropriate characteristics to do so.

D) GLOBALIZATION: Globalization connotes an expansion of interfaces between nations, the flow of business, goods or capital from one country to another. A global enterprise, (Parker, 1998):

- Draws resources from the world;
- Views the entire world as its home;
- Establishes a worldwide presence;
- Adopts a global business strategy;
- Transcends internal boundaries (of people, process and structure) and external boundaries (of nation, time and space).

According to Brawley (2003), globalization can be defined as follows (cited in Davoudi and Kaur, 2012a):

- A process whereby markets and production in different countries become increasingly interdependent due to the dynamics of trade in goods and services and flows of capital and technology.
- In addition, a change in the nature of goods being traded, with vertical transnational production being fragmented, more intermediate goods crossing borders and corporate strategies based on outsourcing to centers based on international specialization.
- The movement of factors of production from one country to another.
- The integration of financial markets (the most transferable factor of production) and more fluid flows of international capital.
- The creation of a global market based on high levels of cross-border flows of labor migration, trade, communication, transport of goods and other items.

The evidence for the increased importance of international business comes from many fronts (Davoudi and Kaur, 2012a). In addition to the preceding paragraphs, Information Technology enables organizations to adapt themselves with the changes caused by globalization. As inferred, VOs have the most appropriate characteristics to operate in today's global market.

3. HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Human Resource management has grown in its range to the point where it has become an industry rather than just a simple occupation (Davoudi and Kaur, 2012b). According to Armstrong (2010, p. 8), the practice of Human Resource Management (HRM) is concerned with all aspects of how people are employed and managed in organizations. It covers activities such as: Strategic HRM, Human Capital Management, Knowledge Management, Organization Development, Resourcing (Human Resource Planning, Recruitment and Selection, and Talent Management), Performance Management, Learning and Development, Reward Management, Employee Relations and Employee Well-Being. Further, the overall aim of HRM is to enable organizations to be successful through their personnel. According to Armstrong (1999, p. 4) the aims of HRM are as follows (cited in Davoudi and Kaur, 2012b): (1) Provide a range of services which support the achievement of corporate objectives as part of the process of running the organization, (2) Enable the organization to obtain and retain the skilled, committed and well-motivated workforce it needs, (3) Enhance and develop the inherent capacities of people – their contributions, potential and employability – by providing learning and continuous development opportunities, (4) Create a climate in which productive and harmonious relationships can be maintained between management and employees and in which feelings of mutual trust can be developed, (5) Develop an environment in which teamwork and flexibility can flourish, (6) Help the organization to balance and adapt to the needs of its stakeholders (owners, government bodies or trustees, management, employees, customers, suppliers and the public at large), (7) Ensure that people are valued and rewarded for what they do and achieve, (8) Manage a diverse workforce, taking into account individual and group differences in employment needs, work style and aspiration, (9) Ensure that equal opportunities are available to all, (10) Adopt an ethical

approach to managing employees which is based on concern for people, fairness and transparency, (11) Maintain and improve the physical and mental wellbeing of employees.

4. HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN VIRTUAL ORGANIZATIONS

As personnel in a virtual organization work far from each other, it can be inferred that human resource management in these kinds of organizations is performed through electronic human resource management (E-HRM). According to Davoudi and Fartash (2012b), "E-HRM is a way of implementing HR strategies, policies, and practices in organizations with the full use of web-technology-based channels. Thus, E-HRM is the application of information technology for performing of HR activities." Similarly, Voermans and vanVeldhoven (2007) defined E-HRM as the administrative support of the HR function in organizations by using internet technology. Another definition of E-HRM is using computer systems, interactive electronic media and telecommunications network to fulfill HR functions (Strohmeier, 2007). As Zafar (2009) stated, the rise of the knowledge economy is accompanied by a transformation of the bureaucratic organization into one of the networked types. This transformation also becomes visible in the relationship between the individual employees and the organization (Davoudi and Fartash, 2012b). To sum up, the chosen statement by Ulrich (1997) tries to show that the e-component adds a new dimension that 'rocks the HR boat'. In order words, E-HRM forces 'traditional' HR professionals to rethink and redefine policies and practices and, indeed, their own profession (Zafar, 2009).

Obviously, HR activities in virtual organizations pose new challenges to HR managers and call for a newer understanding of the different dimensions of personnel and their problems. According to Thomson and Mabey (1994), "Truly virtual organizations create new problems for human resource management. A networked company does not require a personnel function but its core management must be adept in managing people at a distance, some of whom may not be 'employees' as such. They are true 'human resource managers'." (p. 5).

As inferred, the HR department in a virtual organization should design HR policies which suit the specific requirements of the virtual environment. Thus, in the following part we clarify the human resource management requirements of virtual organizations.

4.1. RECRUITMENT: Virtual organizations must make the optimum use of information technology for recruiting personnel (e-recruiting). E-recruitment (or online recruitment) ensures a faster processing of applications. Online recruitment refers to posting vacancies on the corporate web site or on an online recruitment vendors' website, and allowing applicants to send their resumes electronically via e-mail or in some electronic format (Galanaki, 2002). It also includes the active search of the internet and the location of resumes (Davoudi and Fartash, 2012b).

4.2. TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT: Using the internet in training and development is one of the mostly discussed aspects of E-HR and probably the one with the most potential in terms of cost benefits. The internet can be used in training needs assessment, in pure e-learning activity and in career management (Davoudi and Fartash, 2012b). E-learning refers to the use of the electronic tools to conduct online training for the personnel.

According to Alexander (2007, p. 26), three forms of e-learning platforms are available for training the personnel of virtual organizations as follows:

- A) Computer-based training, where the course information is provided on the computer without any link to external learning resources.
- B) Web-based training, where information is presented through the Internet, intranet and extranet with necessary links with outside learning resources.
- C) Technology-based instruction, where audio-visual tools, including computer and TV, are used extensively for training the virtual employees.

It should be noted that training in virtual organizations should not focus only on the development of skills and knowledge of personnel but also on sharing them among them. According to Noe and Simmering (2002), in the course of training, the HR department must identify the competencies of the employee and ensure that these competencies are shared among other members.

4.3. COMPENSATION: Virtual organizations should apply suitable compensation and reward system which will be different from that of the traditional organizations. Unlike in the traditional organizations, the compensation packages of virtual organizations should be flexible. For instance, According to Davoudi and Fartash (2012b), employee self-service allows employees to submit electronically their preferences in terms of benefit selection, reducing the burden for the HR department.

4.4. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION: As there is no face-to-face interaction between the superiors and the personnel in virtual organizations, the HR department should depend only on the end results produced by the virtual personnel for performance evaluation. Thus, organizations should have clear performance objectives and criteria for evaluating the virtual personnel. According to Davoudi and Fartash (2012b), "E-HRM allows the whole performance appraisal to be conducted on-line, on the corporate internet interface. This means that the manager and the employee are able to submit performance data directly to the HR department in electronic form. This practice, though criticized for the lack of written evidence, reduces paperwork and if read receipts for both supervisor and supervised are used, it can impressively decrease time and cost for the HR department."

4.5. COMMUNICATION: As face-to-face interaction is missed in virtual organizations, with the aid of information technology, human resource should defeat this challenge (E-HRM). As cited in Davoudi and Fartash (2012b), E-HRM includes the use of electronic mail for communication with the personnel. The penetration rate of computer-mediated communication, mainly e-mail, is higher than 75 percent in corporate environments and e-mail has emerged as the communication medium of choice (Bontis et al., 2003).

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present paper attempts to clarify human resource management in virtual organizations. As past researches stated, personnel are the most important resources of all organizations (Davoudi, 2012; Davoudi and Fartash, 2012b; Davoudi and Cherati, 2012; Davoudi and Kaur, 2012a; Davoudi and Fartash, 2012c). Thus, in today's environment, new methods of managing these important resources should be recognized and need to be understood. Only in this way organizations reach to the competitive advantages. Competitive advantage occurs when strategic actions result in resource or capability differences that produce higher organization-level profitability and cash flows (Rumelt, 2003; Pacheco-de-Almeida and Zemsky, 2007). To achieve competitive advantage an organization should be different from its competitors in ways that allow it to earn higher returns. Taking into account the above literature, virtual organizations will face many new challenges which need to be understood by managers. As discussed above, E-HRM is a new method of managing human resources which will decrease organizational costs and increases organizational efficiency, effectiveness and productivity which firstly leads to organizational survival and then leads to organizational success.

Introducing E-HRM in organizations especially virtual organizations will help them to cope with the emerging challenges. Moreover, the introduction of E-HRM to virtual organizations' personnel brings changes in the way they experience HRM in their organizations and in the HR tools and instruments they get offered. They acquire the chance to get updated in terms of organizational dynamics and take part in online communications.

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